

**European Association for the History of Medicine and Health
Biennial Conference**

**Leuven, 7-10 September 2021
Faith, Medicine and Religion**

European Association for the History of Medicine and Health Biennial Conference

Faith, Medicine and Religion

7 - 10 September 2021

Leuven

Book of Abstracts

Program

Tuesday, 07/Sept/2021

3:00pm EAHMH Board Meeting

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4:00pm

4:30pm Opening of the Conference and Welcome by Kaat Wils

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4:45pm

4:45pm Leuven Medical History in 20 slides by Joris Vandendriessche

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5:00pm

5:00pm **Shinjini Das: Sacred Histories of Public Health: Leper Asylums, and the Medical-Evangelical State in Twentieth Century British India**

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6:30pm

Chair: Prof. Frank Huisman, UMC Utrecht. The Netherlands

Wednesday, 08/Sept/2021

9:00am -	1A: Exploring Trust in Oral Medical History Chair: Dr. Felicitas Petra Söhner, Heinrich-Heine-University Düsseldorf	1B: Medical Care and Catholicism in France (1930s-1960s) Chair: Dr. Florent Serina, University of Strasbourg	1C: Catholic Discourses on Reproductive Health in State-Socialist Poland, 1960s-1990s Chair: Dr. Katerina Liskova, Masaryk University	1D: Illness, Gift or Punishment? Medical Examinations of Religious Corporeal Practices in the Habsburg Monarchy, 1830-1870 Chair: Prof. Tine Van Osselaer, University of Antwerp	1E: Learned Medicine and Sacred Diseases Chair: Marc M Dooms, UZLeuven
10:15am -	Break				
10:45am -	2A: Managing Melancholy: Dynamics of Medicine and Religion in the Eighteenth Century Chair: Dr. Catherine Beck, University of Plymouth	2B: Global Hospital Networks Chair: Prof. Jonathan Reinartz, U Birmingham, Great Britain	2C: Faith and the National Health Service Chair: Dr. Rosemary Cresswell, University of Strathclyde	2D: Faith and Mental Illness in the Nineteenth Century Chair: Prof. Herve Guillemain, U of Le Mans, France	2E: Twentieth Century Missionary Health Care Chair: Prof. Frank Huisman, UMC Utrecht, The Netherlands
12:00pm -	Lunch Session 1A: Roundtable Digital Methods in Medical History. Reflections from a Research Project on Religion and Ideology in Nineteenth Century Medicine Chair: Prof. Kaat Wils, KU Leuven		Lunch Session 1B: Roundtable Religious Healing Practices in the History of Nursing Chair: Luc De Munck, KU Leuven		
12:45pm -	Lunch Session 1C: Getting Published: From Thesis to Monograph Chair: Dr. Cara Dobbing, SSHM				
12:45pm -	3A: Bodies out of Control Chair: Kristof Smeyers, University of Antwerp	3B: Health Movements in the Twenty-First Century Chair: Dr. Ian Miller, Ulster University	3C: Old Age in Early Modern England Chair: Prof. Javier Moscoso, CSIC	3D: Religion in Twentieth Century Hospitals Chair: Dr. Joris Vandendriessche, KU Leuven	
2:45pm -	Break				
3:15pm -	4A: Cultures of Healing in the Early Middle Ages (c. 750-900) Chair: Dr. Debby Banham, University of Cambridge	4B: Abortion, Medicine and Morality in the Twentieth Century Chair: Dr. Agata Ignaciuk, University of Granada	4C: German Chronicles of Welfare, Health, and Spirituality, 1750-1900 Chair: Dr. Avi Sharma, TU Berlin	4D: Nurses and Midwives Chair: Prof. Hilary Marland, U of Warwick, Great Britain	4E: Health and Religion in Latin-America Chair: Prof. Frank Huisman, UMC Utrecht, The Netherlands
4:30pm -	Break				
5:00pm -	Anne Harrington: Almost a Miracle: Reflections on a Medical Archive at the Boundaries of Skepticism and Experience Chair: Dr. Rosemary Cresswell, University of Strathclyde				
5:00pm -					
6:30pm					

Thursday, 09/Sept/2021

9:00am -	5A: Animal Magnetism, Hypnotism and Religion in Nineteenth Century Europe Chair: Prof. Heather Wolfram , University of Canterbury	5B: Rethinking Changing Concepts of Health and Disease Chair: Dr. Hieke Huistra , Utrecht University	5C: Faith and Healing in the Middle East Chair: Prof. Javier Moscoso , CSIC	5D: Modern Mental Health Discourses Chair: Prof. Octavian Buda , 'Carol Davila' University, Bucharest	5E: Female Bodies Across Time Chair: Prof. Anne Kveim Lie , U of Oslo, Norway
10:15am -	Break				
10:15am -	Break				
10:45am -	6A: Religious Differentials in Causes of Death, 1850-1940. Part I Chair: Prof. Angélique Janssens , Radboud University Nijmegen	6B: Continuity, Convergence and Consensus Between Religion and the Mind Sciences Chair: Prof. Benoit Majerus , Université du Luxembourg	6C: The Role of Religious Institutions in Health Care: English and Belgian cases Chair: Dr. Joris Vandendriessche , KU Leuven	6D: Reproductive Medicine and (Loss of) Faith Chair: Dr. Anne Hanley , Birkbeck, U of London	6E: Faith, Medicine and the Cold War Chair: Prof. Heiner Fangerau , U of Düsseldorf, Germany
12:00pm -	Lunch Session 2A: Presentation of a Historical Wargame Chair: Jelle Janssens , Ind. Docmaker				
12:45pm -	Lunch Session 2B: Roundtable Religious Medical Heritage in Leuven Chair: Marc M Doods , UZLeuven Chair: Prof. Luc Verpoest , KU Leuven				
12:00pm -	Lunch Session 2C: Roundtable Does Religion Matter for Histories of Reproduction in Post-War Europe? (cases France, Germany and the Nordic Countries) Chair: Dr. Agata Ignaciuk , University of Granada				
12:45pm -	Lunch Session 3: Presentation EAHMH Book Award Winner				
1:30pm -	7A: Religious Differentials in Causes of Death, 1850-1940. Part II Chair: Prof. Isabelle Devos , Ghent University	7B: Missionary and Colonial Medical Practices Chair: Dr. Tinne Claes , KU Leuven	7C: Medical Objects: Faith and Healing Chair: Dr. Joris Vandendriessche , KU Leuven	7D: Faith in/and Psychiatry Chair: Prof. Heiner Fangerau , U of Düsseldorf, Germany	
2:45pm -	Break				
3:15pm -	8A: Roundtable Modern Medicine and Catholicism: Historiographical Challenges Chair: Prof. Jacalyn Duffin , Queen's University	8B: International Scientific Research stays to fight against Infectious Diseases: Faith in Vaccines and Vaccination Chair: Dr. Maria-Isabel Porras-Gallo , University of Castilla-La Mancha Chair: Dr. Marta Velasco-Martín , Universidad de Castilla-La Mancha (UCLM)	8C: Hospitals, Medical Practices and the Church Chair: Prof. Javier Moscoso , CSIC	8D: Moralizing Pregnancy and Infancy through Care Chair: Prof. Hilary Marland , U of Warwick, Great Britain	8E: End of Life: Reflections and Debates Chair: Prof. Anne Kveim Lie , U of Oslo, Norway
4:30pm -	Break				
5:00pm -	Tine Van Osselaer: Between Hope and Resignation: the 'Patient' in Catholic Devotional Culture, Nineteenth and Twentieth Centuries Chair: Dr. Joris Vandendriessche , KU Leuven				
6:30pm					

Friday, 10/Sept/2021

9:00am - 10:15am	9A: Healing Miracles and Medical Expertise Chair: Prof. Vincent Barras , Institute for the Humanities in Medicine	9B: Medical Ethics Chair: Dr. Noortje Jacobs , U of Rotterdam, Netherlands	9C: Religious Actors in Russian and Eastern European Health Care Chair: Dr. Tinne Claes , KU Leuven	9D: From Mesmerism to Jean-Martin Charcot Chair: Prof. Kaat Wils , KU Leuven	9E: Faith, Relief and Medical Education in the Low Countries Chair: Dr. Joris Vandendriessche , KU Leuven
10:15am - 10:45am	Break				
10:45am - 12:00pm	Meet the Colleagues		The EAHMH Buddy Program		
12:00pm - 12:45pm	Lunch Session 4A: Heritage of Care - Care for Heritage Chair: Dr. Kristien Suenens , Katholieke Universiteit Leuven		Lunch Session 4B: Roundtable Does Religion Matter for Histories of Reproduction in Post-War Europe? (cases: Belgium, United Kingdom and Ukraine) Chair: Dr. Agata Ignaciuk , University of Granada		
12:45pm - 1:30pm	Lunch Session 5: Presentation of the European Journal of the History of Medicine and Health				
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2:15pm - 2:45pm	EAHMH Board Meeting				
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3:00pm - 4:15pm	10A: Catholic Doctors and Medical Ethics Chair: Dr. Tinne Claes , KU Leuven	10B: Spiritual Mothers: Medieval Discourses of Medicine, Religion and Reproduction Chair: Lydia Rose Shahan , Harvard University	10C: Cancer and Miracle Cures in the Twentieth Century Chair: Dr. Noortje Jacobs , U of Rotterdam, Netherlands	10D: Fear and Epidemics in Early Modern Europe Chair: Prof. Laurinda Abreu , U of Évora, Portugal	10E: Healing Bodies Chair: Prof. Kaat Wils , KU Leuven
4:15pm - 5:00pm	Break				
5:00pm - 6:15pm	Maria Pia Donato: Medicine and Religion at the Deathbed. Reflections on Death, Dying and the Doctors in Early Modern Europe Chair: Prof. Kaat Wils , KU Leuven				
6:15pm - 6:30pm	Van Foreest Student Award & Closing Remarks by Kaat Wils				

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Keynote presentations

List of abstracts
(in order by program schedule)

Keynote 1: Shinjini Das

Timing: Tuesday, 07/Sept/2021, 5:00pm - 6:30pm

Sacred Histories of Public Health: Leper Asylums, and the Medical-Evangelical State in Twentieth-Century British India

Shinjini Das

University of East Anglia, United Kingdom

To what extent did histories of Christian conversion, public health and the imperial state converge in colonial South Asia? With a particular focus on the leper asylums in British India, I will explore the sustained interaction between the three to gain a deeper understanding of colonial medicine, global Christianity and of colonialism itself. By the first quarter of the twentieth century, medical governance and evangelisation became deeply intertwined in British India. I call this entanglement the 'medical-evangelical state'. The British imperial state and protestant missions collaborated towards building and maintaining leprosy asylums, which became sites for imperial segregation, Christian conversion, biomedical experiments as well as colonial translation and vernacularisation. Indeed, the medical-evangelical state adopted a range of techniques to hegemonize the leper body. A focus on the colonial leper asylum reveals the range of translational practices through which biomedical evangelists and missionaries engaged with the language, culture and the religion of the colonized lepers with a view to convert them to Christianity and/or use them as subjects of biomedical drug trials. Consequently, in the colonial leper asylums, the distinctions between the worlds of faith and science, prayer and medicine, the spiritual and the pathological, the patient and the devotee as well as the imperial scientist and the missionary became blurred. The paper ends by reflecting on the contexts through which it was possible for the colonized leper to question and even resist the authority of the medical-evangelical state.

Keynote 2: Anne Harrington

Timing: Wednesday, 08/Sept/2021, 5:00pm - 6:30pm

Almost a Miracle: Reflections on a Medical Archive at the Boundaries of Skepticism and Experience

Anne Harrington

Harvard University, United States of America

The Lourdes Medical Archive in southern France must be the most unusual medical archive in the world. It contains reports of miraculous healings that do not just consist of testimonies of the faithful, but that have all also been extensively reviewed and glossed by medical authorities, both Catholic and otherwise. The view of the medical committees who assess all the reports is that inexplicable (and potentially miraculous) recoveries are possible, but exceedingly rare. For this reason, of the more than 8,000 dossiers in the Lourdes archive, only 70 have survived the skeptical scrutiny of both medicine and theology. What, though, about the 7,930 other files— all the unheralded, ambiguous, rejected or stalled cases of alleged medical miracles? We should not assume that a “failed” miracle is by definition an uninteresting miracle. On the contrary, the huge archive of unsanctioned miracles stored in the archives of Lourdes has a great deal to teach us about ways that ordinary people in the modern world may struggle to make sense of their intimate experiences of suffering, fear, faith and grace. At the same time, these same dossiers cast fascinating light on what it may be like for an ordinary person to undergo a process of tough-minded evaluation that was historically designed by the Church to privilege expert testimony over personal stories.

Keynote 3: Tine Van Osselaer

Timing: Thursday, 09/Sept/2021, 5:00pm - 6:30pm

Between hope and resignation: the 'patient' in Catholic devotional culture, 19th and 20th centuries

Tine Van Osselaer

University of Antwerp, Belgium

The Emmerick Gedenkstätte in the German town Dülmen, a small museum in honor of the beatified Anna Katharina Emmerick (1774-1824), has the crutch of the famous bedridden mystic on display since the late nineteenth century. The stick is not the only one exhibited at a religiously meaningful location. At several pilgrimage sites, the crutches of those who were healed formed a material sign post of the power of the site. In both instances, the crutches are emotionally loaded objects and whilst they evoke patients at both locations, they narrate quite different Catholic stories of illness and injury. The crutch in Emmerick's case fits a narrative of resignation to God's will and heroic suffering, the crutches at the pilgrimage sites tell a story of hope and trust in divine intervention. One is a symbol of the idealization of patiently suffering through illness and injury, the other of the triumphant victory obtained with the help of divine beings.

What both have in common however is that they give us an insight into how devotional culture has integrated the stories and objects of the sick and suffering. Catholics presented themselves as 'patients' or were presented as such for various reasons. This presentation looks into these different contexts, explores the ways in which this (self-) styling happened, and what this tells us about the Catholic patient of the nineteenth and twentieth century and his/her relationship with medicine. By exploring both story lines (of hope and of resignation), we will see that references to medical expertise were not only ways to strengthen the credibility of a miraculous cure (the 'medicalization of the miracle', as others have shown), but could also become part of the hagiographic and the self-reflective accounts that idealized the Catholic patient and his/her trust in God and medicine.

Keynote 4: Maria Pia Donato

Timing: Friday, 10/Sept/2021, 5:00pm - 6:15pm

Medicine and Religion at the Deathbed. Reflections on Death, Dying and the Doctors in Early Modern Europe

Maria Pia Donato

CNRS, Institut d'Histoire Moderne et Contemporaine, France

Death and dying have long been a fully fledged research object for historians. Since the 1960s, at a time when medicine was profoundly changing Western conceptions of, and approaches to, the end of life, historians, historians of medicine, ethicists and specialists of religious studies have delved into the relations between medicine and religion with regard to death. The ethics and etiquette at the deathbed, and the attitudes towards life and death have been investigated in a historical perspective in the wake of *historiens de la mentalité* like Philippe Ariès and Michel Vovelle.

In dealing with the conflicts between physicians and ecclesiastics in face of the dying in the early modern period, historians usually point at the very limited autonomy of medicine vis-à-vis religion until, in the late eighteenth century, Enlightenment culture and the secularization of European society entailed a more active stance of physicians on the end of life.

The aim of this talk is to survey recent scholarship and revisit the relation of medicine and religion at the deathbed from three standpoints - palliative care, active euthanasia and resuscitation – with a view to offering a more nuanced understanding of how early modern physicians dealt with death and dying.

Panel, roundtable and oral presentations

List of abstracts
(in order by program schedule)

Session 1A: Exploring Trust in Oral Medical History

Timing: Wednesday, 08/Sept/2021, 9:00am - 10:15am

Chair: Felicitas Petra Söhner, Heinrich-Heine-University Düsseldorf, Germany

This panel focuses on oral history as a widely used method of contemporary historical research. In particular, it seeks to engage with historians of medicine regarding conceptual issues with a focus on trust.

First, Söhner/Nebe discuss concepts of trust between eyewitnesses and historians of medicine as a key factor for the success of oral history projects. Then, these challenges are demonstrated using the example of ongoing and planned projects on 'vulnerable groups' (Hinz/Sparing/Löffelbein) and 'elite physicians' in a European perspective (Hansson/Halling).

Keywords: Oral History, Methodology, Biographical Interviews, Trust

“Relationship of Confidence” in Oral History

Felicitas Petra Söhner¹, Julia Nebe¹

¹*Heinrich-Heine-University Düsseldorf, Germany*

In oral history researchers have a special significance, because they enter into direct human interaction. In fact, oral historians play an important role - as collectors and preservers of accounts of human experience. In some way they become the instrument of questioning themselves. But how do historians handle this trust? This directly leads us to two different levels in oral historiography research, where trust must be regarded as an essential precondition.

On the one hand, trust is important during the process of questioning. So the researcher is responsible to recognise the narrator's limits during the process of interviewing. And on the other hand, empathy is needed, when interpreting what is said. In secondary analysis, this dynamic continues to develop.

Not least in view of the increasingly far-reaching digital analysis possibilities offered by technological change, it is necessary to discuss to what extent and how long a relationship of responsibility lasts. Experiences of previous projects (including the project on the history of psychiatry, human genetics, medical child protection) show that, for example, transparency in how personal data and histories are handled is a prerequisite for many respondents to participate in research projects at all.

Against this background, this talk raises questions about the methodological, ethical and legal issues, arising from oral data collection and discusses them based on practical experiences.

Keywords: biographic history, oral history, methodology, trust, data sharing, research ethics

Biographical interviews in psychiatry history and disability studies

Nils Löffelbein¹, Uta Hinz¹, Frank Sparing¹

¹*Heinrich-Heine-University Düsseldorf, Germany*

In view of numerous reappraisal projects on experiences of violence and abuse in European psychiatric hospitals, children's homes and institutions for the disabled after 1945, research into living conditions and everyday experiences in inpatient institutions has recently come into focus in medical history. Current studies on therapeutic and pedagogical practices therefore try to shed light on the perspective of those affected. In the process, the obvious limitations of written records in state-run and church-run institutions become apparent. Interviews with contemporary witnesses are therefore becoming increasingly important in medical history research.

This presentation sheds light on the particular methodological challenges of interviewing eyewitnesses from a particularly vulnerable group of the population, residents of juvenile psychiatric wards and homes for disabled children and adolescents. Since "classic" interview and interpretation methods are considerably more difficult due to the individual needs of the interview partners, alternative ways of obtaining, conducting and evaluating eyewitnesses will also be discussed. It will be argued that in addition to particularities in the communication process, such as barriers to the linguistic expression of experiences, it is also important to consider the specific living situation in inpatient facilities, which is often characterised by lifelong dependency relationships and imprints on the residents. The talk is based primarily on practical experience in conducting eyewitness interviews in European psychiatric hospitals and denominational homes for the disabled.

Keywords: Oral History, Disability History, Methodology, institutions for the disabled, psychiatries

The notion of excellence: Interviewing 'elite physicians'

Nils Hansson¹, Thorsten Halling¹

¹*Heinrich-Heine-University Düsseldorf, Germany*

During the last decades, much has been said about the methodological challenges and tactics of interviewing groups of 'elite physicians and scientists', e.g. with regard to witness seminars and video podcasts featuring renowned scholars, such as Nobel laureates and leading members of international medical societies. On a university level, too, it exists a large number of online semi-structured interviews by historians with alumni and emeriti that seek to present and contextualize scientific (local) highlights in medicine. Such material is often presented on university websites as a complement to lists of 'milestones' in medical faculties. Reflecting on the publications and questionnaires of recent oral history projects on excellence in medicine, this talk will, first, give an overview of current such initiatives with a prime focus on universities in northern Europe. It draws from an ongoing study by the EAHMH network "Medicine in the Baltic Sea region" that examines how authority and prestige play out in an institutional sphere. Second, we will outline a new interview project that circles around the experiences of active and retired employees at the University Hospital in Duesseldorf, Germany, and raise questions about how the reputation of scholars is enacted in such settings. Finally, we will propose to launch a platform with European colleagues around the topic.

Keywords: reputation, authority, prizes, public understanding of science, universities

Session 1B: Medical Care and Catholicism in France (1930s-1960s)

Timing: Wednesday, 08/Sept/2021, 9:00am - 10:15am

Chair: Florent Serina, University of Strasbourg, France

This panel aims to shed new light on the various interrelationships between health care practices and the Catholic faith in France, over a period extending from the inter-war years to the 1960s. Our objective is to study the beliefs, ideas and the practices of different personalities—physicians, psychiatrists, and members of the clergy—, by questioning their ways of associating health care and religious dogma, in contexts marked by multiple tensions and fault lines (sacred-profane, professional-amateur, orthodoxy-heterodoxy). To do so, our papers will draw on a wide range of unpublished archives, including personal papers, networks of correspondence, as well as medical records.

Keywords: Medical practices, Amateurism, Heterodoxy, France, 20th century.

The rise of a new popular practice. Dowsing priests in 1930s France

Hervé Guillemain

University of Le Mans – TEMOS CNRS 9016

In the 1930s medical dowsing appears in media. It inherits the tradition of ancient dowsers but is built as a new discipline of care which will become very popular in France after Second World War. Catholic priests, such as Abbé Bouly (in the North of France), are at the origin of this practice connected to new discoveries like radio waves. How historians could study that kind of medical practice carried by amateurs and remaining on the fringes of the academic field? The aim of this paper is to answer this historical question. To do so, it will rely on the personal archives of the Abbé Bouly, founder of medical dowsing, and on the study of the bulletin of the French Dowsers' Association created in the 1930s. After having evoked the scientific context which influences this emergence, I will describe the rudiments of the practice and the objects it produces, then I will analyse the setting up of a new national network which supports it before concluding on the historiographical scope of such an example for the history of health and for the history of Catholicism.

Catholic physicians in France during the interwar period: allies or enemies for spreading of esoteric influences within the medical culture?

Léo Bernard

Ecole Pratique des Hautes Etudes, Université PSL, LEM, UMR 8485

This paper aims to extend some reflections that the author's doctoral thesis has helped to bring to light. Focused on the relations between esoteric currents and medical holism during the interwar period, the thesis notably highlighted the fact that the porosity of borders between scholarly rationality and religious rationality tends to favour the porosity of borders between medical orthodoxy and medical heterodoxies. More precisely, catholic physicians helped alternative medicines such as homeopathy to be better considered within academic medical circles. As shown-up in the thesis, these alternative medicines were deeply influenced by esoteric currents, but such influence was not

uncontroversial, particularly among homeopathic physicians. On one hand, catholic physicians led the criticism against so-called occult influences, while, on the other hand, they also allowed practices such as chiology, closely tied-up with esoteric currents, to be quite widely disseminated within medical circles at that time. To illustrate this paradox, this paper will focus on different medical personalities which exemplify the variety of such ambiguities: the cases of Drs Maurice Fortier-Bernoville (1896-1939), Pierre Delore (1896-1960) and Paul Carton (1875-1947) will each give us a different insight on the complex relations between Catholicism, esotericism, and medicine.

Treating the psychic disorders of the clergy. Théophile Kammerer, a Catholic psychiatrist at work (1940s-1960s)

Florent Serina

*University of Strasbourg – SAGE CNRS 7363 and Institut des Humanités en Médecine – CHUV
Lausanne*

In 1953, Théophile Kammerer (1916-2005) became head of the University Psychiatric Clinic of Strasbourg, a central institution for the care of patients in Northeastern France. This neuropsychiatrist trained in psychoanalysis, whose personality has marked Alsatian memories, was particularly attached to his Catholic faith throughout his life. It is on this little-known, if not ignored, aspect of this major figure in French provincial psychiatry that I will focus, with a particular interest in the way his religious convictions influenced his medical practice. To this end, I will first present an unpublished study by Kammerer, transmitted by letter to the physician, psychoanalyst and Catholic priest Marc Oraison, entitled “Reflections on the psychic disorders observed in the clergy” (1956), in which he draws up an assessment of his clinical practice (private and public) on members of the Church and formulates a series of recommendations with a view to improving the recruitment of candidates for the seminary or novitiate. Secondly, I will look at how Kammerer was personally involved in the treatment of religious men or women (sisters, priests, abbots), admitted to the Strasbourg Clinic, through a systematic study of medical records over a period covering the first ten years of his tenure (1953-1962).

Session 1C: Catholic Discourses on Reproductive Health in State-Socialist Poland, 1960s-1990s

Timing: Wednesday, 08/Sept/2021, 9:00am - 10:15am

Chair: Kateřina Lišková, University of Granada, Spain

In state-socialist Poland, where the majority of population was baptised Catholic, the Catholic Church was an important actor in the reproductive health arena. Papers in this session underscore diversities in Polish Catholic discourses and practices linked to reproductive health between the 1950s and the 1990s. Through the case studies of the representations of infertility, premarital sex and broader ideas linked to reproductive health in Catholic magazines and popular literature, the authors analyse the relationships – and mutual exchanges - between medical and religion-based expertise around core areas of biopolitical intervention for the socialist state and the Catholic Church.

Keywords: reproductive health, Roman Catholicism, state-socialist Poland, infertility, sexuality

Debating premarital sex in Catholic and state-socialist Poland

Agata Ignaciuk¹, Natalia Jarska²

¹*University of Granada, Spain*, ²*Tadeusz Manteuffel Institute of History, Polish Academy of Sciences, Poland*

This paper examines the discourses surrounding youth sexuality in state-socialist and Catholic Poland, particularly the ideas surrounding “virginity”. Secular advice literature and sexological writings published between the late 1950s and the end of Polish communism in 1989 presented ambiguous and non-homogeneous discourses on premarital sex. The “culture of sexuality” promoted by experts tended to be limited to marital relationships: explicit advice on sex was largely directed at married couples or in the framework of “preparation for marriage”. While secular experts did not brand premarital sex as immoral, throughout the 1960s, 1970s and 1980s, they provided a range of medical and social arguments against the practice, at times based on gender hierarchies. Analogically, throughout the state-socialist period, both popular books aimed at the Catholic public and available in libraries, and unpublished scripts for the clergy and lay Catholics delivering “preparation for marriage” training at various levels, welded sex with marriage and forbade premarital sexual activity. The anticipated negative consequences of premarital sex were, again, steadfastly gendered: girls and women would suffer most as they were not only deemed responsible for controlling male sexual urges and advances, but also sexual violence. We concluded that overlaps and mutual borrowings existed in Catholic and secular approaches to premarital sexuality. While secular experts were unlikely to conceptualize premarital sex as a sin, they often mirrored Catholic views by framing the discourse in love, sex, responsibility and social danger.

Faith and lack of offspring: infertility in the Catholic press in Poland (1956-1989)

Natalia Pomian

University of Warsaw, Poland

With the end of the Stalinist era, the traditionally defined family and the Catholic vision of marriage regained prominence in Poland. Catholic premarital education, institutionalised in Poland from the late 1960s onward, prepared future spouses to parenthood. But what happened with the couples who had difficulties to conceive? In 1980s, a reported 10% of marriages were struggling with fertility problems, and in mid-1980s 3,4% of couples married for 10 or more years remained childless. Even though the Catechism of the Catholic Church highlights that childless couples can be fruitful through love, openness to others and sacrifice, the social and political pressure to have children in Poland remained enormous. This paper analyses the debates about infertility and childlessness in Poland through the pages of "Tygodnik Powszechny" - a Catholic weekly magazine focusing on social and cultural issues. I am particularly interested in underscoring the proposed solutions to the problem of infertility/childlessness, such as adoption and medical treatment of infertility (including insemination and in vitro fertilization), and the hierarchies established between these solutions. As sociological research showed, only 16% of infertile women were considering adoption, the rest chose long-term treatment or, as a last resort, 8% would choose artificial insemination. Looking at early discussion on infertility in a popular Catholic medium enables the understanding of the controversies attached to the contemporary Catholic approach to this problem and the social context of creating methods of therapy that suits Catholic ethics (e.g. naprotechnology).

Fair, natural, and reasonable. Sexuality and reproduction in the discourse of a religious organisation of Polish migrants in France

Agnieszka Kosiorowska

University of Warsaw, Poland

"A child in a marriage is its most honourable goal, and the decisions regarding having offspring are up to the parents. The Church only wants these decisions to be fair, in accordance with the laws of Nature, and reasonable" (1980). These words come from a 1980 issue of a newspaper published under the patronage of the Polish Catholic Mission (PCM) in France. The PCMs exist in twenty-eight different countries of the world, and exercise pastoral care over Polish migrants living in those countries. They play an important role in the lives of migrant communities, helping migrants with practical problems of everyday life and serving to sustain community bonds and cultural identity. This paper focuses on ways in which the PCM in France attempted to shape gendered health practices of migrants, in particular those related to reproductive health. I focus on the 1980s and 1990s, a time when the PCM in France assisted a large inflow of Polish economic migrants who left Poland due to the economic crisis during the last decade of state socialism. I analyse the PCM's newspaper "Głos Katolicki" (1980-1999) and focus on specific advice concerning reproductive health and sexuality, and behaviours and practices constructed as (un)healthy for men and for women. My hypothesis is that Polish Catholic Mission in France tried to manage and influence migrants' sexual and reproductive practices, considering that Polish people's practices in this matter should be different to those thought to be a norm in the French society.

Session 1D: Illness, Gift or Punishment? Medical Examinations of Religious Corporeal Practices in the Habsburg Monarchy, 1830-1870

Timing: Wednesday, 08/Sept/2021, 9:00am - 10:15am

Chair: Tine Van Osselaer, University of Antwerp, Belgium

In the nineteenth century, the Habsburg monarchy and especially 'Holy Land' Tyrol brimmed with religious fervour. The faithful channelled and expressed their religious enthusiasm into prayers, devotional practices and, on some occasions, corporeal religious practices (such as fasting or flagellation). The bodily aspect not seldom gave cause for concern. Whether deemed unhealthy, believed to be supernatural (in duration or form) or rejected as fraudulent, these corporeal practises inspired debates and called for medical examinations. This panel addresses these medical examinations and their outcomes, explores the reasons for organizing them and examines their impact on the reported cases.

Keywords: corporeal religious practices, medical examinations, Habsburg monarchy, nineteenth century

Undiagnosed disease or supernatural signs? Inedia, stigmata, and medical reports in the Early Nineteenth-century South Tyrol. The cases of Maria Von Mörl and Maria Domenica Lazzeri

Leonardo Rossi

University of Antwerp, Belgium

New attention has recently been given to medical examinations of supernatural phenomena and religious practices. These studies showed how medical reports are milestones in establishing natural or supernatural explanations for mystical phenomena in the nineteenth century, especially when they diagnosed hysteria (Mazzoni, 1996; Pires Marques, 2010). Medical analyzes had a wider circulation than the scientific field, influencing the public debate. Civil and ecclesiastical authorities, faithful and non-Catholic thinkers used and (re)interpreted them according to contexts and purposes (Van Osselaer and Smeyers, 2020). But what happens when medical expertise did not formulate a 'verdict', that is it did not diagnose pathology or exclude natural causes? Did this have the same influence?

In the first half of the 19th century, several mystical phenomena were reported in South Tyrol (Gadaleta, 2012 and 2014). Inedia, religious ecstasies, stigmata were claimed by dozens (even hundreds; Rubatscher, 1936) young women including Maria Von Mörl (1812-1868; Priesching, 2004) and Maria Domenica Lazzeri (1815-1848; Marinolli, 1998). In their cases, physicians could not reach a specific diagnosis, much less provide a cure. In my contribution, I will explain how, despite the non-'verdict', these reports played a crucial role in spreading the mystics' fame. They were read and used by clergymen (who collaborated closely with doctors), cited by international scholars, debated by local people (Brunelli, 1968). The reports without a diagnosis were not seen as a failure of medical expertise, but left the field open to interpretations (both medical and spiritual) by turning 'common' patients into exceptional case-studies and local saints.

“This iron penitential belt could be taken from him only with trickery” Psychiatrists about painful religious practices – the case of Tyrol, 1830–1870

Maria Heidegger

University of Innsbruck, Austria

In 1846, during the initial examination of 25-year-old Franz Anton K. the asylum physicians at Hall in Tyrol found his hip loosely wrapped with a belt made of iron wire and tin sheets with sieve-like perforations. The rough side of the metal sheets was turned inward and had caused a superficial rash on the skin. This iron belt could be taken from him only with cunning. When he was asked if anyone had advised or ordered him to wear the said belt, he replied that he had freely imposed this penitential exercise on himself and had put on the belt for the love of St. Peter.

How did psychiatrists perceive the religious dimension of corporeality in their concrete encounter with Catholic patients who hoped for a way to heaven by self-punishment? This question stands at the centre of my contribution, which is based on the files of 19th century Tyrolean psychiatry. I will examine case studies of patients who inflicted pain on themselves on religious grounds in a broad spectrum ranging from painful exercises associated with the "sinful" body to auto-aggressive acts such as self-mutilation in religious delusion. My paper will reflect on some methodological problems related to the material and question how/if medical discourses on painful corporeal practices strengthened medical authority in a period characterized by an intensified religiosity, an inwardly directed piety and the revival of medieval mysticism of suffering.

“On Friday, the patient expressed a great desire for meat.” Medical observations of extraordinary religious phenomena in Mid-Nineteenth-Century Vienna: the case of Juliana Weiskircher

Linde Tuybens

University of Antwerp, Belgium

In the late 1840s, curious crowds gathered in the streets of Schleinbach, a town near Vienna, to get a glimpse of Juliana Weiskircher, a young woman who relived Christ's Passion and displayed the stigmata on her body. Civil authorities, alarmed by this commotion and popular enthusiasm, appointed a medical commission to investigate the case, resulting in a forced admission of six months to the General Hospital of Vienna. In this paper, I'll discuss the double objective of this hospitalization: to provide proper care for the seriously ill and suffering woman, but also, as the main reason, to put her under close observation. From the outset, her admission seemed to be aimed at detecting and collecting evidence of deceit.

Juliana's stigmata, visions and religious ecstasies ceased during her time in the hospital, but her prolonged stay and constant monitoring gave the medical commission the opportunity to observe other corporeal phenomena that become extraordinary due to their length, such as paralysis of the limbs, inedia, and the ability to go without sleep. Whereas in this case, Juliana claimed her inability to eat and lack of sleep to be a burden, these symptoms contributed to the idea of a miraculous body as proof of the divine. I will show that by disproving, and even mocking these phenomena the commission tried to denounce the extraordinary nature of all events. In doing so, the commission also addresses Juliana's religiosity – or in this case a presumed lack of religiosity – to undermine her credibility.

Session 1E: Learned Medicine and Sacred Diseases

Timing: Wednesday, 08/Sept/2021, 9:00am - 10:15am

Rare Diseases in Mediaeval Europe

Marc M Dooms

UZ Leuven, Belgium

Monastic rules made an end to infanticide and child neglect in the Middle-Ages by caring for children with (rare) disorders: Disabled and impaired citizens became part of daily life. Historic, paleopathological, iconographic and genetic research revealed several cases of acromegaly, achondroplasia, alpha-1-antitrypsin deficiency, cystic fibrosis, Down syndrome, Dupuytren's contraction, goiter, Marfan syndrome, Paget's disease and phenylketonuria. These observations want to illustrate that diseases with a low prevalence are not recent observations but already existed for many centuries.

Through the ages diseases with a low prevalence have always occurred but physicians did not have the knowledge to prevent nor diagnose, the surgeons not the tools to operate and the pharmacists not the medication to treat patients with common diseases, let alone rare disorders [53]. Moreover during the Middle Ages these patients were accepted as part of everyday life with little desire to change their situation by various techniques or treatments and without wishing to exclude it either. Care (*caritas*) will slightly change into cure (*Θεραπείες*) over time.

Reference: Dooms M (2020) Rare Diseases in Mediaeval Europe. *Int J Rare Dis Disord* 3:016. doi.org/10.23937/2643-4571/1710016

Keywords: Paleopathology, Orphan drugs, Child oblation, Genetic epidemiology, Middle-ages

„A masterpiece of scientific sanity“. Modern receptions of the hippocratic treatise On Sacred Disease

Nadine Metzger

FAU Erlangen-Nürnberg, Germany

The hippocratic On Sacred Disease famously rejects a supernatural cause of epilepsy, leading to its praise as “a masterpiece of scientific sanity” (Naylor 1909). Until today, it is widely believed to be an outstanding example of Greek „rational“ medicine speaking out against superstitious explanation and treatment of disease; foundation to the inherently naturalistic, even scientific, cosmology of 2500 years of medicine to come; witness to the readily assumed struggle between religion and medicine as old as „our“ Western medicine. In this vein, On Sacred Disease has been used as a projection screen for modern demarcations between medicine and religion.

However, On Sacred Disease only rose to fame after the advent of scientific medicine. For most of its reception history, the treatise has not elicited much scholarly interest, being branded a third-class polemic unworthy of Hippocratic medicine. Only around 1900 did it begin to evoke more than cursory study. Some decades later, at least since the 1930s, the treatise was considered “truly Hippocratic” – either written by the master himself or embodying genuine Hippocratic ideas.

This paper wants to address the reception history of *On Sacred Disease* in relation to the interpretational framework provided by the rising *Deutungsmacht* of modern scientific medicine in society. By outlining the long-term development of the growing esteem of the treatise it shows that *On Sacred Disease* acquired Hippocratic authorship and scholarly esteem only in a certain intellectual climate deeply connected with the changing face of medicine and its socio-cultural embedment.

Keywords: Hippocratic medicine, ancient reception studies, 20th c. hippocratism, The Hippocratic Question, epilepsy

Bibliographical rituals: the Medical book as an object of trust. The case of 17th-18th cent. Portugal

Hervé Baudry

Universidade Nova de Lisboa, Portugal

This paper fits into the framework of the early modern history of book and science in Portugal. A systematic study of the national print production is now possible due to the full bibliographical survey of both centuries, completed in 2020 (with, respectively, 99 and 576 items). Beyond the prints that refer to the usual mixture of religious and scientific contents, this work sheds light on an abundant paratextual dimension, in particular the numerous dedications to religious entities. On the other side, the medical book was straightly controlled by the Inquisition in charge, since the middle of the 16th century, of the updating and enforcement of the indexes of prohibition and expurgation (at least until 1768). Not surprisingly, many physicians were members ("familiar") of the Inquisition. This double approach leads to analyse the medical book not only in its dimension of object of faith, but also its orthodoxy, efficacy and power.

Keywords: Book, Portugal, 17th-18th centuries, Dedictees, Inquisition

Session 2A: Managing Melancholy: Dynamics of Medicine and Religion in the Eighteenth Century

Timing: Wednesday, 08/Sept/2021, 10:45am - 12:00pm

Chair: Catherine Beck, University of Plymouth, United Kingdom

This panel explores the entanglement of medicine and religion in psychiatric and lay understandings of mental difference and distress. Each paper approaches melancholy in the different confessional contexts of eighteenth-century Denmark and Britain from the respective angles of theology, forensic psychiatry and social history. Considering the (self-)management and identification of melancholy in the context of Pietistic introspection in Lutheran Denmark in contrast to the varied religious practice of sailors within the highly medicalised space of the eighteenth-century naval ship, the papers interrogate the role of secularization in the evolution of melancholy as a psychopathology and legal impaired mental state.

Keywords: Psychiatry, Insanity, Religion, Legal, Maritime

On the road to salvation or sickness? Introspection and theological diagnostics regarding melancholy

Tine Reeh

University of Copenhagen, Denmark

The phenomenon of melancholy was considered of an ambiguous character in Pietistic thought. On the one hand, melancholy could be considered a state on the way to conversion or rebirth and, hence, have a constructive potential. Yet, dwelling or staying in a melancholic state could be considered not only sinful but extremely dangerous and deadly. The Pietists' occupation with the (constructive) use of melancholy gave rise to criticism by proponents of the Enlightenment, and research has pointed to a connection between melancholy diagnosis and criticism of religion in the second half of the 18th century. At the same time, one could say that the pietists occupation with melancholy paved the way for empirical studies of the self in order to diagnose the sound as well as impaired mental states.

One of the tools to diagnose the inner person was self-observation, self-examination or introspection. It occurred in Puritan traditions and became a common element in Hallensian Pietism. Using some of the popular and wide spread pamphlets from Denmark-Norway, this paper outlines signs and symptoms used to identify the constructive religious melancholy, and what warning signs and complaints could point to an unsound and perilous condition. It then examines some of the tangible consequences of this classification in how The Faculty of Copenhagen used them to assess criminals when the absolutistic kings of Denmark-Norway requested assistance in their final decisions regarding critical cases involving melancholy.

“Melancholic Murder” in Copenhagen – on forensic psychiatry in statu nascendi

Ralf Hemmingsen

University of Copenhagen, Denmark

Before the 18th century, legal practice in Denmark-Norway limited its conception of disordered mental states to only externalized, aggressive or antisocial behaviors such as madness, fury, or mania (e.g. Danish Code 6-6-17). However, in 1765 the King mitigated death penalty to imprisonment for life of a melancholic woman, who declared to be weary of her life and therefore killed a two-year old girl to lose it. In 1767, a decree on “melancholic murderers” decisively acknowledged attention to melancholic states in the legal process, although not an insanity defense but rather as a factor when securing a functional and just punishment.

So-called "melancholic murders", also labelled suicide murders, suicide by proxy or judicial suicide, have raised debate in research regarding the connection between religious ideas and reactions of distress on different levels. The court records reflect officials' attempts to establish facts as well as the murderers' intention, premeditation, sanity and motive.

Based on data from an in-depth study of 64 cases of murder in Copenhagen during the period 1697-1777, this paper explores religious and mental components at the individual case level.

What was the pre-medical nomenclature, used by the perpetrator, the witness statements and the judicial experts? How did it develop, and can we identify a plausible relation to contemporary pietist vocabulary? Can the material on melancholic murder in Copenhagen elucidate interactions between religious perceptions and forensic psychiatry in statu nascendi?

Contagious Melancholy, Cheerfulness and (Ir)religiosity: responses to mental difference and distress at sea

Catherine Beck

University of Plymouth, United Kingdom

The depressing action of the sea occupied the attention of many ships' surgeons in the eighteenth century. The fatigues of sea-service, rigid discipline, and the boredom posed by the unvaried prospect of the sea itself, all seemed to make sailors peculiarly vulnerable to 'dejection of spirits'. Within the 'gloomy walls' of the ship, melancholy also appeared to be 'contagious' and could take hold of a crew just as readily as the scurvy and typhus it so frequently seemed to usher in. Surgeons recommended the careful maintenance of 'cheerfulness' as a valuable prophylactic measure on a level with cleanliness and ventilation. Conversely, religious provision was perceived as important on board ship, but for maintaining order, rather than providing spiritual care to those suffering from low spirits and melancholy. Sailors were often thought of as 'unthinking' and lacking in the refined feeling required for introspection. By reputation, they ranged from naïve, superstitious and god-fearing, to irreverent, hard-hearted, 'sabbath breakers'. Consequently, many officers and surgeons regarded religious intervention in the mental health of a ship as detrimental. However, sailors seemed to have treated the administrations of the ship's chaplain similar to those of the ship's surgeon: as high-handed, formal and something sought only when self-treatment failed. This paper investigates the range of approaches sailors employed in their self-management of melancholy and low spirits, which blended medical intervention with emotional tools and understandings including the use of religious practice to self-sooth.

Session 2B: Global Hospital Networks

Timing: Wednesday, 08/Sept/2021, 10:45am - 12:00pm

Chair: Prof. Jonathan Reinarz, University of Birmingham, United Kingdom

Modernizing traditional Ottoman healthcare institutions during the 19th century: The cases of Balikli Greek Hospital of Istanbul and the Communal Christian Hospital of Heraklion*

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During the 19th century, radical reforms took place in the Ottoman Empire. The ottoman state initiated an ambitious modernizing program that challenged pre-modern economic and administrative policies, old social hierarchies and institutions, established religious, cultural and scientific beliefs and practices.

Healthcare sector was heavily influenced by these reforms. The traditional ottoman medical paradigm, during the 19th century, was gradually replaced by a modern one. Modern sanitation practices appeared, new healthcare institutions were established, public health laws passed and medical schools and hospitals begun to function. At an ideological level, the concepts of health, sickness, philanthropy and pauperism took a new form.

The focal point of this paper will be two hospitals during the 19th century that belonged to Christian Orthodox communities. The first one is the Balikli Greek Hospital, located in the ottoman capital and the other one is the Communal Christian Hospital of Kandiye (modern day Heraklion, Greece) in the ottoman province of Crete Island. By examining these two hospitals, this paper will try to answer questions like: How was the transition from a traditional, eleemosynary type to a modern, state-backing hospital made? When did these hospitals lose their asylum approach to healthcare in favor of scientific, medical-oriented practices? How was the religious character of these hospitals replaced by a secular type? Did the ascending Christian bourgeoisie manage to undertake the control of the hospital's administration over the clergy? And if so, how did this affect the services of the hospital? Finally, did the medicalization of healthcare prevailed?

Keywords: Ottoman Empire, hospitals, healthcare institution, history of health, Crete

Writing the 'Aga Khan Hospitals' into the History of Healthcare Architecture in the Twentieth Century

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Global histories of health in the twentieth century on the one hand and histories of architecture on the other have, for some time, questioned a model of ideas moving from the metropolitan core to the

* This paper is competing in the Pieter van Foreest Student Prize.

periphery, highlighting instead the multi-directional nature of knowledge transfer and the cooperation within the Global South. These studies have not yet been extended to include healthcare architecture. As a result, the pavilion plan/ hospital-as-officer-tower/ hospital-as-shopping-mall histories of healthcare architecture (Adams, 2016, 2008; Kisacky, 2017; Willis, Goad, and Logan, 2018) have remained unchallenged and continue to drive a linear narrative that sees the 'modern' hospital as a product of the 'West' that was exported to, or imposed upon, the rest of the world. This paper aims to challenge this linear narrative through a focus on the 'Aga Khan hospitals', a network of international hospitals based in Dar es Salaam, Mumbai, Kisumu, Mombasa, Nairobi, and Pakistan (Regarding Aga Khan development network, see Karim, 2014). It will provide some background information about these hospitals; after which, it will draw on works by Sunil Amrith (2006, 2014), Abigail Green (2017), and Lukasz Stanek (2020), among others, to present some initial thoughts concerning the role of the Aga Khan Development Network and the transnational Shai Ismaili Muslim Community in the 'internationalisation' or otherwise of healthcare architectural forms in the twentieth century.

Keywords: Aga Khan Hospitals, Global history, Healthcare Architecture, Twentieth Century

Hospital Networks around the Bay of Bengal: Institutions in a Time of Crisis

Francesco Bianchini¹, Michael Willis¹, Daniela De Simone¹, Dolors Rodriguez Roig²

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The medical traditions of South Asia rest on ancient texts, notably Suśruta's and Caraka's Compendia. These cover diseases, assorted disorders, instruments, surgical practices and theories of the body. Concurrently, extracts from the Buddhist canon were recited for prophylactic and therapeutic purposes. A substantial corpus of texts, known as dhāraṇī, was also composed to provide protection and control diseases if recited, copied and worn as talismans. Specific genres emerged to deal with special problems, the Garuḍa Tantra, for example, covering snake bite and poisoning.

None of these literatures describes in detail the institutions that were developed to deliver medical knowledge and treat patients. The history of these institutions—known as ārogyaśālā or hospitals—is known primarily from inscriptions and sites where such inscriptions were found. The history of these hospitals is in its infancy. Accordingly, we have formed a team to collect a wide range of epigraphic texts for analysis and comparison. The results, along with many other inscriptions, can be seen on www.siddham.network.

The paper proposed for EAHHM 2021 will present our work to date, and highlight some examples of hospitals and the finds associated with them. The inscriptions and finds give insight into healing practices and the nature of the hospitals supported by the state and the Buddhist 'Church'. What emerges from the evidence is a burgeoning of hospitals in the late medieval, a time of severe climate disruption that precipitated the collapse in the 1200s of both the Khmer empire (Cambodia) and the kingdom of Polonnaruwa (Sri Lanka).

Keywords: Hospitals, Medieval, Epigraphy, Cambodia, Sri Lanka

Session 2C: Faith and the National Health Service

Timing: Wednesday, 08/Sept/2021, 10:45am - 12:00pm

Chair: Dr. Rosemary Cresswell, University of Warwick, United Kingdom

Chapel Appeal: Maintaining space for Christian fellowship in the new National Health Service

Robert Piggott

University of Huddersfield, United Kingdom

For much of the twentieth century, England's hospital chapels offered a space to celebrate Christian fellowship amongst medical staff, and a place of worship and solace for others. The Second World War had negatively affected hospital chapels either leading to bomb damage or extra space being needed for emergency medical care. Although Nye Bevan, Minister of Health, had made a pledge to the Church of England's Church Assembly in May of 1948 that chapel space would be provided in new National Health Service foundations, chapel appeals in various places over the next decade hurried the process along. These appeals maintained the traditional links between religious congregations and the hospitals which had seemingly been challenged by nationalisation in 1948. Through friends groups and chapel appeals, volunteers, congregations and medical practitioners came together to maintain a space for Christian fellowship in the hospital. The resulting chapels were used to mark the Christian calendar and for special services for staff, often as part of nurses' reunion services. Medical personnel and friends groups showed their religious devotion by furnishing the chapels, often providing such items as organs, cushions, and stained glass windows. This paper examines this history, focusing on the role of the chapel in Christian fellowship amongst staff inside the hospital and links with religious congregations outside of it.

Keywords: National Health Service, Worship, Christian Fellowship, Voluntarism, Material Culture

The Place of Charity Within a Tax-Funded Hospital System: the British NHS Since 1948

Martin Gorsky

LSHTM, United Kingdom

Funding from philanthropy has been a feature of hospital provision throughout history and across different national traditions. However, its position under the British National Health Service (NHS) presents an unusual case. When the NHS was founded in 1948 it aimed specifically to leave charity behind, moving instead towards a secular system of tax-based public financing and ownership. The accumulated gifts and endowments held by the former voluntary hospitals were permitted to continue as trusts, but with uses now confined only to research and amenities for staff and patients. Current and capital expenditure on medical care would now come from the public purse. By 2020 though, charitable funding had not disappeared, but continued to grow, to the extent that it was providing some £500 million per annum, mostly in support of NHS capital projects. In this paper we ask why charity survived in a statist health system, and whether it aided or improved goals of efficiency and equity.

We begin by discussing some theoretical approaches to the role of the voluntary sector in social provision. We then outline the changing legal framework of British charity, exploring how changing political climates led to phases of liberalisation in the 1980s and 2010s. We examine case study examples of NHS hospitals in London, Glasgow and other locations to show how old endowments and new charity funds were managed and used. Did they advance community interests or particular institutional agendas which hampered equitable access and planning?

Keywords: Charity, National Health Service, Britain

'We regard doctors as gods, but I have lost all faith in the medical profession': The emergence of 'patient safety' in the NHS, c.1990–2020

Christopher Sirrs

University of Warwick, United Kingdom

At least rhetorically, 'patient safety' is at the heart of medicine. The need for doctors to protect the safety of patients is embodied in the Hippocratic dictum 'do no harm', in professional ethics, and attempts by healthcare practitioners to reduce the risks of interventions. It may seem surprising, therefore, that a focus on 'patient safety' as an explicit goal of healthcare policy and the regulation and management of healthcare systems is a very recent development, emerging only since 1999 in health systems worldwide. Only in the last twenty years has 'patient safety' also crystallised as a discipline, with a discrete set of theories, tools and approaches to preventing, reducing and ameliorating patient harm.

This paper seeks to specifically explain the emergence of 'patient safety' in the policy and management of the British NHS. The Department of Health report 'An Organisation with a Memory' in 2000 highlighted how 1 in 10 patients admitted to NHS hospitals encountered an 'adverse event', or physical or psychological injury caused by an event or omission during clinical care. This indicates the routine nature of adverse events within the clinical encounter in hospitals, a level of patient harm which the history of medicine has yet to fully comprehend. The paper highlights not only developments in the scientific understanding of 'adverse events' which promoted a focus on 'patient safety' in the NHS, but significant cultural shifts around medical practice and professional regulation, people's trust in doctors, medical negligence litigation and the publicity surrounding healthcare scandals.

Keywords: patient safety, NHS, risk, medical errors, professional cultures

Session 2D: Faith and Mental Illness in the Nineteenth Century

Timing: Wednesday, 08/Sept/2021, 10:45am - 12:00pm

Chair: Prof. Herve Guillemain, University of Le Mans, France

Between Faith and Mental Illness: the Lazzaretti Case in Post-Unification Italy

Emilia Musumeci

University of Teramo, Italy

The aim of this paper is to retrace a peculiar case of religion and mental pathologies occurred in the complex context of the decades after Italian Risorgimento and the Italian unification (1861). In particular, it will be analysed the case of David Lazzaretti a poor carter from Tuscany, self-proclaimed “Christ, Duce, Judge” and “the Second Son of God come to earth”, considered a heretic and excommunicated from the Catholic Church due his blasphemous writing. He founded the “Giurisdavidic Church” based on a sort of mystical and utopian socialism (his motto was: “The Republic is the kingdom of God”). His figure has given rise to lively controversy between those who considered him a martyr and who reputed him a mad visionary or, more prosaically a charlatan. In any case, Lazzaretti’s movements are emphasized above all for his tragic end: on the morning of August 18, 1878, while he was driving a peaceful procession from Monte Labbro to Arcidosso, a little town in Tuscany, he was killed by Italian carabinieri who opened fire on the helpless population during the religious ceremony. After his death, medical science and in particular positivist psychiatry, also called “alienists”, described Lazzaretti not as a sacrilegious impostor but as a mentally ill person, who would have benefitted more from treatment than prosecution. In particular, under the aegis of Lombroso, the Positivist School of Criminology helped stigmatise religious deviant behaviour that manifested itself in alternative forms of spirituality, which in post-unification Italy were especially widespread on the countryside.

Keywords: David Lazzaretti, Cesare Lombroso, Italy, Religion and Mental Health, Positivist Psychiatry.

‘God the Great Physician’: Religious Activities in Nineteenth-Century British Asylums

Ute Oswald

University of Warwick, United Kingdom

Our perception of the nineteenth-century asylum has largely been shaped by images of shackles, leeches and padded cells. Yet this obfuscates a very different side of these institutions; proponents of the then pioneering ‘moral treatment’ put a particular emphasis on kindness, location and occupation. Alongside traditional employment and recreation, the provision of religious services garnered increasing importance and support with a view to effecting a lasting cure or, if this was not possible, at least some level of amelioration and self-control.

This paper aims to interrogate the largely unexplored -and purportedly contradictory- relationship between religion and mental science in Scottish and English asylums, as diagnoses of religious insanity seemed at odds with the healing powers ascribed to religious activities and beliefs. It will show how different aspects such as sermons, bible-practice and hymns were adapted to suit an asylum population of varied religious persuasions and mental afflictions, taking into consideration the rise of

evangelicalism and its implications inside and outside the asylum walls. It will further explore the role of the chaplain, highlighting his influence on the patient body and discussing his position alongside the medical superintendent. A wide range of primary sources such as treatises, annual reports and articles in the popular and scientific nineteenth-century press will reveal the complexities of these relationships and the extent to which religion was understood as a therapeutic as well as a management tool, despite an arguably increasing secularisation outside the institutional walls.

Keywords: asylum, religious activities, chaplain, physician, insanity

‘A few months in the solitary cell renders a prisoner strangely impressive’: Prison chaplains, the separate system and mental breakdown in English and Irish prisons, 1842-1860

Hilary Marland¹, Catherine Cox²

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As the separate system was introduced to English and Irish prisons in the mid-nineteenth century, prison chaplains played a key role in supporting and implementing a system of extreme solitary, cellular confinement. They claimed an expertise above and beyond that of prison medical officers in understanding the minds of prisoners, and asserted their ability to improve the mental status of prisoners and to produce deep-seated reform and redemption, largely through cell visitations. Such cellular encounters, intended to extract confessional statements from the prisoners, enacted an early, somewhat sinister, form of ‘psychoanalysis’, producing self-reflection and repudiation of sin, as prisoners shared ‘their deepest anxiety and guilt in their isolated cells’. The optimism of the chaplains and their vigorous support of the separate system, however, would soon be challenged, as prisons adopting the discipline witnessed an increased incidence of mental breakdown among prisoners, marked by delusions and hallucinations, extreme excitement, irritability, depression, anxiety, and religious mania provoked by over-zealous brethren. At some Dublin prisons, it was alleged that ‘fanatical’ evangelical chaplains exploited these encounters to ‘unsettle the belief of a Catholic Prisoner’ and coerce mentally fragile inmates to convert. Drawing on English and Irish prison archives, official reports, and the publications of the prison chaplains, this paper will explore the chaplains’ enthusiastic pursuit of prisoners’ reformation and mental improvement. It will also examine the increasing self-doubt of Reverend Kingsmill at Pentonville about the ability of cellular confinement to produce mental improvement and his acknowledgement that the system itself might trigger mental breakdown.

Keywords: Prisons, chaplains, separate confinement, mental breakdown, proselytism

Session 2E: Twentieth Century Missionary Health Care

Timing: Wednesday, 08/Sept/2021, 10:45am - 12:00pm

Chair: Prof. Frank Huisman, UMC Utrecht, the Netherlands

On Kimbanguist 'plagues': Catholic missionaries' medical-humanitarian conceptions and the 'church-state alliance' in interwar colonial Congo

Eva Renate M Schalbroeck

Utrecht University, the Netherlands

In 1921, the 'Black Prophet', Simon Kimbangu, began to heal people in the Belgian Congo. Followers destroyed traditional healing fetiches and spoke of 'Blacks becoming Whites'. The Catholic Church and the colonial state condemned and repressed this 'plague'. This is generally seen as a straightforward example of the 'church-state alliance', based on a clear division between the political and the religious.

This paper questions this by examining Catholic missionaries' medical-humanitarian arguments regarding Kimbanguism when interacting with administrators or commenting on state policy and interventions. It focuses on which aspects of health care, Kimbanguism, and 'native welfare' they considered political and religious, which responsibilities they ascribed to the state and which to missionaries. This is connected to missionaries' conceptions of African society, sense of identity, practice, and divisions between the body and the soul, the emotional and the rational. This paper posits Kimbanguism and health care as a domain in which missionaries reflected on where the boundary between the political and the religious was and examines how they used medical-humanitarian language to shift it.

This paper argues for seeing medical metaphors as more than just 'tools' to discredit Kimbanguism. Doing so, it does not uncover minor conflicts, exceptions 'proving' the 'rule' of the 'church-state alliance'. Rather, pointing to the role of medical-humanitarian language in shaping interactions between missionaries and state representatives, it argues for an essentially malleable relationship. More generally, it cautions against merely refining 'big notions' such as secularisation. It calls for creating more dynamic case study based analytical frameworks.

Keywords: Kimbanguism, colonialism, Congo, church, state

European Christian Medical Missions in Decolonization

Walter Bruchhausen

Global Health, University of Bonn, Germany

Whereas the role of Christian medical missions in the preparation, establishment and stabilization of colonial rule has been researched extensively much less is known on their roles and attitudes during the decolonization of Africa and Asia in the 1950s and 1960s.

The fate of Christian health facilities and staff in (former) colonies was highly diverse. Those from neutral states like Switzerland could largely continue without major interruptions, those with national ties to the colonial power often experienced difficulties. In some African countries, churches and

mission societies run the majority of hospitals whereas India tried to reduce foreign influence for different reasons. Some doctors and nurses returned to their home countries, others saw new opportunities and wanted to support the young states or found an escape from unemployment and other unsatisfactory circumstances in Europe. Some traditional Christian health issues like leprosy experienced a revival, others like mother and child health became domains of governments. Denominational differences partly determined decisions on nationalization, the beginnings of so-called European development aid broadened the financial basis of some major churches for health care activities.

Based on extensive work in Tanzanian, East and West German and British archives, with research literature on Swiss, German and British mission hospitals in Africa and Asia and on missionary publications the paper attempts an overview on the developments and gives some examples on medical missionaries' ambiguous attitudes towards changing health policies, national independence and European influence as well as advocacy for those who were regarded as less privileged in health.

Keywords: Medical missions, Christianity, Health Care, Decolonization, Mission hospitals

The Franciscan Missionaries of the Divine Motherhood and a system of Franciscan transnational healthcare: Ireland and Singapore, 1942-1970

Brian Casey

Durham University, United Kingdom

Reflecting upon her early life working in a home for unmarried mothers in Highbury, London, Sister Catherine Whelan fmdm recalled the challenges the community faced in offered a dignified existence to the women and children under their care. The dignity of all human life wherever they are present is central to the charism of the Franciscan Missionaries of the Divine Motherhood. Following her election as Congregational Leader, Mother Francis Spring set out to improve the physical surroundings of the healthcare system that the Congregation was building. She commenced with energetic fastidiousness and determination to construct a transnational network of healthcare where the Franciscan tradition remained centred.

Sisters were formed in this tradition and spirituality to ensure that they were robustly prepared and trained to work wherever their presence was needed. The desire to build hospitals to best international standards that also reflected modern Catholic medical ethics was at the core of the FMDM charism. This was manifested in the construction of nursing schools in both Ireland and Singapore to train sisters in such practice, as well as lay nurses and the centralisation of this training helped them to infuse their spirituality in all aspects of their medical work. This paper explores the efforts of the Franciscan Missionaries of the Divine Motherhood to establish a presence in Ireland and Singapore and their negotiations with government, local clergy, medical professions and communities to ensure best practice in all aspects of medical and spiritual well-being remained central.

Keywords: healthcare, Franciscanism, spirituality, transnationalism, gender

Lunch Session 1A: Roundtable

Timing: Wednesday, 08/Sept/2021, 12:00pm - 12:45pm

Chair: Kaat Wils, KU Leuven, Belgium

Digital methods in medical history. Reflections from a research project on religion and ideology in 19th-century medicine

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³*National Library of Belgium (KBR)*

The sprawl of digital heritage in combination with the proliferation of data-mining has extended the historian's toolkit considerably. Instead of forging narratives based on intimate knowledge of a limited amount of sources, historians nowadays often mine large collections to extract patterns. This panel discusses the challenges of the digitization of 19th-century medical journals and the use of digital techniques to study the role and development of medical concepts and ideas in the 19th century.

Medical journals played a pivotal role in 19th-century medicine. In these journals, professionals shared, discussed and developed ideas by writing meeting reports, academic articles and reviews. Because of the technical nature of the medical discussions in these journals and the sheer quantity of the published texts, it is difficult to get a grip on historically evolving medical concepts, ideas and arguments by means of familiar close reading methods. In order to overcome such difficulties, digital methods can be used to distillate relevant passages in a large corpus and to analyze the used terminology both within these passages in detail and across the entirety of the text corpus.

This roundtable is built around an interdisciplinary project IMPRESS (2017-2021) which involves researchers from the National Library of Belgium (KBR), the Université libre de Bruxelles (ULB) and KU Leuven. This project entails the digitization of three major Belgian medical journals, their online publication on the KBR Digital Library (<https://www.belgicaperiodicals.be/>) and the use of digital methods to study the role of religion and ideology in these journals. We focus on the methodological choices that were made and discuss the extent to which text mining has allowed us to identify and evaluate expressions of ideology in a corpus of scientific texts. In laying bare the difficulties and outcomes of both the digitization and the digital analysis, we intend to contribute to the current debate on the gains and limitations of digital methods in the humanities. While acknowledging the many interpretative interventions in preparing searches and qualifying outcomes, the use of the digital tools has allowed us to reach more sophisticated research results than the exclusive use of non-digital methods would have.

Keywords: Medical journals, digitization, digital analysis, religion, ideology

Lunch Session 1B: Roundtable

Timing: Wednesday, 08/Sept/2021, 12:00pm - 12:45pm

Chair: Luc De Munck, KU Leuven, Belgium

Religious Healing Practices in the History of Nursing

Sioban Nelson¹, Barbra Mann Wall², Christine Hallett³, Anna La Torre⁴

¹University of Toronto, Canada; ²University of Virginia, United States of America; ³University of Huddersfield, United Kingdom; ⁴University of Milan, Italy

In this panel, attention will be paid to religious healing practices in different countries over different periods of time, with a focus on the practices used in nursing.

Prof. Dr. Sioban NELSON is professor at the Faculty of Nursing of the University of Toronto (Canada). She is the author of *Say Little, Do Much. Nurses, Nuns and Hospitals in the Nineteenth Century* (University of Pennsylvania Press, 2001). At the roundtable she will discuss the idea of nursing knowledge with particular reference to two seventeenth century texts for nurses: the Conference of Vincent de Paul to the Daughters of Charity (France) and *Instrucciones de Enfermeros to the Brothers of the Congregation of Bernadino de Obregon* (Spain).

Prof. Dr. Barbra Mann WALL is professor at the University of Virginia School of Nursing (USA). She published three books on the intersection of religion, hospital establishments and nursing after 1865, including her acclaimed *Unlikely Entrepreneurs. Catholic Sisters and the Hospital Marketplace 1865-1925* (Ohio State University Press, 2005). As in her book, in the roundtable she shall elaborate on the religious and nursing practices of nuns between 1865 and 1925.

Prof. Dr. Christine HALLETT is professor at the University of Huddersfield (UK). Much of her work focusses on the history of nursing practices. Her most recent books include *Edith Cavell and her Legend* (Palgrave, 2018), *Nurses of Passchendaele* (Pen & Sword, 2017), *Nurse Writers of the Great War* (Manchester University Press, 2016) and *Veiled Warriors* (Oxford University Press, 2014). At the roundtable, she shall focus on the spirituality of British nurses serving on the Eastern front during the First World War.

Anna LA TORRE earned an MS in Nursing (2008) and an MA in History (2015), with a specialisation in Christianity history. Currently she is pursuing a PhD in History at the University of Barcelona (Spain). She is a teaching assistant at the University of Milan (Italy), focusing on nursing history. In 2020 she became the president of the European Association for the History of Nursing (EAHN). Her most recent publications are: "The RAF passed over Milan, the nurses' response to the 1940-45 bombings", "Grenade Syndrome and the Talking care. A care challenge during the First World War" and "Life at the Policlinic of Milan during the Spanish flu. A story of courses and recourses" (all published in 2020 in *Historica Medica*). At the roundtable, she shall look into the religious practices of Italian nurses in the 20th century.

Luc DE MUNCK shall moderate the session. He holds a master in History, and is currently pursuing a PhD in History at KU Leuven (Belgium), His PhD is about the professional identity of catholic nurses in Belgium between 1919 and 1974. In his research, he analyses the healing practices of religious nurses. He is the author of *Altijd troosten. Belgische verpleegsters tijdens de Eerste Wereldoorlog* [Always Comforting. Belgian Nurses during the First World War] (Amsterdam University Press, 2018).

Keywords: Religious practices, nursing, First World War, spirituality, professional identity

Session 3A: Bodies out of Control

Timing: Wednesday, 08/Sept/2021, 1:30pm - 2:45pm

Chair: Kristof Smeyers, University of Antwerp, Belgium

This panel is about unruly bodies in Europe from the Enlightenment to the Second World War, and about some of the twining forces that attempted to control them: supernatural, medical, historiographical. Undead, bewitched and possessed, these bodies acted seemingly independently from the minds of their owners. Each paper interrogates medical approaches to extraordinary bodies. We also examine how those forces impacted how people experienced their own bodies. Together, these papers historicise experiences of the body as well as medical attitudes to 'bodies out of control'.

Keywords: body, supernatural, vampirism, witchcraft, possession

To Believe or not to Believe? Medical and Religious Debates on the Undead in Enlightenment Europe

Timea Solyomvari

Newcastle University, United Kingdom

In Eastern Europe, vampirism was understood within a disease-based explanatory system in the context of epidemics for hundreds of years. In times of plague, cholera, or swine fever, with the agreement of the village, corpses were dug up and destroyed by means of specific rituals. During the eighteenth century, medical reports of these cases provoked a heated debate in the learned Protestant circles of Halle, Jena and Leipzig. Secular representatives of the Enlightenment persecuted superstition with equal fanaticism instead of ignoring it as inefficient practice. The body became a topic of discussion, raising questions such as: where is the line between life and death, the animate and the inanimate, and the normal and abnormal corpse?

This paper will assess the specific physiological dimension of the belief of the dead returning to life, and the relationship between a new belief that arose in the context of new medical knowledge and the budding Enlightenment in Central and Eastern Europe. The participants of the debate regarding vampires blamed the Orthodox clergy of inspiring superstitious fear into people's hearts about the rising dead. The central question will be what role religion played in the interpretation of belief in a physical rather than spiritual afterlife, especially from the point of view of the challenge of the Catholic doctrine of purgatory.

Itchcraft: Feeling Cursed in France, 1790-1940

Will Pooley

University of Bristol, United Kingdom

Did it feel different to be cursed in 1940 than it had in 1790?

Bodies are historical. Not simply at the level of representation, but in the very feelings and experiences of the flesh. Yet it has proven much easier to write the histories of elite experiences of the body than

those of the working population. This paper turns to a particularly ‘popular’ medical tradition – the fear and fascination of witchcraft – to ask: how did experiences of embodiment among the masses change in this period?

Since the 1990s, there has been a steady rise in interest in the histories of European witchcraft after the end of the witch trials. Historians now know that the decriminalization of witchcraft in different jurisdictions at different times in the seventeenth to nineteenth centuries did not put an end to disputes over witchcraft. After decriminalization, courts still heard cases of fraud, slander, assault, and murder connected to sorcery. Between 1790-1940 in France there were close to 1,000 cases of this type. Yet historians of witchcraft after the trials have done little to historicise witchcraft itself. This paper asks how being bewitched may have felt different in 1940 than it had in 1790. From flea infestations to ingested reptiles, it surveys the diversity of itchy, exhausted, nauseous, frozen, cramped, restless, burning, and paralyzed sensations that the bewitched described. And it charts the appearance of new cursed experiences, such as electrifying sensations and nervous complaints.

Bodies Besieged: Ethics of the Possessed in Interbellum Europe

Kristof Smeyers

University of Antwerp, Belgium

When the Devil enters a body, it sets in motion a series of invasive acts: curious and clinical eyes gaze; gloved hands touch; the priest exorcises; the needle pokes; the stethoscope listens; the generator whirs and zaps; the camera clicks; a public opinion, fed sensational(ised) snippets of information, judges – fraud, narcissism, insanity!

The bodies of the possessed have been under attack for centuries.

They have suffered from supernatural as well as natural forces, even from those that called the possessed ‘victims’ – whether of Satan’s malice or mental struggle – and tried to heal them. This paper hones in on the nature of medical invasions of possessed bodies in interbellum Europe to ask what the ethical implications were: on those medical disciplines that engaged with possession, and on their bodily subjects. Methods of prodding and probing possessed bodies increasingly provoked criticism in the first half of the twentieth century, especially in those prolific cases that involved young women.

Whose body did doctors, psychologists, and psychical researchers examine when they examined a body in which demons housed? And who claimed ownership over these bodies during medical inquiries: the doctor, Satan, the public, and/or the possessed themselves? Studying the growing concerns about the ethics of examination reveals another side to possession cases, in which the bedevilled body could become a vessel for discussions about a more humane, less invasive medical science. From this perspective, it is hoped, possession history can help recover some of the historical agency and ethical urgency of the examined body.

Session 3B: Health Movements in the Twenty-First Century

Timing: Wednesday, 08/Sept/2021, 1:30pm - 2:45pm

Chair: Dr. Ian Miller, Ulster University, United Kingdom

Medicalised mindfulness and the healing potential of spiritual practices

Stephen Gene Morris

University of Kent, United Kingdom

In 2015 the UK's Mindfulness All-Party Parliamentary Group (MAPPG) formalised the promotion of mindfulness as a tool of national wellbeing. However, scientific reviews indicate that uncertain theoretical frameworks limit the clinical development of medicalised mindfulness. When seen from a history of science perspective, the migration of meditation to psychology has taken place in several waves since 1970. In common with mindfulness, Transcendental Meditation (TM) and the Relaxation Response (RR) showed initial clinical promise before having their utility challenged by critical scientific reviews. This repeated pattern indicates the presence of a process in attempts to medicalise meditation. A persistent confounding factor in these relocations is the 'translation' of spiritual practices into concepts accessible to science and scientists. For the first time, this paper will demonstrate how the translation process inevitably changes the curative potential and, in the case of mindfulness, has also led to ontological conflict. The contemporary role of mindfulness reflects the intrinsic links between belief and religion with health and healing. However, to overcome the current crisis in mindfulness research, psychology will need to develop theoretical approaches that understand rather than translate the world views of spiritual practices.

Keywords: meditation, mindfulness, health, spirituality, religion

Religious Conversion Narratives in Twenty-First Century British Clean Eating*

Louise Morgan

University of Warwick, United Kingdom

The twenty-first century saw the development of a new approach to healthy diets – clean eating. This style of eating, at its most basic, was a commitment to eating mostly whole foods in as close to their natural state as possible, removing any food which was believed to be 'processed'. This was often intertwined with a broader emphasis on mental wellbeing or 'thinking clean', alleviating chronic symptoms, and using natural cosmetic products, allowing clean eaters to market this way of eating as a lifestyle, not a fad diet. In promoting a clean life through social media profiles, blogs, and bestselling cookbooks, British clean eaters such as Ella Mills (Deliciously Ella) came to be seen to be promoting a new moral code for modern life. This paper will examine how this code was explained through a narrative which often explicitly echoed the language and style of religious conversion, and hinted at the possibility of an Eden-like utopia. This narrative followed the clean eater as they encountered difficulties in their life, discovered a philosophy around food which helped cure these problems, and led them to spread the word of this new belief system to their followers on social media. Furthermore,

* This paper is competing in the Pieter van Foreest Student Prize.

it will examine the intense media scrutiny the clean eaters faced which explicitly targeted their use of the language of cleanliness. This backlash focused on the promotion of an apparently impossible standard of morality regarding food and nutrition in a contemporary Britain which was facing rising food poverty and food bank usage.

Keywords: clean eating, wellness, contemporary history

„Countless beings have contributed their precious life energies to supply this food that we are about to eat. Let us remember them, with gratitude. Let us eat with reverence for all life.“ - The adaption of religious practices into the US-American Wellness movement

Philipp Hauss

University Vienna/Leuphana University, Austria

Can Wellness be read as an extension of the rationalization of professional life to the private and physical? Or is it merely a technologically upgraded public health program supposed to guide a society increasingly sick with stress, wear and tear, and physical degeneration back to being productive healthy workers? Or is it another redemptive fantasy from the 1960s and 1970s California era, which was not exactly short of salvation teachings? Where does the Wellness movement stand on religion?

In my presentation I would like to introduce the trope of metaphysical gutting as an answer. This describes an ambivalent diagnosis. On the one hand Wellness concepts can be understood in terms of Max Weber's classical secularization narrative, building on a reason-led gradual rationalization of everyday life and disappearance of religious elements. On the other hand the new prominence of religious or spiritual practices contradicts such a narrative. So, to turn around Max Weber's notion of the "inner kinship" ("innere Verwandtschaft") of Protestantism and capitalism, I argue that in the case of wellness an "outer kinship" can be observed, the practices are kept alive, while the inner meaning changes. This corresponds to an ethical framework that no longer functions in the religious categories of "good" and "evil", but succumbs to a seemingly universal ideal of a homoeostatic balance, which oscillates between "too much" and "too little." In this, the wellness movement has been influential and taken hold in contemporary lifestyles.

Keywords: Prayer, Meditation, Mind-Body-Medicine, Wellness, Homoeostasis

Session 3C: Old Age in Early Modern England

Timing: Wednesday, 08/Sept/2021, 1:30pm - 2:45pm

Chair: Prof. Javier Moscoso, CSIC, Spain

Old Age Care in the Time of Crisis: Institutional Elderly Care During the Reformations of the Sixteenth-Century with a Case Study of Henry VII's Almshouse.

Christine Merie Fox

University of London, United Kingdom and Utrecht University, the Netherlands

During his formative reign, Henry VII, built, in conjunction with his Lady Chapel, an almshouse to help support his chantry at Westminster Abbey. The almshouse provided care to thirteen elderly ex-crown officials along with three elderly women who looked after the almsmen. At this time, care for the elderly was embedded within the foundations of pre-Reformation religious practice. Parish churches, hospitals, and monasteries distributed alms in the form of money, food and shelter to the poor, sick, and elderly, often in return for intercessory prayers for the benefactors. The Reformations of the sixteenth century altered and disrupted this cycle and care for the elderly was then placed in the hands of the state and civic community which resulted in stricter distinctions between those who deserved relief and those who did not. Age was no longer a gauge for charitable relief. If you were elderly and able bodied you were expected to preform your duty to society and to work. Henry's almshouse provides a good example of the impact of these changes. It managed to survive these challenging times, although not unscathed. Ultimately, it was transformed from an institution grounded in medieval Catholic charity to one based on Protestant philanthropy, providing a new model of elderly care.

Keywords: Institutional Elderly Care, Reformations, Crisis

God's Punishing 'Rod' or Supporting 'Staff'? Spiritual Interpretations of Old Age Infirmity in Early Modern English Diaries and Letters*

Amie Bolissian

University of Reading, United Kingdom

In 1723, the 65-year-old Protestant antiquarian Ralph Thoresby worried in his diary that his 'lameness and indisposition' might not be 'ascribed wholly to the infirmities that naturally accompany old age', but instead could be punishment for his 'sins'. The implication of these words is that some 'natural' elderly diseases and disabilities were not perceived as divine punishments for personal failings. Historians have explored the prevalence of providential interpretations of sickness in early modern England, showing that believers were inclined to regard sickness as divine correction for sin, a doctrine that gave rise to self-examination, feelings of guilt, and repentance practices - but rarely has age been considered a factor. Through the analysis of seventeenth and early eighteenth-century diaries and letters of women and men who identified as 'old', 'aged', or 'ancient', this paper re-examines such assumptions and shows that as women and men aged, their spiritual interpretations of illness and

* This paper is competing in the Pieter van Foreest Student Prize.

infirmity changed. They became less likely to see suffering as a direct consequence of sin, but rather emphasised the positive religious opportunities brought by sickness. This change can be seen in the very words and imagery used - the 'rod' of affliction was transformed into a supportive 'staff', a ubiquitous symbol of old age in contemporary images and texts. Through these discussions, this paper sheds light on the emotional repercussions of faith, infirmity, and old age, and in doing so, reveals a more favourable picture of ageing and illness in early modern lives than has previously been recognised.

Keywords: Age, Infirmity, Sin, Guilt, Emotions

Session 3D: Religion in Twentieth Century Hospitals

Timing: Wednesday, 08/Sept/2021, 1:30pm - 2:45pm

Chair: Dr. Joris Vandendriessche, KU Leuven, Belgium

Lay and religious nurses in the hospitals of central Europe, 1918-38: Complementary or competing?

Barry Michael Doyle

University of Huddersfield, United Kingdom

Until the twentieth century almost all nursing in Europe was undertaken by people drawn from religious orders. However, following laws in France to exclude religion from public life and more general moves toward the professionalization of nursing led from the Anglophone world, an increasing numbers of hospitals sought to replace the religieuse with lay sisters. Drawing on local records, reports from the Rockefeller Foundation staff in Europe, especially Frances Crowell, and medical journals, like *Nosokomeion*, this paper will explore emergence of lay nursing in the successor states of central Europe formed in 1918, especially Czechoslovakia and Poland.

The paper will provide a brief assessment of the role of religious nurses in these states before examining the beginnings of lay nursing in the region. This will include consideration of the part played by the Rockefeller Foundation and other NGOs in developing training programmes and facilities. It will explore the conflicts and compromises that emerged as hospitals sought to introduce lay nurses and the development of courses for religious sisters. Finally it will trace the increasing integration of trained lay nurses across the interwar period, highlighting problems caused by the weakness of health finance in the region. Overall, it will conclude that a significant range of barriers prevented the transition of nursing from religious to lay control but in the process peaceful coexistence emerged as women from orders increasingly received the same training, in the same classes, as the lay staff, leading to the professionalization of services in the region.

Keywords: Nursing, Central Europe, Training

From Re-foundation to Decline: A Century of the Catholic Church Hospitals Spain

Pilar León-Sanz

University of Navarra, Spain

From a long-term perspective, the presentation analyses the contribution of the Catholic Church to the Spanish Hospital System from the 1880s, when the first Spanish children's hospital (San Rafael, Barcelona) was created, until the 1980s, when the Hospital System changed because Public Administration transferred the healthcare competences to the Regional Governments (Autonomous Communities) and a new General Health Law (1986) was approved.

In Spain, after the processes of confiscation of the Church's properties, throughout the 19th century, hospitals with Ecclesiastical dependency disappeared. The new hospitals that re-emerged in the 1880s incorporated scientific innovations and medical specialization that were developing at that time. And, although with an interruption during the period of the Second Republic and the Civil War (1932-1939),

over the years, the Catholic Church maintained an important role in some sectors of the Health System through a good number of mainly urban and specialized hospitals (Surgical, Maternity, Children's, Psychiatric, Hospital-asylums, etc.). We also present the analysis of the reduction of the number of hospital beds that depended on the Church that occurred in the 1980s, when the contribution of these hospitals to the entire Hospital System dropped from 17% of all the beds, in 1963, to 7.5%, in 1986 (Leon-Sanz, 2018).

Keywords: History of Hospitals, 20th Century, Catholic Church, Spain

Healing the Soul: Hospital Chaplains in Britain, 1948-1990

Sian Janaki Warner

University of Birmingham, United Kingdom

This project explores the work, place and identity of Church of England hospital chaplains in Britain from 1948 to 1990. The investigation of these individuals offers a novel perspective and addition to the extensive body of historical literature examining the relationship of medicine and religion. Based upon data collected from three archives, secondary literature, and an interview conducted with an Anglican hospital chaplain, a comprehensive picture of hospital chaplains is depicted through the exploration of their workings in three different contexts. Firstly, an investigation into the introduction of the National Health Service in 1948, alongside its subsequent reorganisations in 1973 and 1990, highlights the development of the chaplaincy service within the new healthcare system. Secondly, a more detailed examination of the hospital reveals a setting in which chaplains were forced to adapt. The identity of the hospital chaplain was shaped by the foreign, professional working environment, alongside the threat of growing secularisation within the British population. Palliative care is the final setting, a specialty which, during its transformation in the twentieth century, confirmed the importance of hospital chaplains and their ministry to those facing death. Through this forty-two-year period, hospital chaplains proved to be an integral, resolute part of the healthcare service, delivering a type of care that no other healthcare professional could provide.

Keywords: hospital chaplain, twentieth century, chaplaincy, religion, palliative

Session 4A: Cultures of Healing in the Early Middle Ages (c. 750-900)

Timing: Wednesday, 08/Sept/2021, 3:15pm - 4:30pm

Chair: Debby Banham, The British School at Rome, Italy

As traditional scholarship has it, the early middle ages were not exactly a high point of medical knowledge: watered-down texts inherited from Late Antiquity were mixed with a range of superstitious, pseudo-religious or outright pagan habits, and these centuries produced nothing worth keeping in later periods. This session aims to present some results of fresh research that re-interprets early medieval cultures of healing. It will show how medical knowledge became thoroughly Christian, was far from provincial and that those texts traditionally labelled 'superstitious' were, in fact, part of venerable learned traditions.

Keywords: medieval, medical knowledge, Christianity, manuscripts

Christian Rituals in Early Medieval Medical Recipes: The Use of the Lord's Prayer

Claire Burridge

Department of History, University of Sheffield, United Kingdom

Early medieval medicine has traditionally been cast as irrational and ineffective, a folkloric medicine guided more by superstition and religion than by science. The appearance of explicitly Christian features in remedies, such as the use of holy water as an ingredient or the saying of prayers during the preparation of a treatment, has been interpreted as evidence of this 'backwardness'. Yet the incorporation of such Christianised material points to a complex, evolving relationship between medicine and religion and reveals the inappropriateness of dividing healing practices into distinct 'secular' and 'spiritual' categories in this period. A systematic investigation into the ways in which Christian rituals were integrated in early medieval medical recipes can provide a more nuanced perspective on this relationship.

The proposed paper takes the Lord's Prayer as a case study, analysing the appearance of this ritual within a sample of approximately 6500 recipes written in early medieval Europe. By considering the ways in which this prayer is used, examining the specific types of treatments in which it is included, and exploring the presence of other healing rituals, both Christian and non-Christian, involved in these recipes, this paper reassesses not only the intersections between medicine and religion but also the intertwining of Christian and pre-Christian rituals within healing practices. This in-depth analysis uncovers striking patterns regarding the use of the Lord's Prayer in recipes, highlighting the integrated, holistic approach to medicine during this period and offering new insights into its evolution.

When the Saints Go Marching In: Relics and Rational Cures around 800

Meg Leja

Department of History, Binghamton University, United States of America

The paper explores healing options available to individuals in early medieval Europe. Focusing on a manuscript that survives from the turn of the ninth century, I use it as a lens onto changing perceptions of the relationship between traditional herbal/dietetic medicine and saintly forms of healing in the

Carolingian Empire. The core of the manuscript consists of works on anatomy, humors, bloodletting, herbal recipes, and signs of illness. But what makes the collection unique is the combination of hagiographical and medical writings in one codex. The so-called “religious” works at the beginning of the book include a passion of two late antique physicians-turned-saints and a moralizing history of the treatment of disease. The history offered cautionary advice to those studying Hippocratic cures, reminding them that knowledge of plants and anatomy was only effective if a doctor sought to placate and worship the omnipotent God. However, far from drawing boundaries between “classical” and “Christian” forms of healing, this codex assembled by an anonymous scribe was a clear attempt to unify therapeutic techniques grounded in reason and experience with cures that stemmed from faith and saintly intervention. Such an agenda takes on particular significance when we consider that the early ninth century witnessed the growing popularity of Roman relics and their transplantation from Italy to northern Europe. Surging interest in the cult of relics’ ability to cure bodily diseases triggered new forms of competition within the early medieval medical marketplace. The reconciliation of these tensions is the focus of the paper.

The Dangers of the Dog Days

Carine van Rhijn

Department of History and Art History, Utrecht University, the Netherlands

This paper will focus on the way in which the so-called Dog Days (Dies caniculares) featured in early medieval medical and medico-astronomical thinking. Traditionally considered to be a typical example of early medieval (‘dark age’) superstition and therefore not part of the medical corpus, this paper will show how, quite to the contrary, ideas about the Dog Days were part of learned traditions inherited from Late Antiquity and a fixed feature of the early medieval cultures of healing. These ideas were, moreover, not passively received and copied in the Carolingian period, but creatively applied and thought through. Especially during the ninth century, with its wide-spread interest in learning and knowledge, there was an upsurge in the composition of all kinds of new texts that built on received ideas, and this includes writings that reflected on the Dog Days. How this worked will be illustrated through manuscripts from the period, that feature Dog Days in contexts as varied as Christian calendars, medical treatises, astronomy, and short tracts about different kinds of unlucky days. One element unites these texts: when Sirius, the Dog Star, was in the night sky, undergoing any type of medical treatment (especially bloodletting) was potentially lethal.

Session 4B: Abortion, Medicine and Morality in the Twentieth Century

Timing: Wednesday, 08/Sept/2021, 3:15pm - 4:30pm

Chair: Agata Ignaciuk, University of Edinburgh, United Kingdom

This panel will explore a particularly controversial area of twentieth-century healthcare, where religious and moral values have been discussed most overtly. Abortion has long been considered incompatible with both obstetricians' and midwives' *raison d'être*, to bring life into the world, and the religious Commandment, 'thou shalt not kill'. We will offer a transnational examination of abortion provision in Ireland, Canada and Britain, considering the grounds on which abortion was made available, the influence of religion and broader moral beliefs to those seeking and providing services, and the extent to which abortion was secularised in these differing medical and political contexts

Keywords: abortion, medicine, morality, religion, secularism

Religion, Medicine, and Criminal Abortions in Ireland, 1900-1967

Cara Delay

College of Charleston, United States of America

This paper examines the interface between religion (Catholicism, Protestantism and Judaism), medicine and criminal abortion in Ireland from 1900 to 1967. Focusing on criminal abortion trials, it demonstrates that religion was significant to some extent in women's clandestine abortions; women almost always sought abortions within their own religious community, for example. However, there was also a distinct lack of moral concern amongst not only abortion-seeking women but also medical professionals, including physicians, coroners, nurses, and chemists, when it came to criminal abortion. Frequently appearing in criminal trials as witnesses and sometimes as defendants, medical experts most commonly expressed sympathy for abortion-seeking women rather than condemning abortion from a moral or religious standpoint. In this, their sentiments mirrored those of abortion-seeking women more so than those of legal officials (police, judges and lawyers), who more often categorized abortion as morally wrong.

The paper demonstrates that the ordinary women seeking abortion, and the members of the medical community who helped them, rarely allowed religious beliefs or even a sense of morality to inform their reproductive decision-making. Instead, they placed their experiences within the familiar context of traditions of domestic health care and community connections. For those nurses, doctors and chemists who were willing to break the law and face serious consequences, abortion was a service they conceptualized as essential healthcare. These professionals practiced a patient-centered form of medicine that prioritised the needs and wants of ordinary women.

Unhappy Accidents: Unwanted Pregnancy, Secularism and Abortion

Chirstabelle Sethna

University of Ottawa, Canada

As a survivor of the Second World War and the Holocaust, Henry Morgentaler sailed from Europe to Montreal, Canada in 1953, opening a medical practice in the city two years later. Having been imprisoned in Auschwitz and Dachau because of his Jewish origins, Morgentaler grew convinced of the toxicity of religion. He joined the Humanist Fellowship of Montreal because of the organization's emphasis on science and secularism and became its president. When the federal government's 1967 Standing Committee on Health and Welfare entertained submissions on proposed changes to the abortion laws, Morgentaler appeared before the committee to present a brief on behalf of the Humanist Fellowship of Montreal. His testimony would place him at the forefront of an abortion law reform battle that raged over the next two decades. This paper revisits Morgentaler's testimony. It suggests that in contrast to the religion-heavy presentations physicians, clergy and laypeople made about the morality of abortion, Morgentaler's testimony deliberately constructed an unwanted pregnancy as an unhappy accident of biology and abortion as an effective technical solution applicable during the first three months of gestation. In order to do so, Morgentaler highlighted the development of the conceptus in scientific terms, secularized the morality of abortion, and insisted upon the religious plurality of Canadian society. These approaches helped him to make a case for women's access to abortion services in the first trimester that was free of legal interference from the State.

'Hideous Atheistic Expediency': Abortion, Medicine and Morality in Post-1967 Britain

Gayle Davis

University of Edinburgh, United Kingdom

The 1967 Abortion Act 'medicalised' abortion by requiring doctors to decide that the grounds were sufficient to justify a termination of pregnancy. Yet many argued that the intentional destruction of human life could not be treated as a normal aspect of healthcare, and doctors arguably had little more than their own moral values to guide them. The Act has since been subjected to fierce contestation. The Catholic Church, the 'most effective pressure group in British politics', has mobilised its networks in various effective ways and championed those Catholic doctors and nurses allegedly discriminated against for refusing to participate. Parliamentarians of strong Christian faith have made the case for (mostly) restrictive reform. The major anti-abortion groups – SPUC and LIFE – have sought to present a more non-denominational character, though not always convincingly. All recognised that medical evidence had the greatest potential to fight their cause, and recruited senior obstetricians as prominent spokespeople.

This paper will examine the relationship between religion, morality and abortion provision in Britain over the lifetime of the Act: how religious belief and moral values informed interpretations of the Act and attempts to restrict the legislation. It will explore how moral arguments were often justified through or translated into medical 'evidence', from the use of in utero visualisation technologies to the pathologisation of women's post-abortion distress as 'post-abortion syndrome', and how such evidence was interpreted by the wider medical community.

Session 4C: German Chronicles of Welfare, Health, and Spirituality, 1750-1900*

Timing: Wednesday, 08/Sept/2021, 3:15pm - 4:30pm

Chair: Avi Sharma, University of Tennessee, Knoxville, United States of America

This panel aims to shed light on the intertwined relationship between the church and health reforms in eighteenth-century and nineteenth-century Germany. Panelists will explore various approaches towards German welfare and health, how the church embraced new intellectual health movements, and the ways in which religion informed state-based poverty relief efforts and public health institutions. They also examine how religious leaders, state officials, and individual citizens interpreted health, death, and the body. These narratives of missionaries and church leaders illuminate the continued influence of religion on German medical knowledge and ideas of health.

Keywords: Welfare, Health, State-Church Relationships, Germany, Spirituality

Spiritual Health, Bodily Illness: Death Narratives in Eighteenth-Century Moravian Church

Kelly Douma Kaelin

The Pennsylvania State University, United States of America

The eighteenth-century sits at the cusp of the modern era. Often associated with Enlightenment ideals and increased medical knowledge, the eighteenth-century was also a time of increased religiosity and a rejection of rational religion, particularly in the German states. The Moravians, a separatist and migratory religious group from eastern Germany, participated in both the wider intellectual movements of the age as well as preaching their “religion of the heart,” a rejection of orthodox Lutheranism and a belief in childlike trust in Christ. The Moravians traveled widely throughout the eighteenth-century world, becoming the first truly global Protestant missionaries. In order to maintain a sense of global community, the Moravians published and circulated spiritual memoirs of their deceased members. This study focuses specifically on the extensive focus on final illness and death within these pages, often comprising up to half of the total life narrative. These narratives contain contemporary vernacular medical terms for lay-diagnoses as well as attempts at cures. Particularly in the Caribbean, where Moravian women both nursed enslaved Africans and themselves fell prey to sudden and fatal illnesses, these memoirs shed light on the religious juxtaposition of bodily sickness and spiritual health. In a church that largely shunned an organized written theology, these constructed and distributed narratives centering on illness, loss of life, and assured salvation offer a fascinating glimpse into how medical crises were interpreted in ways both beneficial for the individual believer and the church as a whole.

Bridging the Divide: Church and State Poor Relief in Elberfeld

Rebekah O. McMillan

Angelo State University, United States of America

Located in the mountainous area of the lower Rhineland in the Wupper Valley, the city of Elberfeld (known today as Wuppertal) is home to the most notable form of state-sponsored German poor relief

in the nineteenth century. Known as the Elberfeld System and originating in 1853, it operated under the conviction that only through knowing the condition of the poor and the circumstances behind that condition could the problem of poverty be solved within a community. The Elberfeld System utilized local poor relief volunteers to investigate the needs of those impoverished and build relationships between those officials and the poor to ensure relief was deserved and appropriate. This System only came about after the city vacillated between church and state relief for over half a century. Even when state control officially subsumed church responsibility, the role of religion and church guidance continued to play an integral part in the System's development. Utilizing municipal and church records, this paper will explore the shift away from church-based control while also exploring the ways in which religious ideas about poverty remained central to the ideology that undergirded state-sponsored relief. Elberfeld provides a unique location study as it was an area of early industrial development within the German states and contained an active church presence of the three main denominations, Reformed Calvinist, Catholic, and Lutheran. Additionally, the Elberfeld System would go on to become the most prominent form of localized poor relief adopted by cities throughout Germany by the end of Wilhelmine Era.

Knocking on Heaven's Door: Religious Leaders and Public Health Institutions in Nineteenth-Century Bavaria *

Alyssa Nicole Culp

University of Tennessee, Knoxville, United States of America

After the 1854 Cholera Epidemic violently ripped through the city of Munich, citizens gathered at Mary's Column in Marienplatz to give thanks to God and with hopes that the worst was over. Soon after, state physicians formed a commission to search for ways to promote cleanliness and prevent illness. They were not the only advocates of health at this time, however. Long before nineteenth-century public health efforts, priests and church leaders took the lead in providing poor relief for their parishioners, recording deaths, and caring for the corpse. Death took on new meaning in the nineteenth century as morgue-based physicians replaced priests as the final authority of death. The morgue set in motion changes to various burial processes and who controlled the corpse. While threatened by this incursion, religious involvement did not disappear entirely as leaders worked to cooperate with state officials.

This paper examines the tension between state authority and religious leaders. While at first opposed to this shift, local religious leaders soon became invested in the morgue and used their church resources to promote cleanliness, provide basic care for their parishioners, and fund these public health institutions. My paper analyzes physician reports, diocesan policies, and clerical journals to reveal how religion continued to inform state-based health institutions like the morgue. I argue that while public health became a state sanctioned venture, religious leaders continued to influence medical practice and public health regulations as they possessed knowledge of common maladies, understood local traditions, and held parishioners' trust.

* This paper is competing in the Pieter van Foreest Student Prize.

Session 4D: Nurses and Midwives

Timing: Wednesday, 08/Sept/2021, 3:15pm - 4:30pm

Chair: Prof. Hilary Marland, University of Warwick, United Kingdom

Faith in Care: Religion and Conversion in Nursing, 1918 - 1965

Sarah Chaney¹, Frances Reed¹

¹*RCN Library and Archive Service, United Kingdom*

When teenager Maria Lorentzon ran away from her home in Sweden to train as a nurse in London in 1960, she was surprised by the way religion permeated hospital wards. Her hospital “was very Anglican” she recalled in an oral history for the Royal College of Nursing (RCN). There were ward services on Sundays and only a communicant in the Church of England could be hired as matron. By 1960, Lorentzon thought, “the cracks really were beginning to show”, and she refused to take part in “conversion activities”.

Nursing in many countries has been closely linked to religious orders since at least the Middle Ages. Historians of nineteenth century nursing, like Siobhan Nelson, have highlighted the “conventual” atmosphere in nursing schools and connections with religious groups. This practice inspired and supported the popular notion of nursing as a vocation, a calling and an act of service.

As Maria Lorentzon’s story shows, the close connection between religion and nursing continued well into the twentieth century, although this has received rather less attention from historians. Drawing on oral histories, books and objects from the RCN collection used in our exhibition *Who Cares? A History of Emotions in Nursing*, this paper argues for a need to look critically at the way religious faith has shaped nursing care and practice. We reflect on our learning from developing the exhibition around the way stories of faith in nursing are shared with a public audience and conclude with some important questions for the history of nursing.

Keywords: history of nursing, nursing, religious conversion, oral history

Proselytizing for the Nursing Profession: American Mission Nurses in Iran, 1916-1979

Lydia Wytenbroek

University of British Columbia, Canada

In the twentieth century, American missionary nurses, working under the auspices of the American Presbyterian Mission to Iran, established areas of educational innovation within mission medicine and Iranian healthcare. Drawing on the records of the American Presbyterian Historical Society, as well as oral histories, memoirs and family photographs, I consider the tensions these women faced between their professional and religious work. In their applications to the Presbyterian Board of Foreign Missions, they emphasized their personal faith and religiosity. Once they were in Iran, however, they strived to develop the nursing profession and “produce fine nurses for Iran.” In effect, they proselytized for the nursing profession. Missionary nurse Eunice Baber noted: “I am not a born missionary, but I am a fanatic about nursing.” This paper considers how American nurses reframed their nursing work as Christian service and used this idea of Christian service to argue for the provision

of high quality health care and nursing education. In this paper, I complicate the often false dichotomy between science and religion and reshape scholarly understanding about transnational medical encounters.

Keywords: Presbyterian missionaries, nursing history, American missions, imperialism, mission medicine

The Dutch Catholic midwives Union: More than shared values?

Marga Pruijt

Tilburg University, the Netherlands

After being granted full political rights in the nineteenth, Catholics in the Netherlands started an trajectory of emancipation. In the political system of pillarisation all social groups got rights to build their own social structure including schools, political parties and professional organisations. In 1912 a Catholic school for midwives was formed and in 1921 a Catholic midwives organisation, the Rooms-Katholieke Bond van vroedvrouwen. Not the midwives themselves, but the clergy initiated this occupational union. The midwives in the southern provinces, that are mainly populated by a Catholic population, welcomed this step. Among a group of 900 midwives in totality, the Catholic Union united about half of the 200 Catholic midwives.

In this lecture I want to address the question what the Catholic midwives Union meant in the pre-war period (1920-1940) for its members, inspired by theories of Freidson, Johnson and Witz. Was the Catholic midwives Union able to represent the voice of its members, and if so, in what ways? Was it especially a community where Catholic midwives shared their religious values and rituals? Did the Union support the acceptance of Catholic midwives by the local population and government to be a trusted partner in the care of mothers and infants? How did the union act on debates on midwifery and obstetric knowledge? How did the promotion of the midwives economic interests take place?

In my lecture I want to give an overview of these issues, based on my PHD research on Midwives in Noord-Brabant 1861-1941.

Keywords: Midwives, catholic, professional organisation, values

Session 4E: Health and Religion in Latin-America

Timing: Wednesday, 08/Sept/2021, 3:15pm - 4:30pm

Chair: Prof. Frank Huisman, UMC Utrecht, the Netherlands

Entheogenic Visions: Latin American Indigenous Psychoactive Substances in Images and Words

Milton Fernando González Rodríguez

KU Leuven, the Netherlands

This paper explores the ways in which images and written resources of various types have historically mobilized ideas about psychoactive substances from a medicinal, therapeutic, spiritual and religious perspective. In specific, the main focus lies on reviewing the visual and textual framing of entheogens, such as *Lophophora williamsii* (i.e., peyote), *Datura wrightii* (i.e., sacred datura), and brews produced of mixing *Banisteriopsis caapi* and *Psychotria viridis* (i.e., ayahuasca). The underlying premise is that ever since the first encounters of Europeans with indigenous communities actively consuming entheogens in the 17th century, these substances have been entwined with elements of spirituality, faith and (dark)magic. The intangibility of hallucination-inducing plants has been contrasted with the materiality of their effects in the care and cure of the body and mind of their consumers. I place emphasis on the instrumentality of the notion of indigeneity at various moments in history to contextualize the attributes of psychoactive substances. As I argue, while the diffusion of the above-mentioned plants reflects changes, additions and transfers of peripheral medicine-related knowledge(s) trans-continently, their commercialization and promotion concomitantly raise questions about the legacy of (neo)colonization. As I show, all along, images have registered the journey of indigenous psychoactive substances from Latin America across Western media outlets.

Keywords: Psychoactive, indigenous, knowledge transfer, spirituality, colonialism

Pascal Baylón, Saint Sebastian, and the Señora de los Remedios – New Spain’s Catholic Saints in Times of Epidemics

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University of Klagenfurt, Austria

While it seems clear that America was no disease-free paradise in pre-contact times, a combination of war, drought, low fertility, and new pathogens resulted in enormous population losses. People turned to saints, deities or super-natural beings for help. Catholicism in Spanish America undeniably had a focus on embodiments of the Virgin Mary. Ciudad de México’ first patroness, the Señora de los Remedios, was closely associated with droughts, phenomena inseparably linked to epidemics. In 1577, during the huey cocoliztli epidemic of hemorrhagic fever, a large procession was organized in her honor. When an infectious disease hit the Yucatán peninsula in 1648, a statue of the “Virgin of Izamal” was brought from her shrine to the main city of Mérida on orders of the governor. The “Virgin of Guadalupe” was proclaimed patroness of Ciudad de México because of her role during the epidemic of 1737–1739, but only after two other icons had failed to end the crisis. In the city of Veracruz, of exposed to yellow fever outbreaks, Saint Sebastian, one of the “grandes santos anti peste” (P. Ragon),

became an iconic figure. Around 1650, the Cakchiquel Maya of the Guatemalan highlands increasingly turned to the veneration of Pascal Baylón, a Spanish priest who had died in 1592, and was said to have appeared in a vision during the deadly cumatz epidemic. Even after the introduction of inoculation in the late 18th century, authorities proposed public veneration of saints, but also relied on support by clerics in the implementation of “modern” health practices.

Keywords: New Spain, Health, Epidemics, Saints, Veneration

A new faith in the state, through public health systems. The first Ministry of Health in Argentina (Santa Fe province, 1938-1941)

Jose Ignacio Allevi

CONICET, Universidad Nacional de Rosario, Argentine Republic

In this presentation we want to discuss a particular case in Argentina that helps to understand how the rationalization of public health helped to shape a new faith in state capacities and civil rights. This process reflects multiple influences. Firstly, global ones, through the impact of international health organisations on the promotion of centralization of health systems, along with the diffusion of new biomedical advances. Secondly, the national arena, that is, the state of affairs of public health debate and institutions in Argentina at the end of the 1930s. My object, though, relies on the specificity of on local government: the province of Santa Fe. Regarding its political and academic particularities, the first public health ministry of the country emerged here in 1941, with clear influences of the Rockefeller Foundation and its network among local physicians. The relevance of this case is that, for the first time in this country, ideas and discourses were accompanied with practices, institutions and budget. The objective of this presentation is to explore how the politicians and experts involved in its process justified this pioneer agency in Argentina in terms state responsibilities, which also constituted a local echo of a global process. Therefore, I will explore how public health appeared to politicians and bureaucrats as an effective way to engineered social structure and solve structural problems. But also to construct a new form of state and public right, sustained on technical knowledge of health experts.

Keywords: public health, international health, state agencies, experts, Argentina

Session 5A: Animal Magnetism, Hypnotism and Religion in Nineteenth Century Europe

Timing: Thursday, 09/Sept/2021, 9:00am - 10:15am

Chairs: Heather Wolfram, Kaat Wils, KU Leuven, Belgium

19th century therapeutic uses of animal magnetism and later hypnotism interfered with religion in many ways. The bodily convulsions that were part of the treatment of physical ailments as developed by Mesmer in the late 18th century, reminded of practices of exorcism by Catholic priests. While the Catholic Church never condemned animal magnetism or hypnotism, it was nevertheless suspicious of its potential materialist character and warned against its moral dangers. When in the middle of the 19th century magnetism became intertwined with spiritualism in Protestant regions and spiritism in Catholic regions, religion entered the therapeutic field in a new way.

Keywords: Animal Magnetism, Hypnotism, Religion

The 19th century debate on animal magnetism viewed from Rome: the Holy Office's decrees

David Armando

Institute for the History of Philosophy and Science in the Modern Age, Italian National Research Council

From the end of the 1830s the Congregation of the Holy Office began to examine the doctrines and practices of animal magnetism and hypnosis. The attitude of the Roman Inquisition towards the prodigies of mesmerist therapies and magnetic somnambulism was divided between a sharp condemnation of their materialistic interpretation, a strong but hidden suspicion of their demonic nature, and a prudent attention to the progress of sciences. The Holy See's concerns about animal magnetism became more and more explicit, but only in 1856 did Pius IX officially condemn its "abuses". The Vatican records also reflect the interest - and the heated scientific and theological debate - that animal magnetism and hypnosis raised all over Europe and beyond. The Inquisition's decrees did, indeed, respond to the demands addressed by ecclesiastic and civil authorities, thus revealing a network of correspondence between Roman theologians and clerics scattered all over the Catholic world, such as the Bruges canon Joseph Andries. But applicants to the Holy Office also include a few Catholic physicians, asking whether they were allowed to magnetize their patients in order to heal them. At the same time the Congregation itself often referred to the most recent scientific positions in order to fight animal magnetism, or to turn it against materialistic philosophy. In both cases, the disputes concerning these phenomena, which challenged both science and theology, help to highlight the shifting border between religion and medicine and their complex relationships, made up of contraposition and concurrence, but also of complementarities and reciprocal transfers.

Catholics, animal magnetism and therapeutic hypnosis in 19th century Belgium

Kaat Wils

Research Group Cultural History since 1750, KU Leuven

During the 1830s and 1840s, a lively and in some cases spectacular culture of magnetic healing developed in Belgium. In this predominantly Catholic country, criticism against these practices did not only come in the form of allegations of unlawful practice of medicine, but also on religious grounds. Attitudes of Catholic authors were however diverse. While some undertook a moral crusade against a practice that was represented as immoral and potentially satanic, others tended to approach animal magnetism as a natural phenomenon which could be put to use in a therapeutic context. Still others, such as the cleric and aristocrat Louis De Robiano experimented with magnetism and propagated its therapeutic use. In the meantime, the public transnational correspondence on the matter with the Holy See (in which also a Belgian cleric, Joseph Andries, actively participated) was closely followed among Catholics. When in the late 1850s lay practices of magnetism became increasingly intermingled with religious spiritism and when in 1856 the pope issued an Encyclical that warned against magnetism's potential dangers, Catholic skepticism towards its use seems to have grown. In the last quarter of the century, however, when hypnotism became popular within a more medicalized and academic setting, Catholic doctors started to embrace its practice and defended its natural character against more skeptical clerics. In so doing, they could tie in with a longstanding Catholic tradition of caring for the soul and develop a secular therapy which was not unfamiliar to the religious practice of exorcism in cases of demonic possession.

Animal magnetism, hypnosis research and religion in Hungary

Júlia Gyimesi

Department of Personality and Clinical Psychology, the Pázmány Péter Catholic University, Hungary

Animal magnetism was known from the early 1800s in Hungary due to German and French influence. Several of the earliest proponents of animal magnetism in Hungary were physicians (such as Ferenc Szapáry, János Kováts, Mihály Lenhossék, Josa Oroszhegyi, János Gárdos, and János Mailáth) who considered animal magnetism to be an especially effective healing method in numerous diseases. Among them, the physician János Gárdos' (1813–1893) theories on animal magnetism proved to be decisive in regard to the evolution of magnetic practices and hypnosis in Hungary. Gárdos identified magnetic phenomena as the result of as yet unknown capacities of the human psyche. The magnetic cures of Gárdos, in which he combined mesmeric techniques and his unique spiritualistic interpretation, gained great acclaim. However, contemporary representatives of early hypnosis research (especially Pál Ranschburg (1870–1945)) rejected his theory and identified it as magical-mystical and superstitious. As a result, animal magnetism was discredited within academic science, however, it subsisted in the field of spiritualism. The most important representative of spiritualistic animal magnetism was Adolf Grünhut (1826–1906). The animal magnetism represented by Grünhut had very strong Christian features. This was partly due to the impact of “evangelistic spiritism” in Hungary, a popular, religious branch of spiritualism. The influence of Grünhut became far-reaching in Hungary both in the fields of animal magnetism and popular healing techniques.

Session 5B: Rethinking Changing Concepts of Health and Disease

Timing: Thursday, 09/Sept/2021, 9:00am - 10:15am

Chair: Hieke Huistra, Erasmus MC University Medical Center Rotterdam, the Netherlands

Between the poles of constructivism on the one hand and realism on the other, medical historians have tended to focus on the social and cultural of health and disease, without getting rid of 'the biologically real' entirely. This philosophical position has not received the historiographical reflection it deserves. What is not socially and culturally constructed about disease and health, and what role should it play in our histories? The project 'Health and disease as practical concepts' proposes a new reading of Fleck's active and passive elements of knowledge as a nuanced solution, using historical cases of diabetes and chronic pain.

Keywords: historiography of disease, constructivism vs. realism, Ludwik Fleck, diabetes, chronic pain

'Except for the sugar, one is completely healthy': concepts of diabetes mellitus in the Dutch Diabetics Association (1945-1970)

Floor Haalboom

Erasmus MC University Medical Center Rotterdam, the Netherlands

In 1947, a Dutch diabetic wrote to his association of fellow diabetics: 'I consider it incorrect that [...] one is treated as a sick person, while, except for the sugar, one is completely healthy.' And he was not the only one. Organised diabetics conceptualized their chronic disease – diabetes mellitus – mainly in terms of health during the first decades of the existence of the Dutch Diabetics Association (Nederlandse Vereniging van Suikerzieken) between 1945 and 1970. They campaigned for a new understanding of diabetics as 'normal' members of society, and redefined their illness in terms of independent health. But diabetics could not simply declare themselves well. Reaching this goal entailed dealing with 'the sugar' by living responsibly according to medical prescriptions. This meant that organised diabetics also had to find new ways to relate to medical authority and vice versa.

This paper argues that looking at organised patients is crucial for understanding changes in concepts of disease and health in different social contexts. The journal of the Dutch Diabetics Association provides early source material to enable this. Different from histories based on individual patient files written by doctors in a clinical context, this source material enables a history of the patient perspective in daily, social life. Disease concepts necessarily differ in these different contexts – but this does not mean that these concepts are solely socially constructed.

‘A disease in its own right’: a social history of the definition and classification of chronic pain

Timo Bolt¹, Rik van der Linden¹

¹*Erasmus MC University Medical Center Rotterdam, the Netherlands*

‘Chronic pain constitutes an immense, invisible crisis at the center of contemporary life’. In this one sentence in *The Culture of Pain*, David M. Morris summarized a disturbing, paradoxical state of affairs. On the one hand, chronic pain entails a huge burden of disease at high social costs, but on the other hand, it remains a largely misunderstood, elusive phenomenon, which hardly generates interest from medical researchers or health policy circles. There is, however, a possible light at the horizon. In the 11th edition of the International Classification of Diseases (ICD), which is expected to be implemented in 2022, a separate category of ‘chronic pain’ is included. By classifying chronic pain as a disease (category), rather than as a symptom, advocates hope to generate more attention for chronic pain and its management.

In this paper, it will be argued that the emergence of the new, distinct category in the ICD-11 should be placed against the historical backdrop of the development of pain medicine since the 1970s, accompanied by an increasingly powerful advocacy of the recognition of chronic pain as ‘a disease in its own right’. From this, it will follow that the definition and classification of chronic pain is and has been a continuing historical process, determined by both social and biological realities and serving pragmatic and performative rather than intellectual and scientific ends. This will, finally, help to define the social utility, the ‘biological’ constraints, and the potential negative side-effects of the new classification of chronic pain.

Between realism and constructivism: active and passive elements of diabetes and chronic pain

Nick Binney

Erasmus MC University Medical Center Rotterdam, the Netherlands

The two previous talks reveal a variety of different ways of understanding sick people. Patients and their doctors want to get chronic pain recognized as a disease, because of the social function of the disease status. In the case of diabetes, patient groups championed the view that by living responsibly they could become well, rejecting the disease label because of its social significance.

How do historians take this social influence on ways of understanding sick people into account without washing their hands of the question of truth? Monica Green has argued that historians writing the history of diseases face a dilemma: to investigate the social ‘reality’ of disease as historical actors understood it, or to make use of modern biological knowledge to investigate what ‘really’ happened to sick people in the past. Appealing to the philosophical work of Ludwik Fleck, constructivist historians such as Andrew Cunningham deny that it is possible to investigate what ‘really’ happened in the past, as even biological reality is determined by social reality. Charles Rosenberg has tried to mediate between these constructivist and realist poles, arguing that disease has a biological reality that is “framed” by society in different ways; but even this admits that there is a biological reality that needs taking into account. By re-reading Fleck’s account of the active and passive elements of knowledge, we can show how to recognize a great variety of different ways of understanding sick people, without accepting that anything people believe is true.

Session 5C: Faith and Healing in the Middle East

Timing: Thursday, 09/Sept/2021, 9:00am - 10:15am

Chair: Prof. Javier Moscoso, CSIC, Spain

The Synergy between Religion and Medicine as a Method of Healing in Arabic Medicine

Ayman Yasin Atat

FU Berlin, Germany

The relation between religion and medicine seems to be having a long historical aspect, in the Arabic civilization for instance, there were a branch of medicine called the prophetic medicine, and its rules were established upon the Hadiths of Prophet. Practicing this kind of medicine was completely depending on the faith level of the patient and even the physician himself. Therefore, it is ordinary to see some Arabic medical books written about using Hadiths or Quranic verses as a method for healing patients. However, we cannot say that the prophetic medicine was the main way of healing during the Arabic civilization, but honestly, physicians were faithful for the traditional method that relies on using simple drugs or compound ones.

On the 15th century al-‘Āmirī ‘Imād al-Dīn (d. 893H/1488 AD) who was a historian, a pioneer speaker, and has a knowledge of simple drugs; in addition, he served as a Shaikh in Yemen. He wrote a fascinating Arabic medical manuscript entitled (Al-Tuḥfah al-Jāmi‘ah li-mufradāt al-Ṭibb al-Nāfi‘ah; “the collective masterpiece for the beneficial medical simples”). It is interesting to note that al-‘Āmirī treats some diseases by using the faith healing as a sedative method to work together with the simple drugs in healing the patients to be as a synergy between religion and medicine. Therefore, through this manuscript this talk is going to shed light on the phenomenon of using the faith of religion and traditional therapies together for healing aims in the Arabic medicine.

Keywords: Arabic medicine, faith healing, Prophetic medicine, al-‘Āmirī, synergy between religion and medicine

Contagion and Faith: between Prophetic Medicine and Science

Shahrazad Irannejad

Orient-Institut Istanbul, Germany

The notion of contagion, now widely assumed as a medical problem, has historically been a point of contestation in the context of hadith scholarship and religious jurisprudence in the Islamicate tradition. Contagion has continually been a contested concept within an alternative mode of healing (active even today in contemporary Iran) widely labelled “Prophetic Medicine”. Prophetic Medicine draws on collections of Prophetic tradition (hadith) with medical content, while explicating pathophysiology using tenets of humoral medicine. In this body of knowledge, there is a twofold resistance to the integration of the concept of contagion: the resistance to contagion inherent in Galenic humorism and a number of transmitted Prophetic Traditions (hadith) that seem to deny the existence of contagion. The textual corpora of humoral medicine offer circumstantial knowledge, while prophetic medicine deals with eternal, revealed knowledge. As laid out by Ahmed Ragab (2012) in the case of modern Egypt, corpora of prophetic medicine keeps getting recreated in accordance

with the contemporaneous, if I may, “scientific” views. Avoiding the trope of the supposed epistemological conflict between religion and science, this paper would explore the nuanced overlaps of the two discourses in Iran, using contagion as a conceptual node. Implementing discourse analysis of texts in Arabic and Persian on the problem of contagion within the tradition of prophetic medicine, the study would show how actors writing within this discourse have needed to constantly find a point of balance between two faiths: faith in contemporaneous “scientific medicine” and faith in the infallibility of Prophetic tradition.

Keywords: Prophetic Medicine, Contagion, Faith, Iran, Discourse Analysis

Health amulets in ancient Egypt

Hedvig Győry

Museum of Fine Arts and HEFS, Hungary

Ancient Egyptian medicine was famous at its time to be very effective. Indeed, the prescriptions contain many drugs used still today, although the way of use changed a lot. One of the big differences is the use of amulets, which were prepared and applied by specific persons and special methods together with medical treatment or instead of it.

Amulets were used in ancient Egypt for various reasons by living and dead persons, gods or even animals, but always in the field of protection or prevention. They worked by the magical power given for them with the spells casted in sacred temple workshops, or places chosen by the wizard-priests; as they called them sau „amulet/protection-men”. The name refers to the aim or the way of their activity, namely they provided protection against accidents, bad intention of gods or people, hex such as evil eye, but also for fecundity, recovery, succesfull medical treatment, providing good mother milk or prevention with the use of amulets – beside other magical means. Either physician or priest or amulet-man examined a patient, they all used for the medical treatment both drugs and magical tools – the proportions changed, however, significantly.

A group of the ancient Egyptain amulets were called „health amulets” by the ancient texts. The paper will discuss how such an amulet was chosen for the given medical purpose, what it was like and which way it was applied, based on ancient Egyptian texts and objects.

Keywords: ancient Egyptian medicine, magic, amulet, iatromagia, health and fecundity

Session 5D: Modern Mental Health Discourses

Timing: Thursday, 09/Sept/2021, 9:00am - 10:15am

Chair: Prof. Octavian Buda, 'Carol Davila' University, Bucharest

Catastrophic Times: Trauma, Jewish Identity, and Mental Hygiene after the First World War

David Freis

University of Münster, Germany

In Eastern Europe, the end of the First World War did not end the fighting. Ukraine was ravaged by the German occupation, the Russian revolution, and the ensuing civil war. From the end of 1918 to August 1920, Kyiv changed hands sixteen times as different factions in the civil war struggled for supremacy. The Jewish community was particularly affected by the violence, as more than 1,200 pogroms, most of the committed by the White army and Ukrainian nationalists, devastated Jewish homes, businesses, and places of worship. Many Jewish children, often wounded, traumatised, and orphaned, flocked to Kyiv.

One place where these children received care and medical treatment was the clinic of the pedagogic institute of the University of Kyiv, led by Fischl Schneersohn (1887–1958), a physician, psychologist, and descendant of an eminent dynasty of Chassidic rebbes. Schneersohn developed a treatment programme that also included an extensive psychological examination – using an innovative methodology that relied on games, narrations, and art. For Schneersohn, his experiences and observations became a point of departure for broader reflections about new forms of ‘social and mental hygiene’ to rebuild Jewish communities and to foster resilience and a shared identity.

The aim of this paper is to explore Schneersohn’s pedagogical treatment and psychological examination of his child patients in the aftermath of the First World War, and to situate his understanding of trauma, resilience, and Jewish identity in the historical and intellectual context of the early inter-war period.

Keywords: Psychotherapy, mental hygiene, childhood trauma, Eastern European history, Jewish history

“Felo de se”: Religious beliefs and medical discourses on suicide

Vasia Lekka¹, Thanasis Lagios¹

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Traditional (positivist) historical narratives tend to see suicide’s historical course as a sign of progress, moving from the theological condemnation of the person who committed suicide as a “sinner” to the scientific explanation and treatment of the “suicidal person”. Indeed, given that, in medieval and early modern Europe, suicide was considered as a deadly sin, there has been noted a significant rupture in late-eighteenth and nineteenth century. Within the context of the emergence of biopolitical societies, scientific medicine and psychiatry constituted suicide as a “disease” and the suicidal person as a “patient”; a process still in the making, culminating in the so-called “Suicidal Behavior Disorder” in

DSM-5, with suicide being both a symptom of several psychiatric disorders and a psychiatric disorder per se. Despite this obvious rupture, however, the dominant attitudes and prejudices toward suicide and the latter's ethical condemnation remained rather intact, with biomedicine taking the reins and emerging as a new form of religion. From this perspective, instead of a strictly conflictual relation between religion and medicine, one can actually detect a rather complementary one, as the dichotomy "legal/illegal" according to the Divine Law is supplemented by the dichotomy "normal/pathological" according to the biomedical Norm. Based upon our recently published book, the aim of our paper is to illustrate suicide's historical course from its theological condemnation to its psychiatrization, in order to delineate the (explicit and implicit) interaction between the medical and the religious discourse regarding suicide within Western societies.

Keywords: suicide, psychiatry, biopolitics, normal/pathological

Session 5E: Female Bodies Across Time

Timing: Thursday, 09/Sept/2021, 9:00am - 10:15am

Chair: Prof. Anne Kveim Lie, University of Oslo, Norway

Female Bodies as Living Relics: Healing Powers, Gender and Faith in three Brabant Vitae*

Pavlina Kulagina

Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Germany

The vitae of three holy women of Brabant, Christina the Astonishing (c. 1150 – 1224), Marie of Oignies (1177 – 1213) and Lutgard of Aywieres (1182 – 1246) depict rather different paths to perfection: those of a penitent castaway, a Beguine saint and a Benedictine nun. At the same time, several common features in the attitude to holiness run through the vitae. Notably, it's clear how their veneration is influenced by the burgeoning relic cult of the High Middle Ages. While the fascinating and often shockingly graphic miracles performed by their saintly remains are regularly cited, a crucial aspect tends to be overlooked. Preceding and prefiguring the post-mortem veneration of remains of the holy women, their own living bodies are already treated as miraculous and desired relics in their lifetime by their communities and even by themselves. The aim of my analysis is to investigate this process in detail. Christina, Marie and Lutgard themselves are fully aware of how their communities intend to use their remains, so the ascetic practices and physically intense mystical experiences of these holy women can be seen as preparation of the body for a miraculous earthly afterlife. Moreover, their bodies start performing healing miracles during life, mainly through bodily fluids such as tears, saliva and breast milk. The presentation will thus focus on how the division between living body and dead relic fades, and "new kinds of animated materiality" (Caroline Bynum) emerge.

Keywords: mysticism, hagiography, relic cult, christian materiality, female spirituality

Medical approaches to female virginity and their confessional context in the Low Countries (1645-1725)

Sophie Herz

University of Ghent, Belgium

The Catholic regime that reigned over Europe in the early modern period are, unlike Protestantism, often seen as a significant limitation on the development of scientific knowledge and practices. My research, however, will argue that this was certainly not always the case. I will analyse how both Flemish and Dutch physicians from 1645 to 1724 confronted their medical knowledge of the female body in their medical treatises based on anatomical dissections with their own beliefs, either Protestant or Catholic. First, I will compare how physicians connected to the Protestant University of Leiden and physicians from the Catholic University of Leuven went about this subject in different ways. Secondly, I will compare this with the way in which physicians working in an urban environment went about the same topic. These comparisons will indicate whether these physicians had more freedom of thought in an urban setting than the ones connected to these two religious universities. They will

* This paper is competing in the Pieter van Foreest Student Prize.

also tell us how Protestantism and Catholicism both influenced physicians in the Low Countries in different ways when talking about the female body and how this differed from one another in different settings, one being the university, the other the city. On this basis, I will argue that the Catholic faith is not necessarily more of a limitation to scientific innovations than Protestantism and was perhaps even an instigator for a more critical way of reasoning.

Keywords: Medicine, religion, gender, Low Countries

Comparative and interdisciplinary research on the issue of female fasting through the ages*

Steve Vilhem

University of Lausanne, Switzerland

Historically, in the West, female fasting was not considered a disease by medicine until the 19th century, although the practice has been reported far before in the past. During medieval times, some women with extreme forms of fasting, far from being medicalized, were revered. This is reported by the many hagiographic sources of the medieval period - such as the famous example of Catherine of Siena. The transition that occurred in the 19th century in the West in the representation of anorexia nervosa was that of the image of the saint (anorexia mirabilis) to that of the sick (anorexia nervosa), this transition being the culmination of a double process of secularization and medicalization of society. The aim of our paper is to propose a comparative study, using an interdisciplinary approach, between two forms of female fasting: mystical and religious in medieval times on the one hand; secularized in our contemporary world on the other. This combination of history and psychoanalysis will enable us to deepen our analysis, insofar as the proposed interpretations are constantly placed in the light of the concrete socio-historical conditions of each milieu in each era. Based on this comparison between two forms of female fasting, we will propose in conclusion an epistemological reflection questioning the very nature and the contemporary psychiatric definition of anorexia nervosa.

Keywords: Anorexia nervosa, female fasting, anorexia mirabilis, interdisciplinary study

* This paper is competing in the Pieter van Foreest Student Prize.

Session 6A: Religious Differentials in Causes of Death, 1850-1940. Part I

Timing: Thursday, 09/Sept/2021, 10:45am - 12:00pm

Chair: Angélique Janssens, Ghent University, Belgium

Historical analyses of the relationship between religious affiliation and demographic behavior have focused on Catholic, Protestant and Jewish differentials, with most studies showing the highest mortality for Catholics. Explanations for the differences have been wide-ranging, pointing to specific religious values, attitudes and/or life styles. Definitive answers remain elusive. In two sessions we present studies from the SHiP network. The network focuses on port cities with individual-level cause-of-death data for the period 1850-1950, supplemented by data for specific subpopulations such as hospital patients. Information on the causes of death of these population groups can clarify how religion affects health.

Keywords: Religion, causes of death, demography

Mortality and Causes of Death in Nineteenth-Century Venice. A Comparison of Jews and Catholics.

Renzo Derosas¹, Cristina Munno¹

¹*Ca' Foscari University of Venice, Italy*

Countless studies showed that in the past and throughout the world, infant mortality in Jewish communities was dramatically lower than in their host populations. Comparisons of mortality at later ages are less common. However, there is enough evidence suggesting that also the mortality of Jewish adults and the elderly was lower, although in a lesser measure, prompting a wider consideration of Jewish specificity. Rates eventually converged, but the Jewish advantage persisted before and during the mortality transition, until well into the twentieth century.

Scholars suggested a variety of factors to explain the lower mortality of Jews, but none seems fully convincing and the issue remains controversial. To disentangle the features of Jewish mortality, in this paper we adopt a comprehensive approach. We compare the members of the Venetian Jewish community to a large sample of the Venetian population around mid-nineteenth century. The two groups shared the same environment and were socially similar. At that time, Jewish integration was well underway, and two thirds of the Venetian Jews dwelled outside the ancient Ghetto.

We combine longitudinal data drawn from the population registers with information on the causes of death, and use a competing-risk approach to carry out cause- and age-specific analyses. In this way, we highlight the different patterns of Jewish and Catholic mortality, and ask whether they concerned only levels or involved any major cause of death. This will contribute to a deeper understanding of the Jewish mortality conundrum.

A World of Difference? Religion, Neighbourhoods, and Infant Mortality in Mid-Nineteenth Century Amsterdam

Sanne Muurling

Radboud University Nijmegen, the Netherlands

Until the end of the nineteenth century the city of Amsterdam had been characterised by high, above national average infant mortality rates. As in other cities, this death toll was not distributed equally; overall, large differences can be observed between the poorer and more well-to-do neighborhoods. Surprisingly, a number of poor neighbourhoods experienced lower infant mortality rates than one might expect based on income levels. Neighbourhoods that were mainly Jewish stand out, but differences also arose between other religious denominations. Geographical isolation, differing lifestyles within communities, breast-feeding practices, and religious precepts are considered important possible explanations, but have proven difficult to particularize based on city-level mortality rates alone. Information about causes of death may provide additional clues, particularly in relation to feeding practices. This paper will therefore draw on the newly digitized registers of causes of death that provide micro-level data. By comparing disease categories (e.g. water- and foodborne diseases, airborne diseases, etc.) across various socioeconomically comparable (sub-) neighbourhoods in Amsterdam in 1856, it hopes to shed further light on the complex relationship between religion, social class, residential environment, and infant mortality.

Causes of death of Catholics and Jews in the city of Antwerp, 1928-1939

Isabelle Devos

Ghent University, Belgium

Many of the historical analyses of the relationship between religious affiliation and demographic behaviour have focused on Catholic and Jewish differentials, with most studies showing the highest mortality for Catholics and the lowest for Jews. Using data from the unique cause-of-death register of the city of Antwerp (1820-1946), recently collected via a large-scale citizen science project (www.sosantwerpen.be) we examine in this paper the main causes of death of Catholics and Jews. Although the register does not mention the religion of the deceased, religious affiliation can be detected for the years 1928-1939 from the place of burial and the funeral director. Taking into account the age and social composition of these populations, we examine which diseases were more frequent among Catholics and Jews, as such enabling us to get a better insight into the underlying determinants of the mortality differentials and the ways in which religion could influence health and mortality in the past.

Session 6B: Continuity, Convergence and Consensus Between Religion and the Mind Sciences

Timing: Thursday, 09/Sept/2021, 10:45am - 12:00pm

Chairs: Benoit Majerus and Valérie B. Leclercq (Université Libre de Bruxelles, Belgium)

The development of western medicine has traditionally been thought of as running parallel to the progress of secularization. In the last decades, however, historians have found and explored many places of continuity between religion and the modern medical domains. The mind sciences in particular have had to grapple with their pre-modern theological heritage, oftentimes prolonging it in new and ambiguous ways well into the 19th and 20th centuries. In this panel we would like to explore instances of continuity, convergence or consensus between religion and the mind sciences, particularly in the psychological and neurological discourses of the two last centuries.

Keywords: psychology, neurology, hallucination, Catholicism, time work

The Politics of Hallucinations in Mid-Nineteenth-century France

Enric Novella

University of Valencia, Spain

Since they were canonically described by Jean-Étienne-Dominique Esquirol, hallucinations became one of the distinctive, yet most controversial, symptoms of modern psychological medicine. Therefore, the central decades of the nineteenth century witnessed –particularly in France– numerous discussions related to their definition, their psychopathological understanding, and their semiological value that reflected not only clinical or theoretical questions –such as their relationship with sensorial images or their possible analogies with sleep or mystic states–, but also significant epistemological and ideological concerns. Some alienists, for example, did not hesitate to qualify as veritable hallucinations some of the ‘extraordinary’ experiences of great men such as Moses, Socrates or Pascal, outlining an alternative, rational and secular interpretation of these phenomena against the traditional narratives from religion or art. However, other authors strongly rejected these views, defended the compatibility of hallucinatory phenomena with the integrity of reason and even postulated the existence of so-called ‘physiological hallucinations’. This was the case of Alexandre Brierre de Boismont, who stood out for his indignation over attempts to retrospectively ‘diagnose’ outstanding figures of thought, literature and –above all– religion who had supposedly experienced hallucinations. In this presentation, I will try to summarize the central elements of this debate and reassess it within the background of the epistemological problems faced by early alienists when establishing the boundaries of insanity and normality at a psychological level, as well as in the context of the conflicts accompanying the deployment of the new gaze embodied by the concepts and categories of psychological medicine.

The Making and Unmaking of Magical Temporalities in English Primary Care

Rhodri Hayward

University of London, United Kingdom

Since the end of the nineteenth century, physicians confronted with anomalous phenomena have sought to make sense of them through the invocation of alternative temporalities. They engage in a kind of 'time work' attributing incongruous physical symptoms to different orders of time. At its most prosaic level, this time work takes place in the turn to psychosomatic explanations with aberrant physical changes being described as primitive responses to present day challenges. With the growing acceptance of the Cannon-Bard theory of emotion in the early decades of the twentieth century, individuals were seen as being caught between the current time of the central and somatic nervous systems and the primordial time of the autonomic.

Within medicine and the mind sciences, time work could be used to contest religious phenomena. From the beginning of the twentieth-century, prophetic visions and religious stigmata were often read, not as signs of a divine future, but as manifestations of subconscious history. Such histories, however, sometimes escaped mundane time. This paper will explore the work of the English general practitioner, Arthur Guirdham (1905-1992) who in the 1950s began to read his own symptoms, and those of his patients, as fragments of their previous incarnations as Cathar heretics facing the Inquisition in early thirteenth-century France. Guirdham's example allows us to think about the way the temporal rhetoric of medicine and the mind sciences can be used for making and unmaking supernatural claims.

What Religion Does to the Brain: Ideological Consensus and Negotiations in the Nineteenth-Century Belgian Sciences of the Mind

Valérie B. Leclercq

Université Libre de Bruxelles, Belgium

This paper will explore the views of catholic and liberal physicians who, in the mid-1870s, were engaged in two of the longest debates that ever took place at the Royal Academy of Medicine of Belgium in the nineteenth century. Both debates were concerned with issues of cerebral pathology and raised the question of religion and its impact on the human brain. Going beyond the seemingly clear-cut antagonism that separated liberal physicians and their catholic counterparts – the first condemning religion as a cause of brain disease, the latter seeing in Catholicism a possible means of mental prophylaxis –, this paper seeks to understand the deeper loci of ideological consensus on which both groups built their proto-neurological discourses. It will then question the link between such tacit form of consensus and the perceived ideological neutrality of nineteenth-century scientific spaces. For under the relentless discord that fuelled the debates laid a belief shared by most speakers that some form of religion was paramount to cerebral health. Another such collectively shared notion maintained that public mental health depended on the upholding of a social status-quo promoted at the time both by conservative Liberals and the Catholic Church. By looking at the complex ideological layering of these discourses, it is my ambition not only to deconstruct the political and religious biases that accompanied the medicalisation of mental acts such as thinking, feeling and practicing faith, but also to gain a better understanding of the process of secularisation of medicine in Catholic countries like Belgium.

Session 6C: The Role of Religious Institutions in Health Care: English and Belgian cases*

Timing: Thursday, 09/Sept/2021, 10:45am - 12:00pm

Chair: Dr. Joris Vandendriessche, KU Leuven, Belgium

Religious institutions were key players in health care. This panel wants to present innovative research about the role of male and female religious in the field of health care from different perspectives: missionary history, gender history and religious history. Two members will mainly pay attention to the Belgian case, while the third one will focus on English Catholic medical missions. The panel shall be moderated by dr. Joris Vandendriessche, post-doctoral researcher at KU Leuven.

Keywords: Catholic medical missions, female religious life, health care, nursing, Belgium

Educating Catholic Medical Missionaries in England (1920s-1950s)

Carmen Mangion

Birkbeck, University of London, United Kingdom

This paper examines the Catholic medical missions. The focus is on the education of medical missionary sisters of three English congregations. It charts the shifts in their medical education from the 1920s to the 1950s, hinging on the influential instructions *constans ac sedula* issued in 1936 by the Holy See which encouraged women religious to obtain medical and midwifery degrees for their work in the mission field.

This paper asks the following questions: How influential was this decree? How were sisters chosen to train as medical doctors and nurses? How did an extended period of education (as was needed for nursing/medical training) influence the novitiate experience? Where were they trained? How was the identity of a religious sister maintained in sometimes secular educational institutes?

Male and Female Religious Care and Health Care Provision in Belgium (19th-20th Century)

Kristien Suenens

KADOC-KU Leuven, Belgium

This paper intends to quantify the role of Belgian religious institutes that are active in health care institutions and organisations (hospitals, sanatoria, psychiatric hospitals, military hospitals, ambulant health care, child health care, ...) in relation to the specific research perspective of faith, health care and gender. Although the 'sister' in the hospital became a stereotype within Belgian society, the role of religious institutes was much more diverse and a significant part of it was played by religious men, and members of brother congregations in particular. However, within the Belgian context the care apostolate of both religious groups was never examined from a general, comparative gender perspective.

* This paper is competing in the Pieter van Foreest Student Prize.

Confronting both groups of religious care-givers, this contribution will focus on the following questions: What was the respective role of female and male religious institutes on the field of Belgian health care? Did their commitment differ in (religious and social) motives, actions and realisations? How did male and female religious translated their religious and gender roles on a field of intensive modernisation, professionalisation and (eventually) secularisation? To what extent differed or changed the relationships of both groups with secular authorities, board administrations and lay colleagues?

This research will be based upon an extensive study of existing monographies about male and female congregations active in health care, as well as complementary research in archives of religious institutes.

Sisters and Brothers of Charity and the Development in Health Care in Belgium (1908-1974)

Luc De Munck

KU Leuven, Belgium

This paper shall focus on the activities of two Belgian religious congregations, created in Ghent at the beginning of the 19th century. Both congregations played an important role in the development of health care institutions in Belgium. On the one hand, there are the Sisters of Charity. At the beginning of the 20th century, they were the first congregation to start with a mainly theoretical nursing education of one year. After the First World War, they created different hospitals and nursing schools. On the other hand, the Brothers of Charity focused from the beginning on health care for mentally ill persons and poor people. They started with the first school for psychiatric nursing shortly before the First World War.

The paper investigates how these congregations contributed to the development of health care in Belgium in the first three-quarters of the 20th century. Their policy documents and reviews shall be analysed. This analysis focuses on the following research questions: To what extent did both religious congregations play a significant role in Belgian health care? Which religious practices were dominant in their daily work? What was the discourse on health care in their reviews *Caritas* and *Ziekenverpleging* [Nursing Care]? What was the agency of leading members such as sister Jules-Marie Heymans, director of the first school for graduated nurses on the European continent, and brother Virgiel Van Petegem, author of the first manual for nursing brothers.

Session 6D: Reproductive Medicine and (Loss of) Faith

Timing: Thursday, 09/Sept/2021, 10:45am - 12:00pm

Chair: Dr. Anne Hanley, Birkbeck, University of London, United Kingdom

„The beginning of a human being at the moment of conception is not a question of personal beliefs, but a fact.” The relationship between faith/religion and medicine/science in the discourses on reproductive rights in Ireland and Poland

Michael Zok

German Historical Institute Warsaw, Poland

Recently, discourses on (female) reproductive rights are once again a main topic of widespread debates between politicians and parties as well as parts of debates in society. The current developments in the Republic of Ireland and Argentina resulting in a liberalisation of the legislation on the one hand and the demonstrations against a more restrictive interpretation of the law on abortion in Poland emblematised the observable differences. Despite the fact that all three countries (as well as others) are characterised by sociologists of religion as “mainly” or “homogeneously Catholic” and the (former) influential position of the Church on society, the juridical circumstances have changed enormously in recent years.

The paper will concentrate on the two European countries mentioned above and will analyse the discourses on (female) reproductive rights in the Republic of Ireland and Poland with special regard to the question of permissibility of abortions. Since the current legislations are the results of long-term developments and discussions, the paper will concentrate on the decades from the 1970s to the 1990s and show continuities and fractions.

As highlighted in the citation in the paper’s title, it were especially pro-life-activists who used scientific arguments to underline their position in these debates and to neglect that their doing was motivated (solely) by their religious beliefs. The paper will therefore analyse the discursive strategies of main actors involved in the debates in a broader context and pay special attention to the complicated relations between “science” and “religion/faith”.

Keywords: Reproductive Rights, Abortion, Poland, Ireland

Against the obscurantist views from the past. Introducing legal abortion to Czechoslovakia as a means of improving women’s health and their right to decide

Katerina Liskova

Masaryk University, Czech Republic

In the mid-1950s, abortion was almost uniformly legalized across the Eastern Bloc. Czechoslovakia was no exception, and the law of 1957 made it possible for women to terminate their pregnancies for ‘social’ reasons. In a country with relatively weak religious norms, proponents of the law still pressed against the ‘obscurantist views from the past’ and hailed abortion rights to improve reproductive health and grant women a crucial right and thus strengthen their emancipation.

Based on expert writings and archives of the ministry of health, I analyze the debates that preceded this law's introduction and follow the first years of its implementation. I trace the field of population expertise as it reemerged and consolidated in the second half of the 1950s around women's fertility. I highlight the crucial role medical doctors, demographers, and other experts played in shaping women's access to abortion, formulating and continually evaluating these policies' real-world impact. I show how a new symbolic framework for the socialist family – including the roles of women and men – was developed, alongside an institutional infrastructure designed to ensure the material preconditions to uphold it. On the case of abortion access, I also detail how this new socialist framework was eclipsed, as early as the beginning of the 1960s, by more traditional approaches to women and childbearing.

This paper fits the 'Technologies of human reproduction and religious norms' stream of the conference.

Keywords: abortion, socialism, emancipation, Czechoslovakia, expertise

'A post-Christian age in an increasingly Pagan society': The attitudes and influence of the Church of Scotland towards contraceptive access in post-"Sexual Revolution" Scotland, c. 1968 – 1974

Kristin Fairns Hay

University of Strathclyde, United Kingdom

In 1961, the first oral contraceptive drug arrived on the NHS. Heralded as 'virtually 100% effective', the pill was the first reliable, female-controlled contraceptive available in Britain. By 1964, 480,000 women were on the pill and oral contraceptives were established as a pivotal harbinger of the "Sexual Revolution" - during which attitudes towards sex, sexuality and chastity were forever eroded (Cook, 2004).

The Sexual Revolution was also exemplified by a notable decline in religious practices throughout the 1960s and 1970s in Britain, as the Church exerted a weakened influence on British society and culture (Brown, 2001). With the pill effectively separating sex from marriage and for the purposes of procreation - coupled with changes in divorce laws and the rise of unmarried co-habitation - the permissive changes that took place throughout the 1960s signified a move towards a more secularised society in Britain. However, in the context of mainland Britain, Scotland was among the most hostile towards universal access to birth control, and religion continued to play a significant role in shaping the discourse surrounding contraceptive use. This makes the Scottish experience distinctive within the broader historiography.

This paper will examine the attitudes and influence of the Church of Scotland towards contraceptive access in the post-Sexual Revolution period. Using oral history, coupled with archival research, this paper will outline how the Church responded to increasing access to the pill in the late-1960s, and the ways in which religious values continued to dictate and regulate Scottish morality and public health policy throughout the 1970s.

Keywords: contraception, sex, Scotland, twentieth century

Session 6E: Faith, Medicine and the Cold War

Timing: Thursday, 09/Sept/2021, 10:45am - 12:00pm

Chair: Prof. Heiner Fangerau, University of Düsseldorf, Germany

Faith in Older People: The Role of Mercy in Late Soviet Society

Susan Grant

Liverpool John Moores University, United Kingdom

When the Bolsheviks came to power in 1917 they were intent on banishing religion and placed the focus squarely on science. In the socialist world the two – religion and science – were considered wholly incompatible. But the binary between the two were not so clear cut. In this paper I focus on the late Soviet period to assess the links between religion and medicine in the context of ageing. Older people can act as a prism through which to view wider societal shifts. This is particularly the case when looking at the mercy or ‘miloserdiya’ movement in the late 1980s.

Although we might associate the late 1980s in the Soviet Union with the unravelling of Soviet power, faith, hope and belief in socialist values and in human kindness and compassion drove campaigns to help society’s older people. As those who had given so much to the socialist cause and made such great sacrifices during the Second World War, ordinary people mobilized to help the aged heroes. The rallying calls were ‘mercy’ and ‘care’. Providing older people with medicines, food, and clothing became the modus operandi of civil society’s quest to help old people. In this paper I trace the origins and actions of the ‘Mercy’ movement and what it tells us about Soviet society’s relationship with older people and belief systems more generally.

Keywords: older people, Soviet Union, faith, religion, medicine

Commemorative practices during the Cold War: Janusz Korczak’s presentation as a martyr in Eastern and Western Germany

Anne Oommen-Halbach

Heinrich-Heine-University Düsseldorf, Germany

Janusz Korczak (1878-1942) was a Polish-Jewish paediatrician and pedagogue, who became an emblematic representative of the fight for children’s rights and health. As a trained physician he took over the leadership of an orphanage in Warsaw, which has been described recently as an “educational clinic”, pointing out Korczak’s closeness to pedagogy and childhood research respectively (Schierbaum 2018). Korczak was killed by the Nazis in 1942, when he accompanied more than 200 Jewish orphans to their death at the Treblinka extermination camp.

The memory of Korczak was widely dominated by the depiction of the end of his life and his presentation as a martyr. It has substantially been shaped by national Korczak memory societies, which existed since the end of the 1970s in East and West Germany against different political backgrounds.

Based on two separate archival holdings of partial estates of both organisations (Karl Dedecius Archive, Stubice, Poland/ Korczak Collection, Düsseldorf, Germany) this paper examines to what extent a religious or political appropriation of Korczak can be determined in the memory in culture in both German states in the context of the debate on guilt, historical responsibility and the Holocaust.

Eastern and western commemorations of Korczak's life, death and work introduced the metaphor of martyrdom in order to give sense to his brutal death. Obviously, this framing of remembrance connected Korczak to religious images well known to the Christian communities in Germany, which is especially remarkable for East Germany, where religion was banned by the state at that time.

Keywords: religious metaphor, martyr, Janusz Korczak, memory societies, Cold War

Bless the Abstinent. Global Catholicism and Asia's Cold War Population Bomb

Wannes Dupont

Yale-NUS College, Singapore

In the wake of World War 2, the newly created United Nations (correctly) projected a doubling of the global population by 1990. This massive population boom would be heavily concentrated in the developing nations of coastal Asia. Fearing that widespread famine and overpopulation would hamper development and drive the region into the arms of communism, the West proposed active programmes of birth and population control. The most formidable resistance to such programmes was organised by the Roman Catholic Church, which successfully stalled them at the level of the UN and WHO throughout the 1950s. After the Catholic dam burst in the 1960s, the Church would nevertheless remain the world's most ardent and ineluctable opponent of population control. Even so, we remain extremely poorly informed about how this Catholic resistance was organised.

This paper examines this resistance in two ways: first, by zooming in on Church lobbying at the global level of the United Nations, and second, by exploring how its opposition was organised at the national and regional level in the Asian countries who were the primary focus of population politics, including India, Malaya/Malaysia/Singapore, Indonesia, the Philippines, Japan and China. Catholic physicians and medical scientists played a key role in this process. I argue that the encyclical *Humanae Vitae* of 1968 was to a large extent, perhaps even primarily so, a response to global health and population control efforts.

Keywords: Catholicism, Global South, birth control, United Nations, Asia

Lunch Session 2A: Presentation of a Game

Timing: Thursday, 09/Sept/2021, 12:00pm - 12:45pm

The Ocean - A Historical Wargame set in a Red Cross Hospital during WWI

Jelle Janssens

The Ocean is a historical wargame based on real events.

The game takes place during WOI in L'Océan, The Queens Hospital. At the end of 1914, Queen Elisabeth turned a former luxurious hotel into the biggest Red Cross hospital in Belgian History.

Through hypnosis, the player enters the mind of Christina, a voluntary nurse who served in L'Océan from 1914 until 1919! and is tasked to heal her traumas. The game questions faith in humanity and the progress of healthcare during this violent conflict.

It encourages players to think about the role of caretakers in society, sacrifice, and female heroism.

Keywords: Game, World War One, L'Océan, Nurses, Red Cross

Lunch Session 2B: Roundtable

Timing: Thursday, 09/Sept/2021, 12:00pm - 12:45pm

Chairs: Marc M Dooms (UZ Leuven, Belgium), Luc Verpoest (KU Leuven, Belgium)

Religious medical heritage in Leuven

Raymond Kenis¹, Rene Thewissen¹, Bruno Mortelmans²

¹*Leuvens Historisch Genootschap, Belgium*; ²*BMedicalPresentations*

The Catholic University of Leuven (KU Leuven) was founded almost 600 years ago (1425) and left religious medical heritage in the city of Leuven, the medical faculty being one of the first schools. Some buildings are recently demolished (chapel of the nursing school at Capucijnenvoer), some are in bad condition (anatomical theater at the corner of the Capucijnenvoer - Minderbroederstraat), some are awaiting restoration (anatomical theater & medical auditoria at Minderbroedestraat) and some are well preserved (Romaanse Poort at Brusselsestraat).

Besides this real estate heritage, a rich collection of medical objects is spread all over the city: written documents in the central library of the university at Ladeuzeplein (Andreas Vesalius), paintings at the Museum M & the Saint Peters church (Dirk Bouts) and a vast collection of medical objects at HistArUz museum (actually closed) including a large collection of dentistry and pharmacy.

Because a visit to the localities in group is not possible at the moment, a round table will be organized during the meeting where images will be shown of the demolished chapel (historical lead in glass) to enhance a discussion about the conservation/restoration of religious medical heritage.

Keywords: Medical objects, books, paintings, conservation, restauration

Lunch Session 2C: Roundtable

Timing: Thursday, 09/Sept/2021, 12:00pm - 12:45pm

Chair: Agata Ignaciuk (University of Warsaw, Poland; University of Granada, Spain)

Does religion matter for histories of reproduction in post-war Europe? (cases France, Germany and the Nordic Countries)

Fabrice Cahen¹, Christina Benninghaus², Hanna Kuusi³

¹Ined France; ²University of Oxford, United Kingdom; ³University of Helsinki, Finland

Histories of assisted reproduction and Christian religions have highlighted tensions and conflicts, proscriptions and prescriptions (e.g. Sèvegrand 1995; McDonnell and Allison 2006; Man Wall 2010; Radkowska-Walkowicz 2018). Regarding artificial insemination, especially the Roman Catholic Church has been described as a conservative force, as Pope Leo XIII had decreed artificial insemination to be illicit as early as in 1897. In the words of Nick Hopwood, this decision was a 'milestone in articulating a Catholic discourse that engaged with interventions in reproduction earlier and more uncompromisingly than other religions' (Hopwood 2018, p. 583). Yet research has also drawn attention to opposition against artificial insemination within other Christian religions, most notably Anglicanism and other Protestant traditions (Davis 2013; 2017; Richards 2014).

In the history of medicine more broadly, recent histories have reassessed these widespread storylines of conflict: drawing attention to entanglements and cross-overs (Pia Donato 2013), questioning common associations between 'religion' and 'conservatism' (Horn 2015; Chappel 2018), and revealing substantive gaps between official church teachings and the discourses and practices of those who considered themselves to be faithful (Woodcock Tentler 2004; Harris 2018; Kelly and Ignaciuk 2020). To sum up, historians have begun to clear up popular and scholarly misconceptions about the homogeneity and stability of religious opinions concerning medical developments. However, this more nuanced approach until today remains largely confined to medical histories of contraception. Religious debates on assisted reproduction have received far less attention (Betta 2017), even though there is an equally important story to be told.

Aiming to showcase new empirical research in the history of medicine and reproduction, this roundtable will focus on artificial insemination with donor sperm (AID). From the 1940s to the 1970s, AID became a reliable if controversial reproductive procedure, resulting in the birth of thousands of children. In this roundtable, three panellists will discuss the diverging developments of this controversial technology in Europe, looking at France, Germany, and the Nordic Countries. The panellists are currently collaborating on a special issue on the post-war history of artificial insemination, and grasp this conference as an opportunity to reflect about the role of religion, from religious authorities to individual believers.

In this light, the roundtable will address the following contested questions:

- 1) Did religion matter in the post-war histories of AID? If so, how and to what extent did religion influence the development of and discourses around AID across the aforementioned national contexts?
- 2) How did religion interact with other medico-moral arguments about AID? What was the role of doctors, theologians, legal regulators and patients in these processes?

3) How did historical shifts in the importance of religion over the decades impact on reproductive policies in various national contexts?

4) Which other explanations need to be considered to explain differences and similarities between different national contexts?

By comparing how religion played out in various national contexts, the panellists not only shed new light on the history of AID in post-war Europe, but also reassess widespread deterministic accounts of modernity, secularisation, and sexual reform.

Keywords: Assisted Reproduction, Comparative History, Artificial Insemination

Session 7A: Religious Differentials in Causes of Death, 1850-1940. Part II

Timing: Thursday, 09/Sept/2021, 1:30pm - 2:45pm

Chair: Isabelle Devos, Ghent University, Belgium

Historical analyses of the relationship between religious affiliation and demographic behavior have focused on Catholic, Protestant and Jewish differentials, with most studies showing the highest mortality for Catholics. Explanations for the differences have been wide-ranging, pointing to specific religious values, attitudes and/or life styles. Definitive answers remain elusive. In two sessions we present studies from the SHiP network. The network focuses on port cities with individual-level cause-of-death data for the period 1850-1950, supplemented by data for specific subpopulations such as hospital patients. Information on the causes of death of these population groups can clarify how religion affects health.

Keywords: Religion, causes of death, demography

Diseases and Divinity: Investigating Religious Differences in Health of Patients in the Binnengasthuis in Amsterdam, 1856-1896

Nadeche Diepgrond¹, [Tim Riswick](#)¹

¹*Radboud University Nijmegen, the Netherlands*

Hospitals played a central role in the nineteenth century as these institutions were so-called gateways to death or places of healing. In this paper, we will make use of an unique combination of sources to investigate differences in religious affiliation of the patients in one of Amsterdam's largest hospitals in the nineteenth century. Our study is based on the patient registers of the Binnengasthuis in Amsterdam, which record the demographic profile of the patients, the duration of their stay, information about their diseases, and if they died. There was no selection in admission based on religious affiliation. In total we are able to analyze 13.250 patients who were admitted to the hospital in the years 1856, 1876 and 1896. By using these patient registers we can ask whether certain conditions were more frequently treated in hospitals and whether the social, demographic and religious profile of those being admitted to the hospital differs. In addition, we are able to link the majority of patients who died to their specific cause of death by using the Amsterdam causes of death database. This enables us to ask questions about similarities and differences in causes of death patterns between religious groups admitted to the hospital. Furthermore, by studying three specific years, we are also able to investigate changes over time. Answering these questions is crucial to gain more understanding into the role played by religion in the history of European hospitals, and their patients, during the period known as the 'medicalization' of hospitals.

Religious differences in cause-specific infant mortality in northern Sweden, 1860-1900

Johan Junkka¹, Maria Hiltonen¹

¹*Centre for Demographic and Ageing Research, Umeå University, Sweden*

Infant mortality rates in Europe declined rapidly during the 19th century. However, not all religious groups benefited equally from this development. Religious affiliation has been shown to affect infant survival, and little is known why some religious groups had lower infant mortality than others. We investigate the relationship between religious affiliation and cause-specific infant mortality. We use longitudinal parish register data from northern Sweden covering the period 1860-1900, identifying affiliation to a free church or the state church on a family level. Data on death records are coded using the SHiP historical cause-of-death coding system which is based on the ICD-10 coding system. The SHiP system allows for systematic and comparative analyses of historical causes of death while retaining information from historical designations. Using cause-specific mortality, we can estimate and compare infant mortality risks due to different diseases and causes, such as water- and food-borne diseases. Thus, providing a better understanding of the mechanisms causing religious inequalities in infant mortality during the demographic transition.

Faith in a Time of Cholera in the Dutch Town of Woerden, 1866

Evelien Walhout¹, Erik Beekink²

¹*Leiden University, the Netherlands*; ²*Radboud University Nijmegen, the Netherlands*

In 1866, the Netherlands experienced its third major cholera epidemic. The impact of cholera in nineteenth-century Dutch towns is almost impossible to grasp: it appeared suddenly and then ravaged through the city streets leaving behind victims suffering from diarrhoea and dehydration while killing most of its victims. In many towns, the municipal authorities kept track of their casualties by meticulously registering when people fell ill, when they recovered or when they died. In the small town of Woerden (located near Utrecht), these cholera-registrations included name, age, address and occupation. For May-September 1866, when cholera hit Woerden, we do know exactly who fell victim to the epidemic. Additional data on household composition, marital status and religious denomination can be derived from the digitalized population registers. Finally, it is possible to study how the municipal and religious authorities acted during this crisis in terms of financial support: who was entitled to support and from which institution? The link between religion and health is not easy to explain and includes various aspects to consider: from specific teachings, values and practices that promote or discourage patterns of behaviour to the characteristics of religious groups (residential pattern, social class, isolation, support system). Did religion play a role in the survival and support of cholera patients in 1866 Woerden? Woerden covered a multitude of faiths and beliefs: circa 60% Protestants, 35% Roman-Catholics and 5% Jews.

Session 7B: Missionary and Colonial Medical Practices

Timing: Thursday, 09/Sept/2021, 1:30pm - 2:45pm

Chair: Dr. Tinne Claes, KU Leuven, Belgium

Therapeutic pluralism and the history of colonial psychiatry in British mandate Palestine

Chris Sandal-Wilson

University of East Anglia, United Kingdom

Across the British mandate period (1920s-1940s), government as well as private mental hospitals proliferated across Palestine, and ever increasing numbers of Palestinians – Muslim, Christian, and Jewish – sought admission for relatives they deemed mentally ill. At the time as well as often since, the arrival of British colonialism is taken as marking a sharp rupture, as responsibility for the treatment of the mentally ill shifted out of the hands of men of religion and into the hands of men of science. This narrative not only ignores a longer history of medicalisation under the late Ottoman empire, but – as this paper argues – the coexistence of medical and religious modes of treatment well into the interwar period in Palestine. Drawing on both archival sources and the ethnographic writings of Palestinian and European folklorists, this paper argues that rather than seeing religious and medical modes of treatment as competing and mutually exclusive, many Palestinians across this period shopped around, turning to one when the other failed. This was an eminently rational strategy on their part, given that the inadequate bedstrength of government mental hospitals and the cost of admission to private institutions rendered them off-limits to many in this period.

Keywords: Psychiatry, Mental Illness, Palestine, Colonialism, British empire

Missionary health care as an example of the entanglement between medicine and spirituality in German New Guinea (1884-1919)*

Magdalena Martha-Marie Kittelmann

University of Erlangen-Nuremberg, Germany

The German colonial period in Papua New Guinea (1884-1919) is very suitable for reflecting on entanglements between medicine and religion.

In 1886, the first Lutheran missionaries (Neuendettelsau Missionary Society) arrived at Finschhafen in Kaiser-Wilhelmsland (today Morobe Province). Missionary societies played an important role in colonial health care as they were often responsible for establishing medical infrastructure among indigenous communities. But even though being part of a Western medical system, missionaries did not act as secularised healers. Instead they often used medical care for missionary purposes: the use of Western medication and medical treatment was instrumentalised for proselytisation.

In indigenous cultures as well as in missionary perception, medical topics such as illness and healing were closely connected to a spiritual context – a fact that enabled religious dialogue and spiritual exchange between missionaries and local communities. This paper analyses the medical work carried

* This paper is competing in the Pieter van Foreest Student Prize.

out by missionaries amongst indigenous people. I question the interconnectedness between the use of Western medication and spirituality in the frame of missionary medical work. Certain diseases could not be treated by potent medication therefore the only treatment remaining was praying. To what extent can we even find similarities between the missionary approach to healing and traditional belief?

Based on literature review and source research in the frame of my doctoral thesis in medical history, my contribution to the conference refers to the medical work implemented by the Neuendettelsau Missionary Society and its spiritual implications on indigenous communities in the space of time from 1886 to 1919.

Keywords: Papua New Guinea, mission history, medical mission, medicine and spirituality, Lutheran mission

Session 7C: Medical Objects: Faith and Healing

Timing: Thursday, 09/Sept/2021, 1:30pm - 2:45pm

Chair: Dr. Joris Vandendriessche, KU Leuven, Belgium

Faith, Hope and Fear

Sarah Bond

Science Museum Group, United Kingdom

Faith, Hope and Fear is one of five new permanent galleries dedicated to the history and practice of medicine at the Science Museum in London. Medicine: The Wellcome Galleries opened in November 2019 and are billed as the world's largest of their type, occupying much of the first floor of the Museum. Drawing on key objects and stories in the collections, they explore measures conceived to prevent and treat disease at the scale of individuals and populations, and reveal how studying the body and its functions transformed medicine from 1500 onwards.

Located at the far end of the suite, Faith, Hope and Fear acts as a kind of coda, providing space for reflection on the emotional impact of illness and the pluralistic approach many people employ to manage the unpredictability of treatment and recovery. It showcases objects invested with powerful feelings and beliefs triggered by confrontations with ill health and mortality, ranging from mass displays of religious material culture to standalone exhibits donated by individuals who have placed their trust in medical practitioners, treatments and relationships, instead of (or as well as) spiritual forces.

This paper considers how faith and religion have been presented in previous permanent and temporary displays of the Science Museum's medical collections, and contrasts these with the approach taken in the new galleries. It examines the particular challenges of tackling the 'F-word' in a museum of science and technology, and reflects on some of the strategies adopted, including the use of person-centred narratives and commissioned artworks.

Keywords: permanent galleries, faith, emotion, uncertainty, personal narratives

The “pharmacy in your head”: The role of faith and belief in the process of healing with “devotional pictures for swallowing”

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Small pieces of paper with a sacred image, intended to be swallowed, and therefore attributed to have a beneficial effect – like the obstetric note of Saint Luke (Lukaszettel) – belong to the category of Schluckbildchen (“swallowable pictures”). They were used as religious practice in folk medicine throughout the 18th to the 20th century for preventive and curative measures. The efficacy consisted mainly of believing in its effect. The “healing power of faith” is also important in nowadays conventional medicine, especially regarding the placebo effect. The physician William Cullen (1710-1790) made it a medical terminus technicus; so later, for example, the psychosocial context in which the treatment of a patient takes place was identified as an important factor in this regard by

neurobiologist Fabrizio Benedetti (*1956). The belief in the physician's word – the hope for improvement or healing – initiates the same effects in the brain as a "real chemical" therapy. These remarks show that faith and belief are rooted in the context of medicine – both in the past and in the present.

This lecture aims to analyze the role of faith and belief in the healing process, using the example of Schluckbildchen. For this purpose, the obstetric Lukaszettel, the Schluckbildchen of John the Baptist (epilepsy) and the Schluckbildchen of the Virgin Mary (various diseases) – archived in ethnographic museums – will be examined. The multisensory experience associated with the incorporation of Schluckbildchen offers a reflection on the mechanism of action of nowadays placebo. Contributions from the field of neurobiology are used for this purpose.

Keywords: Faith, belief, Placebo, Medicine, Traditional

Mystical wax sculptures: faith in the bowels of mercy of Jesus Christ between the Middle Ages and the modern age

Teodoro De Giorgio

Italian Institute of Human Sciences, Italy

In the second half of the seventeenth century, a particular type of wax crucifix emerged, which was characterized by an opening on the sternum showing part of the Saviour's thoracic and abdominal cavity, with the anatomical representation of the inner organs. Through the examination of surviving examples and recourse to scriptural, patristic, and other literary sources, this paper analyzes the origin and the meaning – theological, symbolic, and iconological – of this invention, demonstrating its connection to the anatomical studies and to the devotion of the Sacred Heart of Christ, propagated especially by the Jesuits, and its intent to represent the divine mercy of Christ. As a matter of fact, the rather summary representation of the internal organs shows that the aim of these objects was not scientific precision, but a symbolic representation, with strong healing power for the body and spirit of the faithful. Both the style of the existing examples and their geographical distribution suggests that Southern Italy, especially Sicily, was the main area of production. The speech starts from the researches conducted by the author and recently published in the «Mitteilungen des Kunsthistorischen Institutes in Florenz», Max-Planck-Institut ("L'invenzione dell'iconografia In visceribus Christi. Dai prodromi medievali della devozione cordicolare alla rappresentazione moderna delle viscere di Cristo", LXI, 2019, 1, pp. 74-103).

Keywords: Wax sculptures, bowels of Christ, divine mercy, mysticism, faith

Session 7D: Faith in/and Psychiatry

Timing: Thursday, 09/Sept/2021, 1:30pm - 2:45pm

Chair: Prof. Heiner Fangerau, University of Düsseldorf, Germany

How We Should Live – Christianity in Finnish Psychosomatic Medicine, c. 1945–1960*

Eve-Riina Hyrkäs

University of Oulu, Finland

The presentation discusses the relationship between Christian faith and medicine through an intellectual biography of single historical agent, the Finnish theologian-psychiatrist Asser Stenbäck (1913–2006). Stenbäck was a prominent figure not only in Finnish psychiatry, but also in Nordic psychiatric cooperation and internationally recognised for his work in gerontology. Most importantly, in the latter half of the twentieth century, Stenbäck developed an original understanding of psychosomatic medicine, which addressed the tensions between Lutheran Christianity, medicine, and health. Stenbäck argued that psychosomatic health could not be achieved without abiding to the ethical guidelines listed in Ten Commandments. The influence of breaking this eternal moral code transferred from the spirit into the soul through moral sentiments, such as guilt and anxiety. Stenbäck's deep Christian conviction was combined with a rigorous take on stress theory, showing how the mind influenced the body through physiological pathways. The presentation acts as a commentary on the morality entailed in psychosomatics, as Stenbäck's argumentation aspired to preserve the idea of 'embodied sin' in the secular age of medicine. I also wish to bring attention to the difference between dogmatic and affective dimensions of religion. Stenbäck's approach emphasised the norms entailed in Christianity rather than the healing powers of faith itself. In this respect, the case study enriches the existing historiography on religiously influenced psychosomatics.

Keywords: psychosomatic medicine, mind-body, religion, ethics, Finland

'The Magic Years?': Faith in American Psychiatry during the Post-War Period

Matthew Smith

University of Strathclyde, United Kingdom

In the American Psychiatric Association (APA) archives, lies a dusty old box with a fascinating secret. In it is an unfinished manuscript written by psychiatrist and APA medical director Daniel Blain (1898-1981) called 'The Magic Years: The History of Psychiatry, Mental Health and Mental Retardation, 1945-1970'. As its title suggests, 'The Magic Years' cast post-war psychiatry in a warm, rosy glow, describing how psychiatry had moved ahead unprecedentedly, with psychiatric knowledge advancing, better treatments, old, crumbling asylums being replaced by community mental health care centres, and increased public and political awareness of mental illness growing, leading to the foundation of the National Institute of Mental Health and legislation such as the Community Mental Health Act. Most encouraging were research collaborations between social scientists and psychiatrists that promised to elucidate environmental causes of mental illness, resulting in preventive psychiatry. For a medical

* This paper is competing in the Pieter van Foreest Student Prize.

discipline that had long been viewed as being not particularly scientific, authoritative, or even respectable, this faith in psychiatry's ability to transform American psychiatry was both refreshing and empowering.

In the decades since, however, historians and psychiatrists have typically portrayed post-war American psychiatry in much more negative terms, describing it as overly idealistic and impractical. Many of these interpretations have pointed to what happened in more recent decades, rather than analysing what psychiatry had hoped to achieve in the years following WWII. In this presentation, I revisit 'The Magic Years', suggesting that we may want to reconsider the preventive, holistic, and interdisciplinary approach to mental health espoused then today.

Keywords: psychiatry, mental health, United States, faith

'We believe in medicine, we believe in science'. Unpacking 'belief' at the intersection of psychiatric nursing and religious healing in rural southwestern Ghana

Cecilia Draicchio

Sapienza University of Rome, Italy

Drawing on my ethnographic fieldwork in the Western Region of Ghana on the articulations between psychiatry and religious healing in dealing with madness and mental suffering, the paper is aimed at discussing the theoretical role that the ambiguous concept of 'belief' may have in understanding such articulations. Both in medical anthropology and the anthropology of religion, eminent scholars have warned us against its use, highlighting the many limits that the concept of 'belief' entails (Good 2008; Meyer and Houtman 2013). Nevertheless, the term has been a keyword in the history of anthropology and continues to be used, sometimes uncritically, in formal and informal ethnographic accounts, as well as in everyday discussions. In conversations about mental healthcare in Ghana, 'belief' is often used in the third person and evoked by institutions and biomedical practitioners as the main obstacle for 'mentally ill' people to get proper care. In the same context, however, the idea of 'believing in something' can often be used also with its original meaning of 'pledging allegiance to' (Good 2008; cf. Smith 1977) and be equally used to talk about spirits, God, and - interestingly - science. Paradoxically, in both uses the term always conveys also its opposite: doubt (cf. Luhrmann 2012; Boyer 2013).

It is precisely the doubleness of the concept of 'belief' and, even most importantly, its constitutive relationship with doubt that could prove surprisingly illuminating in order to understand how people (patients, relatives, practitioners) navigate different therapeutic resources and meanings during healing processes in Ghana (and beyond).

Keywords: Ghana, psychiatry, religious healing, belief, doubt

Session 8A: Roundtable

Timing: Thursday, 09/Sept/2021, 3:15pm - 4:30pm

Chair: Jacalyn Duffin (History of Medicine, Queen's University, Kingston, Canada)

Modern Medicine and Catholicism: Historiographical Challenges

Emmanuel Betta¹, Barbra M. Wall², Isabelle Devos³, Tine Van Osselaer⁴, Kaat Wils⁵

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Over the last two decades, the topic of Western biomedicine and religion has gained firm ground among medical, social and cultural historians. They started to shape a field that in an earlier stage seemed above all of interest to scholars in religious studies or in other domains within the health humanities. The first systematic historical overview of the question, published in 1986 and republished in 1998, *Caring and Curing: Health and Medicine in the Western Religious Traditions* was emblematic of this tendency in which a religious perspective dominated. This changed in the decades afterwards. Historians started to approach the topic more critically, aiming to take distance from both confessional approaches and interpretations of the past that were implicitly informed by a 'conflict' narrative – a narrative which assumed an incompatibility between modern biomedicine and religion, and whose power might explain why it took so long for medical historiography to integrate religion in its own right into its research questions. New attempts at systematic overviews, such as Gary Ferngren's *Medicine and Religion: A Historical Introduction* (2013) were sided by edited volumes such as *Medicine and Religion in Enlightenment Europe* (2007), by Ole Peter Grell and Andrew Cunningham, and *Médecine et Religion. Compétitions, Collaborations, Conflits* (2013) by Maria Pia Donato and colleagues. This historiography is certainly not blind to the many instances of conflict or tension between medical and religious practices or beliefs, but it also sheds light on phenomena of separate coexistence and on examples of mutual influence and collaboration.

In this roundtable, we aim to discuss the state of the art and the future agenda of the historiography of Catholicism and biomedicine in Europe and the United States. As Catholicism epitomizes the 'backward' character of religion within a popular narrative of conflict, it constitutes an interesting case to assess the state and the needs of historical research on the question. Attention will be paid to the themes of conflict, coexistence and collaboration, with specific interest in the role of tradition and adaptation. While tradition indeed plays a central role within the Catholic church, for instance within moral theology, which grounds Catholic medical ethics, overestimating its impact runs the risk of de-historicizing Catholicism, as if its positions haven't changed over time. The same goes for the centralized and hierarchically organized character of the Catholic church. Historians have to take this distinguishing feature into account, but it shouldn't make them blind for the many ways in which national and local churches and Catholics adapted to different political, social and cultural circumstances. Differences between center and periphery and majority and minority churches indeed account for very different historical positions of Catholics and their relationship with modern medicine. This also raises the question to what degree we can strive for a unified history of biomedicine and Catholicism and what challenges are part of such an endeavor.

Keywords: Historiography, Modern Medicine, Catholicism

Session 8B: International Scientific Research stays to fight against Infectious Diseases: Faith in Vaccines and Vaccination

Timing: Thursday, 09/Sept/2021, 3:15pm - 4:30pm

Chairs: María-Isabel Porrás-Gallo, Marta Velasco, University of Castilla-La Mancha, Spain

When medicine became the new religion in the 19th century, medical knowledge and practice for curing and preventing infectious diseases acquired new value, particularly after the triumph of bacteriology. Vaccines were exalted as the right way to fight against epidemics like the influenza of 1918-1919 and poliomyelitis during the 20th century: the panel analyses the cases of Spain, Argentina, France, and Italy. At the same time, vaccine preparation and production were linked to faith in Western biomedical research which, as the panel shows, depended on interchange of knowledge between countries and thus on circulation of scientists through research stays.

Keywords: history of influenza and poliomyelitis vaccines, scientific research stays, Italy, France, Argentina

Polio control strategies and policies in France (1955-1968)

María-Victoria Caballero¹, Baptiste Baylac-Paouly², María-Isabel Porrás¹

¹*University of Castilla-La Mancha, Spain;* ²*University of Lyon, France*

At the beginning of the 20th century, polio became more visible, spreading over the Old and New Continent. The incidence of the disease gradually increased throughout the century to become critical after the Second World War. The two main polio vaccines were developed in the USA and allowed progressive control of the disease, or even its virtual eradication, in America or Europe.

While the history of polio control in the United States or in several European countries is overwhelmingly well-documented, very few studies have focused on the case of France, where Pierre Lépine developed an inactivated virus vaccine, quite similar to the Salk vaccine.

This communication deals with polio control strategies and policies implemented by France from 1955 until 1968. We focus on the role played by foreign research stays of main French scientists involved in the process and on one actor, the Institut Mérieux of Lyon, which was one of the two producers of polio vaccines in France with the Institut Pasteur. We'll seek to understand how this actor mobilised the health community around polio; who were the other actors involved and which was the role played by foreign research stays of Pierre Lépine in the development of his inactivated virus vaccine; what interests Institut Mérieux could derive from this business; whether political, economic, or even socio-cultural determinants have had an influence in the fight against the disease; and ultimately if the actions of Institut Mérieux had a real impact on polio control strategies and policies in France.

“Dear Albert, Caro Augusto”: notes on the introduction of Sabin vaccine in Italy

Maria Teresa Brancaccio

University of Maastricht, the Netherlands

The introduction of the Sabin’s oral polio vaccine (OPV) in Italy was a lengthy and complex process that pitted a group of renowned academic virologists and a pharmaceutical company against the Ministry of Health. The paper makes use of the correspondence between Albert Sabin and some Italian scientists, in particular Augusto Giovanardi, and of other primary sources to shed light on the scientific and political contingencies that framed the process of polio vaccine innovation in Italy between the second half of the 1950s and the early 1960s. The paper deals especially with aspects of this process that have so far been overlooked, namely the emergence and development of an informal international cooperation between Albert Sabin’s laboratory in Cincinnati and a group of scientists working in Italian public and private laboratories, the political and economic contingencies that led the Ministry of Health to obstacle experimentation with and production of OPV in Italy, and the political changes that led to introduction of OPV in anti-polio vaccination campaign in 1964.

The Argentinian Bacteriological Institute and the vaccine against Spanish influenza. Initiatives in the peripheries of science (1918-1919)

Adrián Carbonetti

National University of Córdoba, Argentina

Between the late nineteenth century and the beginning of the twentieth the governing élite of Argentina undertook a process to encourage scientific activity by the creation of institutes dedicated to research, and by the hiring of foreign scientists, particularly from Europe. Among these institutions was the creation, in the early twentieth century, of the Bacteriological Institute, a body dedicated to research into infectious diseases and the preparation of treatments to cure or prevent them. The Director of the Institute, not long after its inception, was Rudolf Kraus, a physician from Bohemia who had studied at the Pasteur Institute and the Hamburg Institute for Maritime and Tropical Diseases. When the Spanish flu reached Argentina the country’s physicians and scientists set to work to find a way to prevent or cure the disease. The team headed by Kraus to prepare a vaccine and a serum to fight the disease based its work on a considerable number of etiological studies that had been carried out in the main countries of western science (USA, France, Great Britain, Spain). From these studies, investigations were carried out enabling the development of a serum and a vaccine. Our presentation aims to analyse the links and networks generated, especially by Kraus and Penna, with European and American scientists; the incorporation of the knowledge that reached Argentina; and the procedures that they brought about. The study will be carried out through analysis of state documentation, articles by doctors who studied the disease and methods of treatment, and the press.

Session 8C: Hospitals, Medical Practices and the Church

Timing: Thursday, 09/Sept/2021, 3:15pm - 4:30pm

Chair: Prof. Javier Moscoso, CSIC, Spain

The Church's move into a secular field: the fight by the Minim Congregation of Poor Brothers for control of Todos os Santos Hospital, Lisbon (1594–1632)

Laurinda Abreu

University of Évora, Portugal

Hospitals in Portugal had, since the Middle Ages, been administered by civil society, except for a few established by the religious orders for their own use and the military hospitals founded in the seventeenth century which were run by the Order of Saint John of God. After a national reform of hospitals, the Portuguese crown began in the early sixteenth century to transfer them to the misericórdias, lay confraternities enjoying royal protection, a process almost completed by the time of the Iberian Union under the Habsburg crown in 1580. In that same decade, Castille started its own hospital reform, in which a prominent part was played by Bernardino Obregón, the founder of the Minim Congregation of Poor Brothers, better known in Portugal as the Obregões. In 1594, Philip II of Spain (I of Portugal) sent the Obregões into Portugal's principal hospital, Todos os Santos – managed since 1564 by the powerful Lisbon Misericórdia –with the task of reorganising it and then doing the same in city hospitals around the country. However, the project was stalled by the Misericórdia, which entangled the Obregões in a web of intrigue and eventually had them expelled from Todos os Santos. The full extent of this protracted conflict between secular and religious powers is yet to be researched. This communication examines these issues by comparing Bernardino Obregón's biographies with documents from the hospital and also scrutinising the effects of the struggle on the hospital's operations.

Keywords: hospital control, hospitals control; religious orders, Lisbon misericórdia confraternity, Portugal

"Persuasive Rhetoric and the Orientation of Responses to Medical Practices: the Role of the Established Church in Elizabethan and Early Stuart England"

Paola Baseotto

Insubria University, Italy

Widely circulated medical books like Thomas Cogan's 1636 Haven of Health often remind people that "the Lord hath created medicines, and he that is wise will not abhorre them" and reiterate the view that: "it is lawful for Christians to use physicke as the gift of God in all diseases". Queen Elizabeth's and King James's public orders warned: "if there be any person that shall hold and publish any opinion that it is a vain thing to take medicaments pretending that no person shall die but at their time prefixed, such persons if they bee Ecclesiasticall shall be forbidden to preach, and being lay, shall not utter such dangerous opinions upon pain of imprisonment"

Documents such as these point to tensions in the experience of disease in early modern England. Prominent religious guides often endorsed competing discourses regarding illness and medicine. Especially on the occasion of major epidemics, influential preachers belonging to nonconformist communities promoted resistance to medical treatments and public orders, while the Church of England endorsed Privy Council's measures of crowd control and quarantine of the diseased, and encouraged acceptance of medical remedies. My analysis of devotional writings, sermons and Church orders documents the role of the national Church in promoting compliance with medical and government strategies of containment of epidemics.

Keywords: Early modern medicine, Church of England, Nonconformists, Rhetorical strategies, Popular responses to medical practices

Icons of Charity: Saints and Hospital Care in Medieval Central Europe

Lucy Christine Barnhouse

Arkansas State University, United States of America

The spread of hospitals in medieval Europe occurred at the same time as the rise of a number of saints' cults for men and women, recently deceased, often laypersons, whose service of the sick was a key signifier of their holiness. Recent scholarship has called for more critical examination of how the examples of saints pursuing hospital work might have inspired staff and donors alike. This paper examines how images of saints, dedications to them, and the circulation of texts about their lives, constituted part of the landscape of charity in late medieval Central Europe. Mainz, a hub of both religious power and economic exchange, developed a religious and civic topography with the care of the sick-poor at its heart. Donations to Mainz's hospitals designated for Martin's feast day indicate that charity for those whom the hospital served was seen as central to the saint's veneration. Elizabeth of Hungary is the saint whose service of the sick-poor is most widely commemorated in the regions under study. In accounts of her life, both her work in the hospital she founded, and the care which she offered to the injured and impaired, are consistently highlighted. Like Elizabeth's, Hedwig of Silesia's life spanned multiple regions of Central Europe; and like Elizabeth, Hedwig was commemorated after death for her works of charity and self-denial. The proliferation of art and text extolling such work — often with surprising realism — offers insight into how late medieval hospital care was conceptualized and performed.

Keywords: saints, hospitals, medieval medicine, Central Europe, manuscripts

Session 8D: Moralizing Pregnancy and Infancy through Care

Timing: Thursday, 09/Sept/2021, 3:15pm - 4:30pm

Chair: Prof. Hilary Marland, University of Warwick, United Kingdom

Evangelising through care. The case of Catholic medical consultations for mothers and infants in Postwar Belgium

Juliette Masquelier

Université Libre de Bruxelles, Belgium

Many authors have shown that, before 1940, care and protection of infants and young working-class mothers were entangled with major religious and political issues (Cova, 2000 ; Jusseaume, 2012 ; Marissal, 2014). From 1945, medicalization of pregnancy, birth-giving and motherhood continued to grow : childbirth gradually migrated to hospitals and contraception became a fully medical issue. The medical consultations of the Œuvre Nationale de l'Enfance (National Children's Charity) are one of the places where this medicalisation happened : from 1953, early medical monitoring of pregnancies became generalised, and from 1959 onwards, the ONE recommended that doctors vaccinate infants during consultations. These medical consultations were then disputed by two competing organising powers : the Catholics and the Socialists.

Based on a study of the archives of the Maternal and Child Services (SMI) organized by the Ligues Ouvrières Féminines Chrétiennes (LOFC), this contribution aims to shed light on how medical and religious issues were entangled within consultations run by Christian working-class women between 1945 and 1970. How, in this particular context, were the issues of morality, evangelisation and care organised ? On the one hand, using the archives of the various ONE councils in which the LOFC took part, I will show what was at stake for a Catholic presence in this medico-social organisation based on « subsidised freedom ». On the other hand, from the internal archives of the SMI, I will outline the Catholic ideological imprint on medical practices in consultations, particularly on certain ethical issues, such as breastfeeding, Lamaze technique (psychoprophylactic method for childbirth) or contraception.

Keywords: Childbirth, motherhood, medicalization, moralisation, working-class women

Poverty, Pregnancy and the Longevity of Religious Influence in Glasgow, c. 1970s-2000s

Janet Greenlees

Glasgow Caledonian University, United Kingdom

By the 1980s, despite the efforts of the organized Churches in Scotland to modernize, service attendance for the two most dominant religions, Presbyterianism and Catholicism, were in significant decline. With similar timing, but not necessarily related, the attitudes of the majority of members of both faiths towards maternity was changing to now view abortion as not always being wrong and that medical birth control was an increasingly acceptable way to limit births. Yet despite an increasingly secular society, by the end of the twentieth century religion had not entirely lost its relevance to Scottish healthcare debates. This paper explores how remnants from past family faith were reflected

in women's healthcare decision-making during pregnancy between c. 1970s and early 2000s. It draws on interviews with nineteen Glasgow women who were living in some of Britain's most socio-economically deprived areas when they had their first child towards the end of the century. While the interviewees did not identify as religious, for many women, historic familial religious ties subconsciously influenced pregnancy behaviours. While arguing that faith was embedded in patient healthcare decision-making would stretch the realities in a secular society, the influence of religion in patient decision-making has not completely faded in favour of medical advice and trust in scientific techniques. While not necessarily at conflict with medicine, religious norms and values continued to exert a hidden influence in low-income Scottish communities into the 21st century.

Keywords: Pregnancy, poverty, religion, Scotland

Medical Advice for Moral Infancy: The Confluence of Science and Religion in America, 1850s-1920s*

Elisabeth M. Yang

Rutgers University, United States of America

The emergent antagonism between science and religion was partially reconciled within the context of 19th century American paediatrics through the endorsement of theological morality by the medical profession. During the second half of the 19th century, the sceptre of moral knowledge concerning child-rearing matters was passed from pastor to physician. As historian Julia Grant notes, the discourse shifted toward a greater reliance upon science in matters of child-rearing. Scientific and medical expertise would supplant any theological advice on child-rearing as parents looked less to the church and more to secular tutelary complexes (which comprised psychologists, physicians, sociologists, and anthropologists). However, despite the secularization of child-rearing advice offered by experts, features of moral and spiritual health and its relationship to child's health continued to figure in prominent ways. I argue that in spite of an alleged secularisation of child-rearing and understandings of infants' moral development by the 1920s, there still existed religious, philosophical, cultural, and political overtones to a scientific morality among physicians, scientists, and child-rearing authorities. Spiritual terms continued to be used in physician-authored child-rearing manuals, such as "soul," "spirit," and "divine." In this paper, I suggest that child-rearing discourse in the late 19th and early 20th century entailed a reappropriation of ideologies in which medical professionals promulgated scientific principles imbued with moral and religious valence, recognizing the infant's distinct emotional and spiritual capacities and needs. Rather than a "displacement" of theology, the emergence of a scientific morality espoused by physicians signified a "replacement" and syncretism of Protestantism and science.

Keywords: Moral, Infancy, Paediatrics, Health, Child

* This paper is competing in the Pieter van Foreest Student Prize.

Session 8E: End of Life: Reflections and Debates

Timing: Thursday, 09/Sept/2021, 3:15pm - 4:30pm

Chair: Prof. Anne Kveim Lie, University of Oslo, Norway

How does a thanatologist die? Spirituality, Eutelia, and the “Crystal Self” in Alaine Polcz’s Autobiographical Writings

Eszter Ureczky

University of Debrecen, Hungary

Alaine Polcz (1922–2007) was a Hungarian psychologist, thanatologist, and palliative care expert who established hospice care in Hungary under the oppressive power of the Socialist regime. A survivor of rape trauma during World War II, she devoted her entire life to helping terminally ill children and adults. She was both an internationally acclaimed academic in her field of end-of-life care and author of several autobiographical volumes recollecting her experiences of war, trauma (published in English as *One Woman in the War*), illness, marriage, infertility, old age, mourning, disability, and finally, death. The paper focuses on the representation of spirituality and the rites of consciously preparing for her own death in her last four books (*A Time of Old Age*, *I Will Not Trot On*, *The Score*, *The Last Mile*). Putting special emphasis on Polcz’s interpretation of the “crystal self”, that is, the sacred core of the personality believed to be indestructible by the pain of physical suffering, the paper will examine her personal and professional attitudes towards eutelia or “good death”. In order to examine the latter notion, the paper will also explore Polcz’s black humour concerning the grotesque experience of the ageing female body as well as the relationship between *chronos* and *kairos* in the process of passing over with dignity. Ultimately, Polcz’s oeuvre calls for the re-spiritualisation of death in the era of hygienic, medicalized, and often lonely death.

Keywords: ageing, autobiography, end-of-life care, eutelia, thanatology

‘Conceptual confusion on euthanasia. Reflections on the Softenon and Nuremberg trials as inhibitors to Belgian euthanasia advocacy’*

Niels De Nutte

Vrije Universiteit Brussel, Belgium and deMens.nu, Belgium

Euthanasia is most commonly translated as ‘good death’ and is now widely known as an end-of-life decision involving a form of mercy killing. As one might expect however, these two meanings are not the only ones in existence. In Belgian newspapers and periodicals published between 1950 and 1982, one finds a variety of articles covering the subject. Interestingly, within one edition, the word might be used in a manner similar to that employed in Nazi Germany, be seen as the modern-day mercy killing, be confused with abortion, or indeed might mean something entirely different. This presentation looks at the variety of connotations associated with the term, focusing on articles relating to affairs foreign (proposed legislation by the VELs, the Nuremberg trials) or domestic (the 1961 Softenon trial in Liege). Two resources are used for this project. The first is the Belgica Press

* This paper is competing in the Pieter van Foreest Student Prize.

collection of the Royal library in Brussels, supplemented by a 1982 publication by the Association pour le Droit de Mourir dans la Dignité. This near 300-page volume consists of newspaper articles published on euthanasia since 1961, providing excellent source material which coincides with its rise of euthanasia as a societal issue spurred on by the unprecedented medical progress. As Belgian newspapers of that period are markedly partisan, understanding the way they dealt with this concept may prove crucial in bringing nuance to the idea that advocates and opponents of euthanasia were to be found on opposite sides of the philosophical-religious fault line at the heart of Belgian society.

Keywords: end-of-life, euthanasia, conceptual confusion, good death, mercy killing

Session 9A: Healing Miracles and Medical Expertise. The extraordinary case of the Convulsionaries of Saint-Médard in 18th-century France

Timing: Friday, 10/Sept/2021, 9:00am - 10:15am

Chair: Vincent Barras, Lausanne University Hospital, Switzerland

We are proposing a panel consisting of three conferences, which will present the current research conducted within the major research project at the Lausanne University Hospital on the relations between medicine and religion in 18th-century France, and more specifically on medical expertise in cases of healing miracles, on medical theories on nervous diseases, and the role of the sick individual in the process of their natural and miraculous healing. Based on vast archival research, these three dimensions of the project explore collaborations, the controversies and cultural, professional and social implications of the articulation between medicine and religion in prerevolutionary France.

Keywords: natural, supernatural, convulsions, miracles, relics

The patient's role in healing miracles, or the pharmacological function of relics

Eva Yampolsky

Lausanne University Hospital, Switzerland

Yampolsky will present her research based on extensive archival research consisting in great part of 1st-person official accounts of healing miracles. Her conference will focus on the natural and then miraculous healing process, as it is experienced and described by the miraculés themselves, and on the active role they played in this process. Even though these miracles were never validated or accepted by the Church, the documentation attests to the traditional protocols of miracle evaluation, including expertise by physicians and surgeons, as well as detailed accounts by miraculously healed individuals and other witnesses. Through an analysis of these case studies, she will show the porous and often ambiguous relationship between the medical and the religious spheres, as well as between the natural and the supernatural. More specifically, she will present the ways in which the miraculously healed individuals appropriated both medical and religious knowledge and healing techniques, namely through a “pharmacological” use of relics, as a way to participate in the healing process. Finally, she will show the relations between the medical and the religious spheres in early 18th-century France extends to the patients themselves, who incorporate not only various healing techniques, but also the language and discourse of both of these disciplines. In order to examine the role of the patient in their healing process (natural and supernatural), Yampolsky will present several case studies from the Archives of the Bibliothèque de Port-Royal (Paris), a rich source of miracle cases consisting of official manuscript documents.

Philippe Hecquet and healing miracles, between the natural and the supernatural

Serge Margel

University of Neuchatel, Switzerland

The French physician Philippe Hecquet is an intermediary figure at the turn of the 18th century, in which we witness the close articulation between medicine and religion. However, the period during which he publishes his texts on the Convulsionaries, including his book entitled *Le Naturalisme des convulsions* [The Naturalism of Convulsions] (1733), this medico-theological stance becomes paradoxical, and especially as it relates to the question of healing miracles. He seeks to radically separate convulsions from miracles, following the distinction between the natural and the supernatural. He not only considers the “agitations” of the Convulsionaries as a nervous disease, but he also founds his naturalist explanations of convulsions on biblical and theological examples. Hecquet is close to the physician Borelli’s iatrophysical school, which combines Descartes’s mechanist vision and experimental observations. This vision allows him to interpret the body of the Convulsionaries in terms of a disordered hydraulic machine and to prove the natural origin of convulsions. This disequilibrium is produced by passions or by diseased imagination, which can in turn produce muscular movements, like convulsions, that are beyond the subject’s control. However, while refusing to see the hand of God in the convulsions, he admits, following the theological and philosophical tradition represented by the “figurism” of the theologian Etemare, the divine power of miracles.

Convulsions and nervous diseases in 18th-century medicine: a medico-religious controversy

Leonard Dolivo

University of Lausanne, Switzerland

A great amount of medical writings is dedicated to convulsions during the 18th century. Physicians address this subject in various types of texts, such as academic dissertations, observations, treatises and letters. By doing so, they continue a rather ancient and well traceable tradition of writing about convulsions and modeling it as an object proper to medicine. One of the core characteristics of those archives is the omission or rejection of supernatural explanations. Theories of the nervous system, including animal spirit movements, *succus nervosus* propagation and the alteration of humours, provide a dominant explanatory framework for convulsions and other physiological phenomena that had often, until then, been attributed to supernatural forces. However, despite this consistent attempt to theorize and frame a phenomenon as a rational pathological entity, during the 18th century, medical expertise on involuntary bodily movements remains challenged by religious interpretations of these phenomena. Indeed, the case of the Convulsionaries of Saint-Médard reveals just how adjustable and sometimes powerless the physician’s expertise can be. Through a close analysis of several 18th-century medical writings, Léonard Dolivo will show that, in the struggle between the natural and the supernatural conceptions of convulsions, physicians position themselves as “natural” arbiters in this controversy.

Session 9B: Medical Ethics

Timing: Friday, 10/Sept/2021, 9:00am - 10:15am

Chair: Dr. Noortje Jacobs, University of Rotterdam, the Netherlands

Lutheran approaches towards medical uncertainty in the early twentieth century

Pieter Dhondt¹, Saara-Maija Kontturi¹

¹*University of Eastern Finland, Finland*

From the introduction of the research university at the end of the nineteenth century, the balance between ‘medicine as an art’ and ‘medicine as a science’ gradually passed over to a purely ‘objective’ approach of medicine as a natural science. However, even the continuously succeeding breakthroughs in medical science never could and will be able to take away uncertainty completely in clinical decision making and therapeutic treatments.

Certainly in comparison to, for instance, the Catholic Church, the long-term acceptance of so-called modern medicine happened much more smoothly within the Lutheran Church. However, this absolutely did not mean that for physicians raised and educated in a Lutheran environment, their religious background was irrelevant. Lutherans generally favour(ed) open communication between caregiver and patient. Assuming a position of equality, the relationship between patients and health care providers had to be a partnership of trust.

How, in such kind of doctor-patient relationships, questions of uncertainty have been dealt with? How (Lutheran) physicians were taught to confront their patients with the fact that diseases are seldom black and white, and why it was sometimes preferred to hide the medical truth, since after all finally “one’s fate was in the hands of God”? By studying a large variety of educational documents from professors and students at the University of Helsinki we will offer a view on the possible impact of the Lutheran religion and the physicians’ personal religious views when dealing with medical uncertainty in education (and in their practical work), during the early twentieth century.

Keywords: medical uncertainty, Lutheranism, doctor-patient relationship, education

Balancing Knowledge Reliability and Ethical Acceptability at the Moscow Institute for New Antibiotics, 1950s-1970s

Pavel Andreyevich Vasilyev¹, Viktoria Vadimovna Vinokurova¹, Alexander Nikolaevich Petrenko²

¹*HSE University St. Petersburg, Russian Federation*; ²*Siberian State Medical University, Russian Federation*

Between the 1950s and the 1970s, the Moscow Institute for New Antibiotics developed a number of innovative drugs that were supposed to treat a range of different conditions. These findings were not only confined within the scientific realm proper but were also reported in the Soviet popular press. This unexpectedly became a source of much controversy in 1958, when an illustrated journal *Sovetskii Soiuz* (available globally in over a dozen languages from Finnish to Urdu) published an article about the Institute’s work directed at the development of drugs against cancer.

Within a few months, the office of received dozens of letters from desperate and frustrated readers from all over the Soviet Union and even from abroad. These readers (or, in many cases, their relatives) were usually suffering from final-stage cancer and were desperate to get any medicine that could potentially improve their condition. They were explicitly challenging Soviet scientists to abandon the complicated bureaucratic procedure for drug testing and to send them their experimental drugs, since, in the words of one reader, 'death is near anyway' (vsě ravno skoro smert').

The Institute's leadership, therefore, was confronted with a difficult task of balancing scientific reliability and ethical acceptability in practice. In the paper, we draw on archival and oral history materials to narrate the untold story of the dilemma that the scientists faced within the context of medical research ethics, Soviet bureaucratic procedures and mid-20th century mediality and use this case to problematize and historically situate the notion of 'patient-centered care'.

Keywords: clinical trials, research ethics, antibiotics, USSR, patient-centered care

"Vera Fautrix Eugenicae": Medicine, Physicians, and the Catholic Way to Eugenics

Carlo Bovolo

Università del Piemonte Orientale, Italy

The paper explores approaches and attitudes of European Catholic physicians towards eugenics in early 20th century. The debate about eugenics involved not only medicine and biology, but also demography, politics, culture, society. The eugenics studies produced debates and resistances, especially within the Catholics. Their opposition were scientific, medical, political, and theological: they criticized the lack of scientific basis in some eugenic hypotheses and defended the human freedom from the interventions of the governments, to preserve the social, moral, and political influence of Catholicism. Catholics opposed mostly towards the Nordic current of eugenics, spread in the Anglo-Saxon, German world, characterized by the idea of the need of an artificial selection of the humankind through strong interventions (sterilization, abortion, birth-control). A Latin current of eugenics based mostly education, prevention and demographic increase, and spread in Catholic Europe and Latin America, obtained consideration in part of the catholic movement, for example the Franciscan physician Agostino Gemelli. Rejecting the negative eugenics policies, Gemelli and other Catholic physicians and scientists (Fallon, Muckermann, Viollet, etc.) approved and embraced the Latin eugenics, stating that the Christian morals represented the effective eugenic principle. A Catholic medicine and its medical and biological argumentations played a key role. Catholic physicians tried to build a Catholic way to eugenics, in accordance with the Faith, and gain a public recognized role in the eugenic debates. The paper examines the the contributions of Catholic physicians in building a scientific and medical opposition to the Nordic eugenics and in shaping a Catholic eugenic approach.

Keywords: eugenics, catholicism, catholic physicians

Session 9C: Religious Actors in Russian and Eastern European Health Care

Timing: Friday, 10/Sept/2021, 9:00am - 10:15am

Chair: Dr. Tinne Claes, KU Leuven, Belgium

Women cloisters and medicine amidst State-Church relationship in late Imperial Russia.

Nataliya Shok¹, Nadezhda Beliakova^{2,3}

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Medicine in the second half of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century was a space of modernization in the Russian Empire. Legislative initiatives expanded the social role of medicine in preserving "people's health". As a result of the Great Reforms of the 1860s, the institution of zemstvo medicine emerged. The rapid modernization of medical care was accompanied by wars, which meant a growing number of widows, orphans, and the disabled, needed socio-medical care. The drastic change in the life of the rural population and rapid urbanization destroyed the peasant family and created new risks for women. At the same time, there was an increase in the number of women's religious communities - cloisters and women's convents, some of which initially emerged as almshouses for widows and elderly women. The number of women entering these cloisters was growing rapidly. These cloisters begin to develop socio-medical care for rural populations and vulnerable groups. Over time, these practices evolve into centers of monastic medicine that combine the experience of "primary theology," "lived religion," and state interests. Interactions between medicine and religion in women cloisters - Orthodox nursing networks - emerge in the context of serious social modernization. This enables authors to rethink the traditional understanding of secularization and medicalization processes in the 19th century scrutinizing medical practices of women cloisters within the system of church-state relations. Authors will show, using specific sources, the importance of the social and medical networks in post-reform Russia.

Keywords: State-Church relationship, women cloisters, Orthodox nursing network, Russian Empire

Fighting the Shame. Physicians, Priests, and Venereal Diseases in Romania, 1853-1874

Lidia Trausan-Matu¹, Octavian Buda¹

¹ *'Carol Davila' University of Medicine and Pharmacy Bucharest, Romania*

This presentation examines the process of collaboration between physicians and priests for the fight against venereal diseases in Romania in the period 1853-1874. This process started with the 1853 Hospital Reform Act. With it, the rulers sought to create a network of county hospitals, with the help of which medical access to rural population was given, through this medicalization.

Despite the best efforts of the physicians, most sufferers did not want to hear about the hospitalization and refused to follow a treatment recommended by the physician. The main reason for the refusal was related to the fact that hospitals in Romania were initially created (in 1842) only for syphilis, a disease that raised great moral problems. This image persisted in the mentality of the citizens until the end of the 19th century. To persuade them to cooperate, the medical authorities

turned to the services of the priests. In the Romanian space, the popular faith attributed to the priest the role of mediator to the divine power of healing. The priests were supposed to convince people of the beneficial role of the physicians and of the hospitals. Thus, starting from 1858 to 1874, the so-called “hospital priest” appeared on the list of employees of the county hospitals in Romania. In this study we will describe the services that hospital priests provide to patients and we will highlight the interaction with medical staff.

Keywords: county hospitals, physicians, venereal diseases, the hospital priest, faith

Poor, Sick, and Mad: Treating the Mentally Ill in the Hungarian Hospitals of the Brothers of Mercy (1740–1830)*

Janka Kovács

Eötvös Loránd University, Hungary

The presentation addresses the early practices of care for the mentally ill in the Hungarian hospitals of the Brothers of Mercy, highlighting the connections between illness and poverty and the social and medical approaches towards the mentally ill. The Order settled in Hungary in the middle of the 17th century intending to provide care for the poor. They were traditionally inclined towards the mentally ill, and even though in this period we cannot talk about standardized care and a systematic therapeutic regime, the pursuit of registering and isolating the ‘mad’ within hospitals is already detectable.

The documents of hospital administration (patient records, registries, and regulations) enable us to examine the socioeconomic background of patients and also how mental illnesses were named and classified in the hospitals. There are numerous references to the isolation of the ‘mad’ and their division into different subgroups based on their mental states (calm, furious, dangerous) and social background (registered poor, privileged classes), somewhat defying the fundamental principles of the Order.

Using the documents of hospital administration, complemented with narrative sources reflecting on the daily routine of the hospitals (such as medical topographies, city descriptions, and travelogues), the problems of medicalization and the pursuit of specialized care will be addressed. The Order’s work in Hungary gives a unique glimpse into the early ways and strategies of care for the mad in a period, when the medico-political authorities were only beginning to address the question in the Habsburg Monarchy.

Keywords: madness, Brothers of Mercy, hospital network, Hungary

* This paper is competing in the Pieter van Foreest Student Prize.

Session 9D: From Mesmerism to Jean-Martin Charcot

Timing: Friday, 10/Sept/2021, 9:00am - 10:15am

Chair: Prof. Kaat Wils, KU Leuven, Belgium

Mesmeric therapy of the self. Medico-spiritual guidance in Mesmer's *Mémoire* (1779) and *Précis historique* (1781)

Chloé Conickx*

Ghent University, Belgium

In relation to religious care, historiography has treated the curious medical therapy of mesmerism as an eighteenth-century 'naturalization' or 'medicalization' of traditionally 'spiritual' concerns, pathologies and healing practices. Mesmer (1734-1815) had introduced the existence of a magnetic fluid that connected all beings, thereby explaining health and disease as caused by natural, 'magnetic' influences rather than as the result of supernatural interventions. This paper problematizes the important elements of continuity between religious and medical/mesmeric therapeutics in Mesmer's *Mémoire* (1779) and *Précis historique* (1781). More specifically, I argue that the appeal and specificity of particular vocabularies and imageries in both forms of therapeutics are symptomatic of their shared nature as technologies of the self (cf. Michel Foucault) or ascetic spiritual exercises (cf. Pierre Hadot).

By implication, I also suggest that a historiographical focus on secularization of religious discourses and world-views is not only uninteresting but also potentially counterproductive in understanding the specificity of such therapeutics. This paper overcomes presentist interpretations of medicine as progressing from 'premodern religious practices' to 'modern scientific discipline'. In addition, it acknowledges that disciplinary borders were quite vague in this period and that early modern practices and discourses, like medicine and (Christian) religion, shared common concerns and ways of meaning-making.

Keywords: mesmerism, (self-)care, therapeutics, Enlightenment medicine

Gérard Encausse: The Occult and Scientific-Self

Genevieve Dally-Watkins

The University of Sydney, Australia

This paper will explore the life and works of the occultist and doctor, Gérard Encausse (1865-1916). Although the esoteric facets of Encausse's life have been extensively addressed, he often falls into the footnotes of French neurological history. My paper will consider Encausse's reconciliation of medical and occult sciences and assess whether his activities aligned with the broader medical and cultural climate of fin-de-siècle Paris. I will argue that Encausse demonstrates how the occult subject could connect to the medical doctor. Specifically, I propose the juxtaposition of degenerate and female passivity with masculine scientific rationality was a common construction within French occultism and medicine. I will contextualise this claim through examining an occult treatise by Encausse and Jean-Martin Charcot's formulations of hysteria and mysticism. Fundamentally, the aim of this presentation

* This paper is competing in the Pieter van Foreest Student Prize.

is two-fold. Firstly, I will demonstrate how identity and disciplinary notions could link esoteric and medical practices. Secondly, I intend to illustrate that late-nineteenth century Paris had an eclectic tradition that melded together medical, aesthetic, and metaphysical systems. This paper demonstrates differing degrees of engagement with this tradition: on one end of the spectrum, figures like Charcot tried to extricate themselves from this framework; on the other, individuals like Encausse championed the system. Esotericists and physicians have been presented as oppositional agents around questions of positivism and faith. This paper will demonstrate that they collectively pathologised spirituality and spiritualised pathological inquiry.

Keywords: Vitalism, Degeneration, Occultism, Salpêtrière, Naturphilosophie

Deconstructing the Miracle: Jean-Martin Charcot's Neurophysiological Interpretation of Faith Healing in Hysteria Patients*

Paula Muhr

Independent researcher

The late-nineteenth-century French neurologist Jean-Martin Charcot became famous for his research into hysteria, a mysterious disorder characterised by various somatic symptoms that appeared to lack a detectable organic cause.

Charcot's approach to hysteria was purely materialistic. He thus argued that hysterical symptoms were caused by a hypothetical functional disturbance of the brain, i.e., a dynamic lesion. Moreover, in a decidedly anticlerical move, he retrospectively diagnosed famous saints, religious mystics and demoniacs as hysterics. Yet, in his last published text, "La foi qui guérit," Charcot acknowledged the efficacy of miracle cures that transpired in religious sanctuaries. In this text, Charcot argued that miracle cures could only happen in individuals suffering from hysteria and that such patient had to exhibit excessive suggestibility.

Several contemporary scholars have taken these claims to mean that Charcot had abandoned his materialistic views and shifted to a psychologically inflected interpretation of hysteria. However, through a close reading of "La foi qui guérit" and Charcot's earlier lectures on medical treatments of hysteria, I suggest that this was not the case. Instead, I show that in Charcot's interpretation, faith healing was not a religious miracle but was grounded in the same neurophysiological principles that informed medical treatment of hysteria. In both cases, healing worked through autosuggestion, which, according to Charcot, was a form of a neurophysiologically determined cerebral reflex. In short, for Charcot, faith healing was effective because it physiologically altered hysteria patients' brain function.

Keywords: hysteria, faith healing, Jean-Martin Charcot, miracle, brain function

* This paper is competing in the Pieter van Foreest Student Prize.

Session 9E: Faith, Relief and Medical Education in the Low Countries

Timing: Friday, 10/Sept/2021, 9:00am - 10:15am

Chair: Dr. Joris Vandendriessche, KU Leuven, Belgium

Faith, religion and public health in the Netherlands; short story of a successful merger*

Jan Hurman

Hurman Consult, the Netherlands

The rise of public health interventions has traditionally been located in the 19th century, as by-product of the consolidation of nation states. In most countries public health was organized in public organisations, on a municipal or a nationwide level. The Netherlands does not fit into this pattern. Private initiatives ('particulier initiatief') were dominant in building Dutch public health. The struggle against the great killers around 1900 (tuberculosis and infant mortality) was primarily the task of so-called 'Kruiswerk' (Cross-work) and TBC-societies, both private organisations.

Initially, during the first 40 years after the founding of the first 'Kruisvereniging' in 1875, this type of organisations was neutral, not connected to any religious or political organisation. As the movement spread over the Netherlands, developing from Noord-Holland to the southern provinces, it met resistance. Catholic bishops and politicians became afraid that the religious neutral 'Kruisverenigingen', with merely rational conceptions of public and personal hygiene, would undermine the catholic moral of their herd. Thus, in Limburg the catholic elite appropriated the 'Groene Kruis' (Green Cross) - neutral in the rest of the Netherlands - from the beginning. In Noord-Brabant the bishops choose for another path. As the 'Groene Kruis' in this province did succeed in building a neutral organisation, the bishops stimulated catholic priests, catholic medical doctors and other members of the catholic elite to found catholic 'Wit-Gele Kruisverenigingen'.

In my presentation I will show how catholic faith and religion merged with modern rational concepts of hygiene and preventive medicine, and how successful this marriage was.

Keywords: Public Health, private initiative, catholic religion and faith

Medicine contra religion. Or: how Franz Joseph Harbaur forces the Sint-Elisabeth Gasthuis to cooperate with the University of Leuven (1817-1819)

Catharina Th. Bakker

Erasmus Universiteit Rotterdam, the Netherlands

It's 1817. The United Kingdom of the Netherlands is in its infancy. Of the many things that need to be arranged, university education is one. Medicine is a keystone. To everyone's surprise, Dr. Franz Joseph Harbaur, court physician of King William I, becomes rector magnificus of the newly (re)founded University of Leuven, with the explicit task of invigorating medical education. In order to do so, good clinical training is required; i.e. bedside teaching. The Sint-Elisabeth Gasthuis, which is run by Augustinian Sisters and headed by a board of laymen, is the only candidate to be set up for this

* This paper is competing in the Pieter van Foreest Student Prize.

purpose. Harbaur, himself a moderate Catholic, has strong ideas about what such a hospital should look like. These ideas however do not match with the existing religious practices. It is all about the settlement and the organization of care. In an increasingly heated exchange of letters between Harbaur and the administration, two worlds collide: medicine versus religion. But it's not just that: it's also the clash of the old and the new world (before the French Revolution and beyond). It's my aim to show this change using the letters as main source. In the end, it's Harbaur who wins the case. At the start of the clinical education in the Sint-Elisabeth Gasthuis he addresses his students: show respect for the sisters!

Keywords: early nineteenth century, hospital care, academic medicine, Leuven

The Friends' War Victims' Relief Committee: medical work in the Marne during the First World War

Linda Palfreeman

Linda Palfreeman, University CEU Cardenal Herrera, Spain

The outbreak of war in Europe, in 1914 presented a serious moral dilemma for members of the Religious Society of Friends (Friends or Quakers). As the tragedy unfolded, many Friends, prevented by their religious principles from taking up arms, sought means of alleviating the appalling scale of anguish and misery being suffered by civilian victims of the war.

Doctor Hilda Clark knew that the existing medical services would be focused on attending the overwhelming needs of the military to the inevitable detriment of non-combatant citizens. Together with prominent Quaker, T. Edmund Harvey MP, Clark set about rallying the support of Friends and sympathisers willing to go out to France and Belgium to administer aid. The small committee created to organise the endeavour would be known as the Friends' War Victims Relief Committee (FWVRC), the same as that used by the renowned organisation that had administered relief in the Franco-Prussian War. The work carried out would fall into four main classes: general relief work; the building of prefabricated housing and repair of ruined homes; agricultural work and medical work. It is the latter category that forms the focus of this paper.

The FWVRC founded a number of vital medical facilities and convalescent homes, and extensive district nursing was carried out. Its' first, most celebrated and most enduring venture, however, was the maternity hospital at Châlons-sur-Marne. Its success, claimed matron, Edith Pye, was due to the religious spirit underlying its work and the essential moral guidance administered to the mothers.

Keywords: FWVRC, Quakers, medical assistance, maternity care, religious and moral guidance

Lunch Session 4A

Timing: Friday, 10/Sept/2021, 12:00pm - 12:45pm

Heritage of Care - Care for Heritage

Kristien Suenens¹, An Vandenberghe², Bart Marius³

¹*KU Leuven, Belgium*; ²*Erfgoedcentrum Zusters van Liefde, Belgium*; ³*Museum Dr. Guislain Ghent, Belgium*

KADOC-KU Leuven and Museum Dr. Guislain, together with other heritage, (health) care and socio-cultural partners, present the project 'Heritage of Care – Care for heritage'. The project has a threefold focus: (1) mapping the diverse and valuable, but also endangered heritage of care institutions and organizations in Flanders (Belgium); (2) building expertise about the features, problems and opportunities characterizing care heritage by means of in-depth case studies; (3) developing a digital, interactive and co-creative platform to support care-givers, care-receivers, socio-cultural and heritage institutions and organizations, researches and the general public in the preservation and valorization of the heritage of care.

Keywords: Heritage, Care, Flanders

Lunch Session 4B: Roundtable

Timing: Friday, 10/Sept/2021, 12:00pm - 12:45pm

Chair: Agata Ignaciuk (University of Warsaw, Poland; University of Granada, Spain)

Does religion matter for histories of reproduction in post-war Europe? (cases: Belgium, United Kingdom and Ukraine)

Tinne Claes¹, Yuliya Hilevych², Polina Vlasenko³

¹*KU Leuven, Belgium*; ²*Universiteit Groningen, the Netherlands*; ³*Indiana University, United States of America*

Histories of assisted reproduction and Christian religions have highlighted tensions and conflicts, proscriptions and prescriptions (e.g. Sèvegrand 1995; McDonnell and Allison 2006; Man Wall 2010; Radkowska-Walkowicz 2018). Regarding artificial insemination, especially the Roman Catholic Church has been described as a conservative force, as Pope Leo XIII had decreed artificial insemination to be illicit as early as in 1897. In the words of Nick Hopwood, this decision was a 'milestone in articulating a Catholic discourse that engaged with interventions in reproduction earlier and more uncompromisingly than other religions' (Hopwood 2018, p. 583). Yet research has also drawn attention to opposition against artificial insemination within other Christian religions, most notably Anglicanism and other Protestant traditions (Davis 2013; 2017; Richards 2014).

In the history of medicine more broadly, recent histories have reassessed these widespread storylines of conflict: drawing attention to entanglements and cross-overs (Pia Donato 2013), questioning common associations between 'religion' and 'conservatism' (Horn 2015; Chappel 2018), and revealing

substantive gaps between official church teachings and the discourses and practices of those who considered themselves to be faithful (Woodcock Tentler 2004; Harris 2018; Kelly and Ignaciuk 2020). To sum up, historians have begun to clear up popular and scholarly misconceptions about the homogeneity and stability of religious opinions concerning medical developments. However, this more nuanced approach until today remains largely confined to medical histories of contraception. Religious debates on assisted reproduction have received far less attention (Betta 2017), even though there is an equally important story to be told.

Aiming to showcase new empirical research in the history of medicine and reproduction, this roundtable will focus on artificial insemination with donor sperm (AID). From the 1940s to the 1970s, AID became a reliable if controversial reproductive procedure, resulting in the birth of thousands of children. In this roundtable, three panellists will discuss the diverging developments of this controversial technology in Europe, looking at Belgium, United Kingdom and Ukraine. The panellists are currently collaborating on a special issue on the post-war history of artificial insemination, and grasp this conference as an opportunity to reflect about the role of religion, from religious authorities to individual believers.

In this light, the roundtable will address the following contested questions:

- 1) Did religion matter in the post-war histories of AID? If so, how and to what extent did religion influence the development of and discourses around AID across the aforementioned national contexts?
- 2) How did religion interact with other medico-moral arguments about AID? What was the role of doctors, theologians, legal regulators and patients in these processes?
- 3) How did historical shifts in the importance of religion over the decades impact on reproductive policies in various national contexts?
- 4) Which other explanations need to be considered to explain differences and similarities between different national contexts?

By comparing how religion played out in various national contexts, the panellists not only shed new light on the history of AID in post-war Europe, but also reassess widespread deterministic accounts of modernity, secularisation, and sexual reform.

Keywords: Assisted Reproduction, Comparative History, Artificial Insemination

Session 10A: Catholic Doctors and Medical Ethics

Timing: Friday, 10/Sept/2021, 3:00pm - 4:15pm

Chair: Tinne Claes, KU Leuven, Belgium

This panel focuses on Catholic approaches to medical ethics. The papers together show different expressions of what it meant to act as a Catholic doctor. Since the 19th century, Catholic normative texts outlined doctors' behavior as a transnational intellectual genre practiced by both theologians and doctors. In the 20th century, Catholic medical ethics also became articulated in other ways. The Belgian gynecologist Marcel Renaer expressed his Catholic views on reproduction through popularizing texts. At the same time, "Catholic" clinical guidelines emerged. The (ethically sensitive) regulation of IVF in American and Belgian Catholic hospitals offers a case in point.

Keywords: Medical Ethics, Deontology, IVF

Changing Conceptions of the Catholic Doctor: Medical Ethics and Catholic Morality in Francophone and Anglophone Normative Literature, c. 1840-1960

Andreas Holger Maehle¹, Cheryl Lancaster¹, Jolien Gijbels², Reinout Vander Hulst²

¹Durham University, United Kingdom; ²KU Leuven, Belgium

In the recent historiography of Anglo-American medical ethics in the nineteenth and early twentieth centuries, secular and professional aspects tend to be foregrounded (e.g. Robert Baker 2013; A.-H. Maehle 2021). By contrast, this paper will focus on intersections of medical ethics and religious commitments by charting conceptions of the Catholic doctor in French and English-language normative texts from the mid-nineteenth to the mid-twentieth century. Behavioural norms for doctors were increasingly emphasised in writings on pastoral medicine, especially regarding obstetrics and advice on sexual hygiene. The Ten Commandments and the Sacraments formed the initial ethical framework, and doctors subscribing to a Catholic way of practising stressed that there was no necessary conflict between Christian religion and modern scientific medicine. For these doctors, moral theology provided authoritative guidance, in addition to the law. From the 1890s, Catholic medical deontology emerged as a genre in its own right, in writing and in teaching, reflecting a distinct identity of Catholic doctors in medical faculties and in their own professional societies in France, Belgium and Britain. Simultaneously, the spectrum of instructions for conduct conforming to Catholic morality broadened. While traditional issues of reproductive ethics such as medical abortion and emergency baptism remained central concerns, eugenic sterilisation and euthanasia posed new challenges for Catholic medical practitioners. More generally, the Catholic doctor was now expected to take on a social role that went beyond the care of his individual patients, especially in questions of population politics.

Marcel Renaer: a personalist Catholic physician

Maarten Langhendries

KU Leuven, Belgium

This paper focusses on the dialogue between Catholic personalist theology and medical practitioners at the Catholic University of Leuven. After the Second World War, under the influence of the doctrine of social personalism, some Catholic physicians started to put the wishes and desires of the patient more in the center of medical practice. At the KU Leuven, especially Marcel Renaer was highly influential in propagating these new medical ideas, specifically in the fields of gynecology and obstetrics. In the '1950s and '60s, he tried to incorporate the philosophy of the Leuven based Universitasgroup into a new form of Catholic healthcare, in which a Catholic doctor had to serve first and foremost the interests of his patients instead of those of the Catholic Church, and take into account more the mental, social, and familial complexity of every individual. This new attitude was most visible in Renaer's views on contraception and family planning. He held the believe every patient should be able to plan his or her family life, which resulted in a large amount of courses, lectures and publications in which he defended the use of contraception. To put his ideas into clinical practice, he founded the chair for Medical Ethics. He was also the first head of the commission for medical ethics at the Leuven Faculty of Medicine. My paper will use the figure of Renaer to shed light on the changing Catholic conceptions of the ethics of doctor-patient relationships in the postwar period.

Diverging Paths: Approaches to IVF in Catholic Hospitals in the USA and Belgium

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This paper compares Catholic hospital policies in two countries – the USA and Belgium – regarding the ethically contested treatment area of In-Vitro Fertilization (IVF). As a medical therapy for infertility, IVF raised complex ethical concerns on the nature of reproduction for many in the Catholic Church. By studying comparatively how this issue was confronted in two different national and sociopolitical postwar contexts, this paper analyzes the varied implementation of Catholic ideas about reproductive medicine in healthcare settings. In the U.S., we show how the centralizing implementation of the Ethical and Religious Directives (ERDs) came to serve as a binding policy document in the latter half of the twentieth century. The ERDs have limited ethical decision-making by clinicians on the ground in healthcare settings around the country, supplanting medical authority with the authority of the U.S. Conference of Catholic Bishops. In Belgium, to the contrary, we show how Catholic doctors debated the issue in (local) ethical committees, agreeing on IVF being ethically permissible in (Catholic) hospitals if certain conditions were met (e.g. the psychological stability of the couple). In these debates, the disadvantage of creating 'superfluous' human embryos during IVF was weighed against the benefits of improving Christian relations by (technically) enabling reproduction within a personalist framework. In the final part of the paper, we will draw out points of similarity and difference between these two very different models of ethical decision-making in religious healthcare institutions.

Session 10B: Spiritual Mothers: Medieval Discourses of Medicine, Religion and Reproduction*

Timing: Friday, 10/Sept/2021, 3:00pm - 4:15pm

Chair: Lydia Rose Shahan, Harvard University, United States of America

Medieval Christian texts often treat pregnancy and parturition as purely theological themes, focusing on Christ's incarnation and virgin birth or on the spiritual birth of the Godhead within the individual's soul. However, metaphors of labour and their use within mystical and religious texts are also in dialogue with contemporaneous medical theories of obstetrics and gynecology, as well as with lived experiences of childbirth. The three papers in this panel bring together theological, medical and devotional writings from the later Middle Ages to reveal how multifaceted understandings of both somatic and spiritual birth influenced medieval conceptions of gender, sanctity and sin.

Keywords: Gender, reproduction, birth, gynecology, mysticism

Eve as Sexual Sinner, and as Fertile Redeemer: Images of the First Woman in Hildegard of Bingen's Theology and Medicine

Lauren Cole

Independent Scholar

In twelfth-century theology, such as that of Bernard of Clairvaux, it is common to find Eve's sexuality depicted as the root of original sin. Her fertile nature is forever tainted, such that women are cursed with immense pain in order to reproduce. Within this context, Hildegard of Bingen (d.1179) wrote her great trilogy of visionary theology, as well as two medical texts which have only recently been released in critical edition. While her theology may align with her male contemporaries, her medicine certainly does not. In the medical work *Causae et curae*, Hildegard describes Eve as "mother of the human race", using the word *mater* (mother), a term almost exclusively reserved for Mary in her theology. This indicates a much more positive view of Eve's reproductive nature than purely as the cause of original sin. Indeed Hildegard writes that original sin is passed down through the generations by "the pollution of semen", flipping contemporary theology on its head to cast Adam's reproductive nature as the root of original sin. From this basis, Hildegard discusses the reproductive process from the compatibility of partners and conception to pregnancy and birth. This paper examines how Hildegard constructed the image of Eve's reproductive nature in a way that departs so dramatically from mainstream theology. It considers her use of different types of knowledge, such as visionary knowledge and humoral theory. Finally it suggests that the medical genre enabled Hildegard to frame herself not as divine amanuensis, but as author in her own right.

* This paper is competing in the Pieter van Foreest Student Prize.

Proof of Pregnancy: Discernment and Diagnosis of Spiritual Pregnancy in Later Medieval Hagiography

Lydia Shahan

Harvard University, United States of America

This paper considers the phenomenon of spiritual and mystical pregnancy in later medieval saints' lives, revealing the intersection between religious and medical modes of discernment and evaluation. In her hagiography, Ida of Leuven, a holy woman in thirteenth-century Flanders, is described as experiencing bodily swelling and internal movements that mimic the appearance and sensations of pregnancy and precede a mystical vision of the Christ child. This was a common manifestation of divine favor for holy women (and some men) in the later Middle Ages. On one occasion, however, a Dominican friar suspects that Ida has literally become pregnant by another friar and dispatches a Dominican medical expert to evaluate her condition. This friar claims to be able to determine whether a woman is pregnant by evaluating her eyes, a diagnostic indicator found in Hippocrates' *Superfetation*, as well as in other medieval treatises on conception. When the friar inspects Ida's eyes, he discovers that she is not pregnant. As a reward for the tribulation of suspected pregnancy, Ida again receives a vision of the infant Christ. This paper discusses how women's embodied experiences of mystical pregnancy were evaluated and "proven" by male confessors and hagiographers. In addition to Ida's *Vita*, it considers the accounts of Birgitta of Sweden's (d.1373) experiences of spiritual pregnancy provided during her canonization process; her male confessor recorded his ocular observation of her spiritual pregnancy. As with Ida, the twin perspectives of spiritual discernment and medical diagnosis are required to construct the cult of a saint.

Mary as Mater Dolorosa: Childbirth, Motherhood, Loss and Trauma in The Book of Margery Kempe

Einat Klafter

Tel Aviv University, Israel

Throughout the *Book of Margery Kempe*, the eponymous protagonist voices a strong desire to present herself as a chaste maiden by dressing in white clothing. However, when it comes to fashioning herself as a holy woman, this late-medieval English mystic draws upon her own experiences of motherhood. Her exemplars are not virgin saints, but holy wives and mothers, ranging from the Virgin Mary to St. Bridget of Sweden, who functions as the main role model for constructing her own sainthood. More specifically, Kempe draws upon the pain, trauma and sorrow associated with pregnancy, childbirth, and motherhood, with which she was intimately acquainted. The joys and rewards of motherhood do not feature prominently, or at all, in *The Book*, in an approach that significantly diverges from the example set by Bridget. This paper argues that this is a by-product of the different experiences of childbirth that the two mystics report, with St. Bridget recounting the miracle of painless childbirth, while Kempe experienced a difficult first pregnancy and traumatic labour that left her ill for months. This paper argues that the differences in how the two mystics experienced childbirth impacted how they viewed the Nativity, connected with the Virgin, and conceptualized their *imitatio Mariae*. Additionally, this paper will explore how maternal pain and the dangers of childbirth are employed in Kempe's attempts to establish herself as a holy woman, either by recounting her own experiences or in caring for women who, like herself, have suffered traumatic childbirths.

Session 10C: Cancer and Miracle Cures in the Twentieth Century

Timing: Friday, 10/Sept/2021, 3:00pm - 4:15pm

Chair: Dr. Noortje Jacobs, University of Rotterdam, the Netherlands

The Making of Modern Oncology through Faith in Science: radiation treatment and diagnostics of patients with brain tumors in Canada in the second half of 20th century

Fedir Razumenko

University of Calgary, Canada

Tracing the development of new approaches of radiation treatment and diagnostics to cerebral tumors in Canada, I investigate how local and international uncertainties of the dose, frequency, and mode of delivery of radiation found their solutions in the clinic and beyond. Since neurooncological malignancies defied therapy throughout this period, cancer clinical trials became sites of experimental research involving patients, producing ethical dilemmas for both physicians and researchers. I examine the role of new institutions, funding bodies, technological innovations, and debates over professional authority among physicians, physicists, and radiotherapists. All of these contributed to the evolution of standardizing units of radiation exposure during treatment and diagnostics. Investigators studied biological effects of radiation doses and transitioned from 'r.e.b.a.' and "rem" to "rad" and finally to Gray, the SI unit of the absorbed dose of ionizing radiation commonly used today. In this process, radiotherapy was considerably overused, and years later, the sequelae came home to haunt the patients along with clinicians. Late iatrogenics continued to be a major factor in clinical decision-making, though in the 1990s it was so because of improved cure rates and considerably increased number of long-term survivors. Consequently, radiation oncologists began considering the quality of life evolving from cancer care and cancer itself in addition to the quantity of life. Exploring developments in neurooncological clinical trials over the second half of the twentieth century, I have the objective to demonstrate how and why a cultural shift to clinical investigation that became more patient-oriented was made.

Keywords: cancer, radiation therapy, brain tumor, neurooncology

Reflections on hell, faith and miracle cures: religion and burns injury in twentieth-century Britain

Jonathan Reinarz

University of Birmingham, United Kingdom

This paper will explore the Christian religious tradition and its survival in terms of the way in which burns injuries have historically been described by the public and the press, in popular discourses, as well as medical publications and policy statements in twentieth-century Britain. It begins by considering the incident which initially caused a burns injury, not limited to Christian ceremonies involving fire. It discusses the period of treatment immediately following injury, often marked by considerable pain and debility, and described by many survivors, religious or not, as the closest they came to experiencing hell on earth.

In contrast, the latter periods of recovery and rehabilitation are less often associated with fiery landscapes and sadistic healers, but miracle cures and guardian angels. In terms of coping with recovery, patients continue to credit their religious faith or belief in God. Given the power of such imagery, depictions of purgatory recur in fire awareness campaigns. Representations of burned individuals are also associated with religious tropes, not least that of martyrs, though scarring has encouraged associations with film villains and an evil nature. As the influence of the Christian religious tradition on the ethics of burns care continues to be overlooked, this paper concludes with an exploration of the religiously inspired ethics of Dr Douglas Jackson, a leader in the field of British burns medicine, who ran the Burns Unit at Birmingham Accident Hospital (1950s-70s), was an early President of the Christian Medical Fellowship and chaired of the BMA's Central Ethics Committee.

Keywords: twentieth century, accidents, burns, Britain

Cancer Cures and Catholic Sainthood: The Case of Mother Seton and Ann Theresa O'Neill

Robin Leona Rohrer

Seton Hill University, United States of America

This paper examines the interconnection between cancer, miracle cures and the Catholic Church, focusing on the roles of physicians/nurses who participated/promoted them. After giving context to mid twentieth century miracle cancer cures, the paper focuses on the cancer cures attributed to Elizabeth Ann Seton, the first American born saint. Two miracle cancer cures, one of a woman in 1935 with pancreatic cancer, and that of Ann Theresa O'Neill, a four year old girl with leukemia in 1952, would provide the basis for Seton's elevation to sainthood in 1975. The role in particular of Sr. Mary Alice, Ann's nurse at St. Agnes Hospital, and that of her Catholic physician, Dr. John Healey are integral in the dramatic story that developed from the dying girl's bedside to the canonization of Mother Seton. Their role as witnesses, validators, and perhaps instigators, did not end with Ann's recovery, as they became the focus of popular writing and eventually the main witnesses for sainthood before the Vatican's Sacred Congregation of Rights. What other motives, although pure, might have been at play to persuade Ann's mom to accept a holy relic pinned to her daughter's hospital gown? The research for this paper includes the archives of the Sisters of Charity, Emmitsburg, Maryland, contemporary newspapers and letters, as well as medical reports from the time. Significant and inexplicable also are the reports of Dr. Sidney Farber, the "father of pediatric oncology", who could find no possible explanation for Ann's recovery from what was then a 100% fatal disease.

Keywords: cancer, leukemia, miracle cures, Catholicism

Session 10D: Fear and Epidemics in Early Modern Europe

Timing: Friday, 10/Sept/2021, 3:00pm - 4:15pm

Chair: Prof. Laurinda Abreu, University of Évora, Portugal

Chronicling Epidemics. The relation between medical knowledge and religious practices among non-medical experts in the Low Countries, 1500-1850*

Theo Dekker

Leiden University, the Netherlands

Especially with reference to the early modern period the relation between medicine and religion has often been studied as a zero-sum game, in which the 'disenchantment' of the world was a precondition for medical progress and innovation. Using digital methods to analyse a corpus of 300 handwritten chronicles from the Chronicling Novelty project led by prof. dr. Judith Pollmann and dr. Erika Kuijpers, new comparative and long-term research is possible to study the relation between religious and medical practices in the Low Countries among the middle-class. Writing a new 'history from below' by studying chronicles as collections of knowledge enables historians to study religious and medical practices not only side by side, but also in relation to each other, as well as to explore how this relation was perceived by the chroniclers. By examining both Catholic and Protestant authors from the Southern- and Northern Netherlands, this paper will present two perspectives on the changing relation between medicine and religion in the early modern period. First, the causal relation between 'divine' and 'natural' explanations for epidemics among non-medical experts. Secondly, how a group of middle-class authors used religious and medical practices simultaneously. As a result, this paper not only nuances the dichotomy between medicine and religion, but also provides insight in the how Catholics and Protestants reflected upon medical novelties in relation to their faith.

Keywords: Religion, Epidemics, Chronicles, Middle-Class, Low-Countries

Ferenc Pápai Páriz and the Western and Central European medical tradition

Endre László Kerekes

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Ferenc Pápai Páriz's work „Pax corporis” published in 1690, he created a sample of medical literature in the Hungarian language. This book has an empirical approach with several religious content. It is also noteworthy that the author discussed not only the peace of the soul, but also the peace of the body. These are inextricably linked, and he considers the healing of the body's disease as important as its soul. He rejected speculative methods and adapted his readers to natural remedies. Of particular importance is his chapter on plague, in which, in addition to empirical solutions, he also goes back to obsolete thoughts, including the miasists' theory that the main cause of the epidemic is bad air.

The aim of my lecture is to place the work of Pápai Páriz, especially his thoughts on the plague, in the context of contemporary medical theses in Western and Central Europe. I compare his theories with the methods of the doctors with whom he met during his studies or important in medical history in

* This paper is competing in the Pieter van Foreest Student Prize.

Central Europe. Among other things, I use the work of the doctor of the University of Basel, Johannes von Muralt „Kurtze und Grundlich Beschreibung der ansteckenden Pest”. On the other hand, I use the account of physician who worked in the turn of the 17-18th centuries, a Habsburg imperial military doctor Johann Christoph Ausfeldt’s text what he wrote during the plague of Szeged in 1708-1711. This work contains apocalyptic visions about the plague and medical methods against the epidemic.

Keywords: Ferenc Pápai Páriz, plague, history of plague, Johann Christoph Ausfeldt, Johannes von Muralt

Fear of Plague or a Plague of Fear? The Impact of Pestilential Fear on Medicine, Faith, and Practice during the Great Plague of Marseille, 1720*

Rita Yates

Warburg Institute, School of Advanced Study, University of London, United Kingdom

On May 25, 1720, the Grand Saint-Antoine returned to Marseille from Lebanon, transporting alongside a precious cargo of silks and cottons, a disease considered the most devastating in early modern society: bubonic plague. However, in lieu of the usual, early modern scripts attributing the collapse of the city to the misdeeds of municipal and medical authorities, some observers ascribed the downfall of the city to the spread of ‘pestilential fear.’

Philip Strong’s model of epidemic psychology posits the idea that outbreaks of disease are followed by waves of fear, panic, and suspicion. Strong’s model has two meanings. It not only refers to the social psychology of the epidemic itself – how people respond to the spread of disease – but to the fact that these responses have their own epidemic nature, and like the disease, can spread quickly. The first psycho-social epidemic is fear (collective panic), followed by explanation (theological, medical, and moral conceptions), and proposed action (control strategies), aimed at mitigating the spread of the disease itself and thereby preventing an epidemic of fear.

Taking its cue from Strong’s model, this paper examines how pestilential fear shaped Marseille’s medical and religious discourses in response to bubonic plague. In a period characterised by rapid religious decline, it discusses the extent to which theological concepts of fear, judgement, salvation, and in particular, fear of a ‘sinner’s death,’ intersected with contemporary theories of contagion - the causal relationship between theories of emotion (fear and terror), humoral imbalance, and the disease’s physical symptoms.

Keywords: Pestilential fear, plague, Marseille, sin, salvation

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Session 10E: Healing Bodies

Timing: Friday, 10/Sept/2021, 3:00pm - 4:15pm

Chair: Prof. Kaat Wils, KU Leuven

Self-injury and autonomy in early modern religious culture

Alanna Skuse

University of Reading, United Kingdom

In the middle of the seventeenth century, surgeon Hugh Ryder attended a woman who had been stabbed 'obliquely in the epigastrium'. Her case was a simple one, remedied by bleeding and medicines. It was noteworthy, however, because the woman in question had inflicted the wound herself – one of a surprising number of early modern people who required medical intervention after acts of self-injury.

This paper examines religious attitudes toward people who injured themselves in early modern Britain. Drawing on medical texts, plays and ballads, I will show that self-injury had a surprising variety of meanings in this period, all of which were coloured by religious belief. Self-wounding might evoke sympathy for a person afflicted by madness or condemnation for one attempting the sin of suicide. However, the figure of Origen also supplied a Christian blueprint for self-injury as a means of self-control, and this precedent was reflected in tales of people (both real and fictional) who injured themselves as a means of protest, persuasion, or self-expression. In contrast to the clear prohibition on suicide, religious attitudes toward such people were far from clear. The complex debate which they provoked raised far-reaching questions about the rights of individuals over their own bodies.

Keywords: suicide, surgery, medical practitioners, self-harm, psychology

'Tortured by Vermin': Parasites and Sanctity in Medieval Europe

Katherine Harvey

Birkbeck, University of London, United Kingdom

This paper explores the religious significance of bodily parasites (i.e. lice and worms) within the context of later medieval Christianity (c.1100-1500). In particular, it considers the stories of holy men and women who suffered from chronic infestations, such as Thomas Becket (whose lice-ridden hair shirt was discovered in the aftermath of his martyrdom) and Henry of Suso (who was 'tortured by vermin' for much of his life). The physical condition of such individuals provoked repugnance (since, contrary to popular belief, most medieval people were not dirty), but also reverence: parasites were often recorded in hagiographies, and were interpreted as proof of their host's sanctity.

These case studies are placed within the wider religious context, considering the contemporary association of parasites with divine punishment and with demons, as well as highlighting the long tradition of self-neglect, suffering and pain as signs of sanctity. They are also viewed through the prism of medical theory, and it is suggested that these accounts were shaped by authorial medical knowledge. It was widely believed that parasites were not caught, but spontaneously generated in or on the human body, whilst medical writers highlighted the apparent susceptibility of clerics to such

problems- a vulnerability which was linked to their adherence to pious ideals such as poor bodily hygiene and a heavily restricted diet. Whilst it has often been assumed that religion and medicine were opposing forces in the middle ages, this material thus suggests that medical knowledge was skilfully deployed by clerical writers to strengthen saintly reputations.

Keywords: Parasites, Sanctity, Asceticism, Medical knowledge

A Presence that Heals: Bodily Gestures and Words in Medieval Medicine

Fernando Salmon

University of Cantabria, Spain

In his book *The Seductions of Psychoanalysis* (CUP, 1990), the historian of science, John Forrester, points out that when psychoanalysis was created the medical profession reacted strongly against it, not because it was thought to be just foolish chatter, but because it revealed the naked essence of the healing encounter. With no instruments for diagnosis, with no prescription of drugs, a disarmed therapist makes it plain that these latter were dispensable and that the cure was himself. For the nineteenth-century physicians who advocated the new hospital and laboratory medicine, the exposure of medical practice as a form of embodied healing seemed without any doubt too dangerous in their fight for pairing their trade with that of the scientists.

They could have been less threatened though if they had taken shelter under the flag of the Western medical tradition. Some 600 years before, when medicine became one of the four branches of institutional knowledge taught and learnt at the European universities, the medical student was trained to become part of the cure by promoting trust and hope in the patient.

In my contribution to this conference, I will explore how, in the thirteenth and fourteenth centuries, a university medical model based on humoralism was able to understand physicians' gestures and words as healing devices and how it also warned about their use.

Keywords: Trust, Hope, Therapeutic relationship, Humoralism, Medieval medicine